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Acronyms

API	Application programming interfaces
AGL	Agualytics
AXA	Axaragua
B2B	Business to business
B2C	Business to consumer
B2G	Business to government
BBF	Biobased fertiliser
BioA	Bioazul
BMC	Business model canvas
BREEAM	Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CAPEX	Capital expenditures
CBM	Circular Business Model
CBMC	Circular Business Model Canvas
CE	Circular economy
CET	Cetaqua
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
COM	Consortium Meeting
COTS	Commercial Off-The-Shelf
DM	Dry Matter
DSS	Decision-Support System
EIB	European Investment Bank
EIC	European Innovation Council
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnerships

EU	European Union
EVH	Ecovillage Hanover
FTE	Full time Equivalent
GB	Gotland Bryggeri
GE	Goldeimer
HCU	Hafencity Universität Hamburg
IBC	Intermediate Bulk Container
IGZ	Leibniz Institute of Vegetable and Ornamental Crops
ICO	Instituto de Crédito Oficial
IP	Intellectual property
K	Potassium
KIT	Kompost aus Inhalten von Teckentoiletten
KWB	Kreiswerke Barnim
LCA	Life cycle assessment
N	Nitrogen
N ₂ O	Nitrous oxide
NEFCO	Nordic Environment Finance Corporation
NPK	Nitrogen, Phosphorus, Potassium
NVZ	Nitrate Vulnerable Zones
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OPEX	Operating expenses
P	Phosphorus
P.E.	People Equivalent
R&D	Research & development
ROI	Return on investment
S360	Sanitation360

SFT	Smart Fertigation Tool
SLU	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
t	ton
TD	Touch Down Gotland
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TT	Tertiary Treatment
TTP	Tertiary Treatment Plant
UDT	Urine Diverting Toilet
VH	Vagtshoff farm
VN	VunaNexus
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WP	Work Package
WRP	Water Reclamation Plant
WWTP	Wastewater Treatment Plant

1 Executive summary

Business model development around nutrient recycling is a dynamic and complex task aiming to ensure alignment between controlled organisational elements and constantly evolving legislative contexts and markets. This complexity is further heightened by the integration of circularity, which requires a broader approach to value creation than traditional viewpoints, encompassing not only economic considerations but also environmental, organisational, and financial value generation.

Under traditional circumstances, business model development occurs within a single organisation, which operates from its own distinct position within the relevant value chain. In this project, however, this perspective is expanded to encompass the entire collaborative circular system, examining not only how the participating organisations create value for their customers, but also how they create value for each other. The value creation mindset is broadened to encompass a system of organisations, who, together ensure that the common circular business model is successful both economically, as well as organisationally and environmentally for all the participating organisations and the stakeholders of the circular value chain.

The methodology to conduct business model development in this report was developed with a qualitative approach designed to exploratively obtain insights from the collaborations established in each P2Green pilot region. This approach was based on the well-established framework of Business Model Canvas (BMC) in a circular economy perspective, taking into account value creation flows across financial, organisational, and environmental levels. The methodology was abductive in nature, allowing for the integration of insights with existing knowledge within business models and circular economy, while maintaining openness to unique and unexpected findings from the data collection process. Data collection sessions were largely based on co-creation, enabling organisations both individually, in collaboration with their direct collaborating partners, and in interaction with experts from the broader consortium, to challenge assumptions and explore opportunities to be integrated into the circular business models.

The task spanned from M1-M30 of the project with the primary goal of developing three circular business models (CBM) – one for each pilot region. However, structural changes within the project led to a shift into how the pilot region partners collaborated. As a result, a fourth business model was developed to encounter these changes. Given that the business models are being developed for early-stage businesses, financing requirements have been identified, and potential funding options and sources have been analysed. Additionally, one of the pilot regions has been selected, where a specific financing structure has been laid out. This financing structure complements the qualitatively described business model elements with a quantitative suggestion on how to organise financially for a successful business model. The report is divided into different sections:

Starting with the background section, principles of the circular economy (CE) are introduced along with the concept of value which feeds into the framework of Circular Business Model Canvas (CBMC).

The following sections cover detailed descriptions of the proposed CBM. All models have been tailored so that the qualitative insights are integrated into 12 respective building blocks of the CBMC, which together make a business model successful. Each model is organised in different value dimensions covering the value proposition, value creation and delivery-, and value capture systems. The value dimensions are followed by a section devoted to financing requirements, and potential sources of funding, while the CBM are finalised in an outlook section, discussing key strengths, challenges and prerequisites to increase the possibility of a successful business model.

In total, 18 in-depth interviews were conducted as a part of D3.1, along with one preparatory mapping exercise, and two co-creative workshops, distributed over five complementary sessions. Each session had a specific focus, starting with a supply- and value chain exercise in M10, helping to map relevant stakeholders and their contributions in the collaborations. The mapped supply- and value chains acted as input for the subsequent in-depth group interviews conducted as a part of the COM held in M11 in Malaga. From here, online in-depth interviews were conducted in M17 to investigate specific elements of the CBM building blocks as preparation for the workshop conducted in M18 at the COM in Gotland focusing on revenue stream generation. While this session shed light on a range of ideas and opportunities, a large part of these relied on assumptions. Thus, the workshop conducted in M24 at the COM in Florence aimed to clarify assumptions underlying key areas of the CBM's, helping to determine the strongest and most viable routes for the business models. Lastly, individual in-depth interviews with all pilot region partners in M26 conducted online, acted as means to obtain insights into the most recent developments, and contributed to fill-in the remaining knowledge gaps of the CBM's.

2 Introduction

The current agrifood practices are based on linear nutrient management systems, based on a “take, make and dispose” approach, which are causing substantial ecological imbalances, pollution, and depletion of vital natural resources such as water and nutrients (European Commission, n.d.a; European Investment Bank & Knight, 2023). As urban populations in Europe continue to grow, the pressure on local wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) further intensifies, creating an urgent need for cities to explore alternative and more sustainable wastewater treatment solutions. Addressing these pressing issues requires a shift towards CE in which nutrients and materials are kept in their system at their highest possible value. Therefore, the European Commission adopted the new Circular Economy Action Plan in 2020 aiming to transform how resources are utilised and recycled within the European Union (EU) (European Commission, n.d.a.). Central to this strategy is the promotion of circularity throughout various sectors and across value chains ranging from production and consumption to waste management and fostering markets for secondary resources (ibid.).

As part of the focus on circularity, the European Commission has launched a wide range of different initiatives to mitigate depletion and drive a more CE within the EU. P2Green is an outcome of this work. The project stands as an initiative that aims at closing the gap between fork and farm for circular nutrient flows by examining and demonstrating innovative recovery solutions that transform human sanitary waste into safe biobased fertilisers (P2Green, 2023b).

Since 2000, the share of the EU population that is linked to wastewater treatment has consistently grown (European Environment Agency, 2024). However, reclaimed water remains underutilised in agriculture and imported mineral fertilisers continue to dominate the market, presenting an opportunity for innovation (Beneker, Gonzáles, Parfitt, & Senecal, 2023). Approximately 6 million t of nitrogen-based products are imported to the EU each year. Adding to this, EU imports app. 1 million t of phosphate fertilisers and around 2 million t of potassium fertilisers each year (European Commission, 2019).

Nonetheless vast amounts of wastewater with a high nutrient content disappear daily into the sewers of large cities. Simultaneously, agriculture uses mineral fertilisers to cultivate satisfying yields to feed a growing global population (Stewart & Roberts, 2012). Nutrients from human excreta in urban wastewater can be recovered and repurposed as valuable resources through innovative circular solutions that facilitate the recycling of nitrogen and phosphorus.

The overall objective of P2Green is to support a circular paradigm shift in the agrifood sector by reclaiming and recovering nutrients. By recovering nutrients as fertiliser for agricultural fields, the aim is to close the loop from Fork to Farm. The project thereby aims to reduce pressure on our planet’s strained ecological boundaries and address

nitrogen and phosphorus pollution by linking urban water systems with rural green spaces (P2Green, 2023b). Through three different European pilot regions, spanning from the Baltic Sea in the north, to the Mediterranean Sea in the south, P2Green showcases scalable and regionally adaptable circular solutions that contribute to sustainable food systems (P2Green, 2023b).

The CBM's, developed for each pilot region, centres around the circular archetype of resource recovery, where urine, faeces, or wastewater is recovered from the end-of-food-cycle and used as input to produce bio-based fertilisers or fertigation practices. Both the biobased fertilisers and fertigation are used in agricultural production and thereby support the creation of a sustainable food system from fork to farm.

Overview and objectives of deliverable 3.1

This deliverable sets out to develop three CBM's, one for each pilot region; Gotland in Sweden, the North German Plain, and Axarquía in Spain. The CBM's are developed using the framework of CBMC to include the environmental impact of the business models alongside the financial and organisational value arising from the collaborations of the pilot region partners.

The following objectives have guided this deliverable:

- Development of three business models, one for each pilot region
- Identification of value creation flow parameters on financial, environmental and organisational levels
- Conducted 9 in-depth interviews with pilot region partners to investigate how value creation flows are evident in the business model
- Identification of financing requirements for the pilot partners
- Analysis of funding options, and identification of suitable funding sources and financing partners
- Development of a financing structure for one pilot region

3 Methodology

3.1 Qualitative approach to drafting pilot business models

The process of developing CBM's for each pilot region was based on the CBMC and the identification of value creation flows that arise from collaboration between the partners of the pilot regions on financial, environmental, and organisational levels. With this backdrop, a qualitative approach has been developed and designed to investigate the opportunities of how the partners of the pilot regions create, deliver, and capture value through in-depth interviews.

The qualitative data collection followed an explorative and abductive approach. This was necessary given that all pilot regions are highly innovative and still in their early stages of development, thus expected to evolve significantly between M1 and M30. The explorative approach draws on elements of a co-creation process, fostering collective creativity among the partners and allowed the process to move from analysis of value creation to synthesis of business models at pilot region levels due to successive iterations (Joyce, 2015).

As the business models are developed over the course of 30 months, it was necessary to structure the data collection process in a way that would accommodate and reflect the ongoing developments for each pilot throughout this period. It was crucial to avoid bias from the outset and instead allow the collected data to guide the development of the business model, ensuring that the process remained open to emerging insights and adapted to the evolving circumstances of each pilot. This required several rounds of data collection, where previously gathered data was continuously reassessed in light of the natural development of each of the pilot regions and its different partners. Therefore, to investigate the phenomena of value creation among collaborating partners in the circular nutrient recycling chain, the approach involved iterative engagement with empirical data from the pilot regions, as well as a review of existing literature on CBM's.

The background research was informed by academic literature identified through keyword searches including terms such as *circular business models*, *nutrient recycling business models*, *sustainable/circular business model development*, *sustainable/circular/responsible business model canvas*, *value creation*, etc. The initial review was conducted using Google Scholar and the databases of the Royal Danish Library encompassing scientific publications.

3.2 Circular business model development process

The CBM's have been developed based on an extensive data collection process. Business model innovation requires a holistic view of the value being created for the stakeholders involved and affected by the operations (Bocken et al. 2014). Hence, all pilot region partners have been engaged in either individual or collective sessions throughout the project.

The data collection was structured in the following way:

- Supply- and value chain mapping
- In-depth group interviews 1: Identification of value creation flows
- In-depth group interviews 2: Structuring business model elements
- Workshop: Revenue stream generation
- In-depth group interviews 3: Assumption mapping
- Individual in-depth interviews: Completion of knowledge gaps
- Economic questionnaire serving as a scoring tool to identify for which pilot a financial structure should be developed

Each of the steps are elaborated below.

3.2.1 Supply and value chain mapping

The initial phase of D3.1 involved a comprehensive review of relevant literature with special attention to CBM's, circular archetypes, the BCM, and circular nutrient value chains. Different academic articles and publications acted as inspiration for the initial analysis of collaboration of the pilot region partners. This analysis also involved the first round of data collection consisting of a supply chain mapping exercise. The supply chain mapping exercise was separated into two parts. First, an online introductory interview was conducted with key representatives from each pilot region with a focus on collecting qualitative descriptions of how the partners perceived the circular value chains. The online interviews were conducted with organisations from all pilot regions (S360, SLU), (EVH, GE), (BioA). Second, the pilot region partners, were asked to identify key stakeholders and map the flow of physical goods in their supply chains. The exercise was conducted in September 2023 and the filled-out supply chains acted as background for the subsequent focus group interviews.

3.2.2 In-depth group interviews: Identification of value creation flows

The in-depth interviews with each pilot were conducted through group interviews during the COM in Malaga, October 2023. The interviews investigated the value creation flows between the partners. The interviews were carried out with partners from each pilot region and focused on collaboration and identification of value creation flows across organisational, financial, and environmental levels. Special consideration was given to how value creation flows become operational, and what potential flows existed in the value chains. These interviews involved organisations from all pilot regions (S360, SLU, HCU), (VN, EVH, GE, HCU), (BioA TROPS, CET, AXA, HCU).

3.2.3 In-depth group interviews: Structuring business model elements

The second in-depth group interviews were carried out with pilot region partners (S360, SLU) (KWB, VN) (KWB, GE) (BioA, TROPS, CET) in April 2024. These interviews nuanced the insights obtained from the previous interviews conducted in Malaga. The CBMC was used to structure the interviews and for each pilot region, different areas of the canvas were addressed, based on each pilot's specific context. Special attention

was given to financial value creation flows, since the insights would act as input for the subsequent workshop.

3.2.4 Workshop: Revenue stream generation

The workshop conducted during the COM in Gotland, May 2024, aimed at co-creatively discuss value capture mechanisms and identify possible revenue stream solutions for the business models of each pilot region. The workshop session was structured with an introductory presentation of common barriers, and challenges for the CBMs. This was followed by illustrative examples that acted as an attempt to draw analogies with solutions applied in other industries to solve societal problems, and 'probe' the participating experts from all partners of the P2Green consortium to develop creative input for the business models. Lastly, the key elements of the business model in each pilot region were presented, concluding with four main questions related to areas where the pilot regions lacked sufficient revenue models. The participating partners of the consortium meeting were separated into groups for interactive discussions. This workshop format provided an opportunity to share new knowledge obtained through the preceding interviews, and an opportunity to co-create solutions for the CBM's.

3.2.5 In-depth group interviews: Assumption mapping

In-depth interviews with each pilot were conducted through group interviews during the COM in Florence, November 2024. Based on the insights obtained from the previous rounds of data collection, different assumptions of the CBM's had been generated for each of the building blocks of the CBMC. The purpose of the in-depth group interviews was to confirm, deny, or adjust these assumptions. The in-depth group interviews were structured with an introductory presentation of how the CBMC had been used to create preliminary drafts of CBM's for each pilot region. From here, the collaborating partners of each pilot region respectively, were separated into groups for three rounds of assumption reviews, also involving partners from other organisations of the P2Green consortium. Each round represented one of the following building blocks from the CBMC: revenue streams, key partners, and value proposition. The rounds were initiated with a quick assumption review, followed by an assumption mapping. The output from these sessions provided insights into which elements of the CBMC are critical/necessary/not essential to the success of the business model and if they were validated/partly validated/not validated.

3.2.6 Individual in-depth interviews: Completion of knowledge gap

The last round of data collection was individual in-depth interviews with all partners from the pilot regions. The interviews were separated into two parts: one which investigated drivers for successful collaboration in circular value chains (D3.6), and the other focusing on filling in knowledge gaps in relation to value creation flows and CBM elements (D3.1). The content of each interview was context-specific revolving around either organisational, financial, or environmental value, or a specific business model building block depending on the partner being interviewed. It must be noted that this

round of data collection represented an opportunity to engage with Agualytics Data (AGL) for the first time due to an amendment of the project.

3.2.7 Economic questionnaire serving as a scoring tool to establish a financing structure for one pilot region

To evaluate financing requirements for all pilot regions and develop a financing structure for one specific pilot region, an economic questionnaire was designed to identify suitable funding sources for the pilot region. The questionnaire covers investment needs, financial planning, and the overall financial structure of the pilot. It served as a scoring tool guiding the selection of the CBM with the most elaborated figures appropriate for establishing a financing structure.

3.3 Process of data analysis

The collected data was coded for areas related to the building blocks of the CBMC as well as organisational, financial and environmental value creation for each circular value chains. The CBM and value creation flows outlined in each pilot region are based on the data collected over the 30-month period. In cases where further insights were needed on specific areas, email correspondence was initiated with the relevant partners who could provide the necessary information. Each of the partners in the three pilot regions has reviewed and approved the content of the business models, ensuring that they could quality check the accuracy of the content and status of each model.

3.4 Assessment of cost structure, finance requirements and structure

To assess the cost structures of the pilots, the data collection template developed in WP2 - responsible for producing comprehensive data collection criteria and templates - was completed by the pilot region partners and subsequently analysed. Costs were categorised into operational expenditures (OPEX) and capital expenditures (CAPEX). Due to confidentiality, specific financial figures for the cost items that constitute CAPEX and fixed and variable OPEX are not disclosed; instead, cost structures are reported in monetary amounts and percentages for CAPEX and OPEX as general cost categories, with the different cost elements elaborated in qualitative terms.

Based on an assessment of the financial data provided, a financing structure was developed for the Swedish pilot region. While creating the financing structure classic financial instruments available were considered (e.g. grants, equity, debt) as well as alternative financing sources like blended finance and crowdfunding. Two possible financing structures were developed, one for the current development stage of the pilot region and another to illustrate how the structure will need to change once the business model is more mature.

4 Background

In this section, the theoretical concepts of CE, value in business models and CBMC are introduced as the theoretical frameworks for developing the business models.

4.1 Circular economy

CE offers an alternative to the traditional linear economy, which follows a 'take, make, use & dispose' model. In a linear economy, resources are extracted from nature, used to create products, and eventually discarded as waste. This consumption pattern depletes natural resources at a rate that prevents the planet from regenerating them (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2023c). In contrast, CE ensures that resources taken from nature never turn into waste, allowing nature to regenerate.

CE is based on three core principles:

- Eliminate waste and pollution
- Circulate products and materials at their highest value
- Regenerate nature

By decoupling economic growth from the consumption of finite resources, CE addresses global challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss, waste, and pollution (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2015). This involves enabling maintenance, sharing, reuse, refurbishment, remanufacture, and recycling (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2024a).

In the context of nutrient recovery and recycling, human excreta management has traditionally followed a linear "take, make, dispose" model. Shifting toward a CE for nutrient streams require rethinking the sanitary resources to recover valuable nutrients within the system, effectively circulating the nutrients at their highest possible value.

4.2 The concept of value

Rethinking and redesigning processes serve as the premise of the business models under investigation in this report. However, the products that are developed throughout the circular value chains from the project's pilot regions must be able to prove their value and compete alongside traditional products being offered in the market.

Understanding business models begins with understanding the concept of value. At its core, value reflects the balance between the benefits an offer provides and the costs it imposes, as perceived by the customer. This balance is essential for businesses, when creating products that resonate with their audience. As stated by Amit and Zott (2012), meeting the perceived needs of the customers are crucial for successful business model innovation.

In a business context, Kotler & Keller (2016) define value as the overall evaluation of benefits and costs associated with a market offering, compared to the alternatives available to customers. Traditionally, this understanding focuses on assessing the

economic, functional, and psychological benefits of an offering against costs such as time, energy, and disposal. Businesses can increase perceived value by either raising the benefits or lowering the associated costs.

When we shift to a CE perspective, the concept of value broadens. It is no longer solely centred around financial or customer centred gains but includes environmental and social considerations. For example, reducing carbon emissions or improving resource efficiency creates value not only for businesses but also for society and the planet (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2023c).

In the context of the CBM's developed for each of the pilot regions, they are centred around a circular value chain partnership and its success relies on the collaboration and the value created within each business model, which extends beyond the flows of nutrients and the tangible product. The focus for the CBM's in the report will be broadened to encompass financial, environmental, and organisational value, setting aside equally significant social dimensions. Social aspects of the pilot region solutions are developed as part of WP2, task 2.2 and 2.3.

The following three levels of value will be investigated throughout the CBM:

Financial value refers to the monetary benefits from the offerings generated by the organisation, which is fundamental for ensuring its economic viability (Anderson & Narus, 1998, Kotler & Keller, 2016). Although the CBM's include value capture such as revenue streams and cost structures, the financial value referred to throughout the CBM's will show the financial value created among the collaborating partners in each pilot region.

Organisational value refers to non-financial factors generated through collaboration, which are beneficial to the overall success of the pilot region and competitiveness of the organisation itself (Osarenkhoe & Fjellström, 2017).

Environmental value refers to the positive impact on the environment resulting from practices that reduce carbon and overall environmental footprints, conserve natural resources, and promote sustainable value chains (Ritala, Albareda, & Bocken, 2021).

4.3 Assessment of financial, environmental and organisational value creation flows

The financial value creation flows under investigation in this deliverable focus on the monetary benefits stemming between the partners in the pilot regions. These benefits involve parameters such as cost reductions, return on investments, or similar. This approach is chosen to understand the mechanisms between the partners, since the collaborating partners in the pilot regions are dependent on each other in order to succeed with a thorough value proposition. Similarly, quantifiable, environmental value creation flows involve parameters like water savings, CO2 reductions, or other quantifiable impacts (Ellen MacArthur, 2014) stemming from the solutions that the partners propose.

While financial and environmental value creation flows often include quantitatively measurable parameters, organisational value is harder to quantify. Organisational value creation, however, plays a key role in the success of a value chain collaboration in the CBMs as they, unlike linear business models, often require greater collaboration, interaction, and interconnectedness among partners in the value chain to succeed (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2024b). While increased collaboration present challenges, such as additional touchpoints and potential bottlenecks, it can also generate organisational value measured through parameters such as capacity building, synergy effects, knowledge sharing, or decreased exposure to supply chain disruptions (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2023b).

Financial, environmental and organisational value creation flows have been identified solely between the partners, while environmental value creation flows also include value created for other societal stakeholders.

4.4 Circular business model canvas

The implementation of circularity into business model development requires a systemic shift in the core logic of how businesses operate and the alignment of incentives for stakeholders (Geissdoerfer, Pieroni, Pigosso, & Soufani, 2020). Business model development has traditionally been focused around assessing the rationale of how one organisation creates, delivers, and captures value. However, the business models for the pilot regions are for collaborating partners in a circular value chain and therefore requires a broader and innovative perspective that integrates the value creating systems of several organisations simultaneously. Furthermore, the organisations involved vary from already established businesses to start ups aiming to reach the market in the future. This diversity increases complexity of business model development due to the differences in maturity of the organisational value systems and internal processes.

A successful business model is not just about innovation, as it must also consider how it interacts with competitors and the broader market. Many business models fail because they focus solely on their own model without recognising how it fits within the industry. Successful business models, and particularly circular business models, manage to create self-reinforcing feedback loops, where each choice strengthens the overall system. Ultimately, success comes from balancing innovation with strategic positioning in the market (Casadesus-Masanell & Ricart, 2014).

The Circular Business Model Canvas (CBMC) stands as the overall theoretical and practical framework to approach the investigation of the business models. CBMC is used as a systemic approach to understand and identify how value is created and flows between the participating partners, while at the same time consider the financial, the environmental, and organisational value, which are a prerequisite for creating a successful circular business model for each of the pilot regions.

The CMBC originates from the broadly used framework, the traditional Business Model Canvas BMC, which serves as a practical tool for analysing how value is created, delivered, and captured (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). The BMC has been widely adapted to principles from CE, with several frameworks developed to support the transition from a linear to a circular economy (Lewandowski 2016; Antikainen & Valkokari, 2016; Nußholz, 2018, etc.).

The CBMC, as the theoretical standpoint of this investigation, differs from the BMC by adding another perspective: the environmental impacts both positive and negative, referred to here as environmental value creation flows. By incorporating both the positive and negative environmental impacts of the business model, environmental considerations are integrated as a part of the business model's foundation. This approach ensures that the proposed value benefits the environment while also identifying potential negative impacts. By identifying these risks early, proactive measures can be introduced to avoid or mitigate them effectively.

This expands the framework and lets sustainable impacts derived from a business model to be considered alongside the financial outcome. The CBMC, like the traditional BMC, offers a comprehensive overview of the key areas that are essential for businesses to succeed (Guldmann, 2016). By investigating the building blocks of the CBMC, it becomes possible to distinguish which aspects of the pilot region business models are still based on unvalidated assumptions and which have already been confirmed. If no areas of the business model have been validated, it indicates an immature business model with a higher degree of uncertainty regarding its success. In contrast, validated assumptions in key areas suggest a more mature and potentially successful business model (Ganguly & Euchner, 2018).

The CBMC used throughout this report consists of the original nine business model canvas building blocks including three extra building blocks consisting of environmental value creation flows, organisational value creation flows, and financial value creation flows.

Along with the original BMC, the building blocks from the CBMC can be separated into three value dimensions: value proposition, value creation & delivery, and value capture. As shown in **Table 1**, these value dimensions are linked to the building blocks from CBMC, and in broader literature on circular business models, these dimensions serve as an integrative approach, linking acknowledged business model principles from Richardson (2008) with the BMC created by Osterwalder et al. (2010) (e.g., Bocken, Rana, & Short, 2015 and Nußholz, 2018). The following section will describe each of the CBMC building blocks in this perspective.

Table 1: Building blocks separated into three value dimensions¹

Value proposition	Value creation & delivery	Value capture
Building blocks	Building blocks	Building blocks
Value proposition (1)	Key activities (5)	Revenue streams (10)
Customer segments (2)	Key resources (6)	Cost structure (11)
Customer relationships (3)	Key partners (7)	Financial value creation flows (12)
Environmental value creation flows (4)	Channels (8)	
	Organisational value creation flows (9)	

4.4.1 Value proposition

The first value dimension, the *value proposition* revolves around the value that is offered and for whom and includes the building blocks of value proposition (1) customer segments (2), customer relationships (3) and the environmental value creation flows (4).

The value proposition (1) is described as the specific bundles of products or services that create value for a specific customer segment (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). In a circular perspective the value proposition uses a circular strategy to build an offer that actively aims to preserve the economic and environmental value inherent in products and materials (Nußholz, 2017). In this relation, **customer segments (2)** are described as the different groups of people or organisations aims to reach and serve, and for whom value is created (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). To arrange the bundles of products and services, the organisation must identify which customer problems are being solved or which needs are being satisfied, to fit their value proposition correspondingly. The aggregated bundles of products and services act as the reason why specific customer segments turn to the organisation over competitors. The customer segments analysed in this report varies from niche segments to larger segments of the mass market. **Customer relationships (3)** also play an essential role within the value proposition, as it clarifies the type of customer relationship that a particular company has or should establish with the customers to foster a relationship and ensure retention and acquisition of new customers (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010; Bocken, Rana, & Short, 2015). These relationships are crucial for the overall customer experience and represent vital feedback loops that allow the pilot region partners to adapt their offerings based on the feedback they receive from their customers.

¹ Adapted from Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010; Richardson, 2008; Bocken, Rana, & Short, 2015; Nußholz, 2018

Customer relationships can be based on personal assistance, enabling of self-service, fostering of automated services, etc. These relationships are crucial not only for creating additional value for customers but also for removing barriers related to the collection of products, facilitating smoother interactions and engagement. (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010) (Nußholz, 2017).

The special focus on **environmental value creation flows (4)** is what distinguishes the CBMC from traditional business model frameworks and directs attention to aspects other than direct economic gains when capturing value. Environmental value often occurs in a closed loop chain, with the potential to be captured (Nußholz, 2017). Thus, the value propositions analysed in this report often create traditional value for customers while simultaneously providing environmental advantages to both customers and society (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2016). The environmental value creation flows unfold the environmental net positives that are created when the partners in the circular value chain collaborate, considering both the positive as well as the negative environmental impacts created.

4.4.2 Value creation and delivery

The second value dimension covers the key activities (5), key resources (6), key partners (7) and key channels (8) that constitute the *value creation and delivery* system of a business, along with the organisational value creation flows (9) that support the overall success and competitiveness of the collaborating partners.

To offer the value proposition, maintain customer relationships and make the overall business model work, the organisation must undertake a range of activities (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). These activities can be described as the **key activities (5)**, as they play an important role in both creating and delivering the potential value of the value proposition. The key activities happen both upstream, in production and in downstream processes, or involve the management of value chain activities across the stages with the goal of closing the nutrient loop (Nußholz, 2018). The **key resources (6)** represent the assets that an organisation possesses including physical (manufacturing facilities, machines, vehicles, etc), financial (cash, lines of credit, funds, etc.), intellectual (brand value, proprietary knowledge, patents, etc.), and human resources (scientists, sales force, or other skilled and knowledge intensive personnel) (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). These resources form the foundation of the key activities carried out across the value chain, are essential to create and deliver the value proposition. These assets can be either owned by the organisation or be acquired by **key partners (7)**. Networks of suppliers, distributors, or other complementors can be identified as key partners, contributing to reducing risks and optimising the business model (Richardson, 2008) (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). The key partners play a vital role in carrying out activities and supplying resources in the circular value chain. In a circular perspective, partnerships are essential when coordinating the closure of material flows, as most material flows can only be closed within a larger value chain network (Nußholz, 2017). Finally, the value propositions should be delivered to the customers through the right

channels (8). The value delivery dimension includes channels raising awareness, enabling evaluation of the offer, allowing purchase, delivering the value proposition, and providing post-purchase support. Customers can be reached through channels of the organisation or through partner channels. Finding the right balance is crucial, as owned channels have high margins but are costly to establish and operate, where partners often have competitive advantages but are offering lower margins (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010).

Throughout the described CBMC's in this deliverable at the end of the value creation & delivery building block, a description of the organisational value creation flows among the partners in the circular value chain will follow. As stated earlier, the organisational value are non-financial factors generated through collaboration, which are beneficial to the overall success of the pilot region and competitiveness of the circular value proposition provided by the collaborating partners. This is not an integrated part of the CBMC, however, the organisational value between the partners is the essence of the circular partnerships, which itself is an integrated part of the CBMC. Ecosystem partnerships and alliances are crucial for circular business models in their ability to coordinate and manage circular systems (Geissdoerfer et al., 2020). Thus, the organisational value is created among the key partners providing different key resources to perform the activities that underly the business model, and therefore this section is placed as an integral part of the CBMC.

4.4.3 Value capture

When activities, partners and channels are organised to create and deliver value, this value should be *captured* to secure the on-going operation and success of the business model. The third and last value dimension, *value capture* refers to how the organisation earns revenue through their established **revenue streams 9**), when providing customers with goods or services (Bocken et al. 2014). Compared to a linear economy, a circular approach allows several rounds of revenue stream capturing by extending the number of cycles in the life of a product (Nußholz, 2018). The revenue earned must be balanced with the expenses of the business, where the **cost structure (10)** of a business model describes the most important costs when operating activities in an organisation (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). The cost structures will be assessed through the distribution of capital expenditures (CAPEX) and the division between fixed and variable operating expenditures (OPEX) in the pilots. These costs are also affected by the **CE** as additional activities when extending the number of cycles for a material (e.g., re-collection), increases the costs. The cost structures will be focused on the economics of the technology providers, due to their critical role in ensuring balance between revenue and costs.

For a comprehensive overview, the complete CBMC is provided in Appendix 1-4.

4.5 Financing circular business models

For each of the pilot regions, funding / financing requirements of the involved parties will be identified throughout the circular value chains. The general financing environment of CE projects includes (i) barriers to entry for investors, (ii) key readiness factors for circular projects, and (iii) potential funding sources. These background topics are relevant for all P2Green pilot regions.

4.5.1 Barriers to entry for potential investors

The financing of CBM's presents unique challenges to investors, either due to longer return-on-investment periods, or the need for upfront infrastructure investments, and in the P2Green solutions also the regulatory complexities associated with waste-to-resource innovations. An overview of these barriers for investors is presented below.

Regulatory uncertainty and certification complexity

The CBM's of P2Green involve 'waste to resource' innovations, which are subject to strict environmental regulations (e.g. EU waste laws, national legislation). The legal classification of human excreta as waste may pose compliance challenges, limiting the operational scope and requiring extensive permitting processes. The lack of established certification schemes for sustainably grown crops irrigated with reclaimed water will add to the complexity.

Unclear or evolving regulatory frameworks regarding wastewater reuse and the use of bio-based fertilisers may create uncertainty around future compliance requirements and can deter investors due to perceived risks.

Market acceptance and consumer perception risks

The concept of using bio-based fertilisers requires a paradigm shift in sanitation systems and agricultural practices. The slow adoption rate and the need to build trust among farmers and consumers can delay market penetration.

Products derived from human excreta may face stigmatisation among end-consumers, particularly in the agricultural and food production sectors, posing marketing challenges.

The novelty of the product may require extensive awareness campaigns to gain consumer acceptance, which adds to operational costs.

Long investment horizon and payback periods

The CBM's of P2Green's pilot regions rely on a gradual shift in sanitation and agricultural systems, which have long turnover cycles. This slow transformation, combined with high initial investments, does not align with typical venture capital investment horizons, making it less attractive for investors seeking quick returns.

High complexity of pilots

The business models span multiple sectors (e.g. sanitation, agriculture, etc), hence the fragmented value chains require collaboration across diverse stakeholders. Coordinating the value chain increases operational complexity and poses additional risks to investors.

However, there is an inherent need in CE projects for strong collaboration among multiple stakeholders, including public authorities, private companies, and other project participants.

Capital intensity in early stages

High upfront capital expenditures for (i) infrastructure (e.g., processing facilities, toilets, collection systems, drying units), (ii) technology development, and (iii) certification processes, without immediate revenue streams can discourage investors.

Dependence on soft funding (grants and subsidies) for early-stage development may indicate higher financial risk if public funding sources are not sustained.

Technology risks

The innovative technological solutions applied in the pilot regions are still undergoing commercialisation and performance validation, making the technology a higher-risk investment.

There is uncertainty regarding the scalability and operational efficiency of the technology at larger volumes which can impact revenue generation.

Addressing these barriers will require strategic partnerships, policy advocacy, long-term financing models, and targeted awareness campaigns to build investor confidence and unlock capital.

4.5.2 Key funding readiness factors

To secure financing for the final development stage (growth and scale-up phase) of the CBM's, several key funding readiness factors must be addressed. These factors signal to potential investors and financing partners that the business model is mature, scalable, and capable of delivering both financial returns and positive environmental impact. The following funding readiness factors are crucial:

Proven technology, certification and performance validation

- **Demonstrated Effectiveness:** The applied technologies (e.g. urine stabilisation and drying systems) must have undergone successful pilot tests with verifiable results on nutrient retention, product quality, and operational efficiency.

- Scalability Assessment: Evidence that the technologies can be scaled without significant loss of efficiency or performance through independent third-party verification of system performance.
- Official third-party certification of agricultural products to validate environmental benefits, product safety and quality.
- Clear labelling strategies to improve market visibility.

Regulatory compliance

- Permitting and Licensing: Obtain necessary permits for waste collection, transportation, and fertiliser production.
- Compliance with Waste Regulations: Demonstrate adherence to EU and national/local waste management laws.

Clear business model and value proposition

- Market Validation: Evidence of demand from early customers (e.g., farmers, municipalities) and positive feedback on product quality and service delivery. Secured supply agreements or letters of intent from retailers.
- Revenue Model: A transparent revenue structure demonstrating how each part of the value chain contributes to overall business profitability.
- Competitive Advantage: Clear differentiation from mineral fertilisers or competing circular solutions, such as higher nutrient content, environmental benefits, or cost-efficiency.

Market readiness and strategic partnerships

- Partnership Agreements: Formal collaborations with key partners along the value chain.
- Distribution Channels: Identified and tested distribution channels for the biofertiliser and other by-products.
- Consumer Acceptance: Positive consumer perception and marketing campaigns to overcome stigmatisation of urine-based products. Community engagement initiatives to foster social acceptance.

Financial track record and projections

- Financial Performance: Transparent financial reporting with a track record of revenue streams from sanitation services, product sales, or subsidies.
- Cash Flow Management: Clear cash flow projections showing how operational costs will be covered during the scale-up phase.

- **Co-Financing Ability:** Ability to secure co-funding from public grants, demonstrating confidence and support from public institutions.
- Detailed business model with revenue forecasts, risk mitigation strategies, and scalability pathways.

Impact measurement and sustainability credentials

- **Environmental Impact Metrics:** Quantifiable data on nutrient recycling, CO₂ reduction, and contribution to CE targets.
- **Sustainability Certification:** External certifications or alignment with EU Taxonomy or other sustainability frameworks.
- **Social Impact:** Community engagement and education, contribution to local sustainability goals.

Risk mitigation strategy

- **Regulatory Risk:** Clear roadmap on how regulatory barriers (e.g., EU waste law) are being addressed and any anticipated regulatory changes.
- **Technology Risk:** Risk-sharing mechanisms (e.g., performance guarantees or insurance) to reassure investors.
- **Business Continuity Plan:** Strategies to maintain operations if one revenue stream underperforms (e.g., diversified revenue sources or public-private partnerships).

Governance and management capacity

- **Professional Management Team:** Experienced leadership with technical and business development expertise.
- **Advisory Board:** External experts advising on regulatory, technological, and market developments.
- **Operational Capacity:** Internal capacity to manage the scale-up process and maintain consistent product quality.

Investors and financing partners will prioritise projects that combine technical viability, market readiness, and financial track record. Addressing these funding readiness factors will not only improve access to financing but also strengthen the overall business case for the CBM's. A summary of necessary measures for each pilot region is provided in each dedicated chapter.

4.5.3 General funding options

To address the financing needs of each key stakeholder, multiple funding options are considered. These include public grants, private investments, and innovative financing models. Breaking these down further, public grants provide crucial early-stage support, private investments help scale proven models, and innovative financing mechanisms such as blended finance can bridge gaps between different funding needs:

- **Crowdfunding and crowd investing** allow businesses to raise capital from a large number of individuals, through public participation through online platforms, making them suitable for early-stage development and commercialisation, awareness-building and initial product rollouts. Particularly for projects with strong public engagement potential.
- **Grants and subsidies** are non-repayable funds provided by governments and organisations, primarily supporting research, development, and pilot-stage initiatives before commercial viability is achieved.
- **Equity** financing, including venture capital and angel investment, is typically used for early-stage businesses (proof-of-concept and commercialisation stages) that require capital to develop and scale innovative solutions.
- **Venture capital:** Private equity financing provided to early-stage companies with high growth potential, often in exchange for equity stakes.
- **Non-VC private Investment:** Impact investors, mission-driven funds, and strategic partners who understand the long-term market transformation required for adoption.
- **Public-private partnerships (PPPs)** enable collaboration between government bodies and private entities to share investment risks and rewards, often facilitating scaling and long-term infrastructure investments, to co-finance demonstration projects that can lead to long-term adoption.
- **Blended finance models** combining concessional finance with commercial finance to reduce investment risks and attract private capital.
- **Revenue-based Financing** includes alternative financing structures that allow gradual repayments based on revenue growth rather than fixed returns.
- **Impact investment** combined with different funding sources can maximise both environmental and financial returns, playing a crucial role in bridging the financing gap at both commercialisation and scale-up stages.

- **Debt** financing, such as loans and bonds, is often used for scaling operations and infrastructure investments in later development stages, once revenue streams are established.
- **Concessional loans:** Loans offered at below-market interest rates, often backed by public institutions or development banks to support sustainability projects.
- **Sustainability-Linked loans:** Loans where the interest rate is linked to the borrower's achievement of pre-defined sustainability performance targets.
- **Green bonds:** Fixed-income instruments designed to raise capital for projects with environmental benefits.

The most suitable funding sources and financing partners for each pilot region will be laid out in each dedicated business model.

5 Circular business model: Gotland pilot region

5.1 The potential of Gotland

In the P2Green project, the Swedish pilot region showcases a local circular solution in which value chain partners and the collection, production and distribution of resources are on Gotland. Gotland is Sweden's largest island located in the Baltic Sea, about 90 km east of Småland. While sparsely populated, the island is a popular destination for tourists and tourism along with agriculture represent the largest sources of economic activities (Britannica, 2025; Danmarks Nationalleksikon, Valeur, et al., 2024).

Agricultural activities generate 2.7 billion SEK annually (approx. 250 million EUR) and employing 10% of the workforce with 31% of the land cultivated (primarily for cattle feed). Key agricultural output from Gotland includes lamb, vegetables, and grain, dominated by wheat and barley (Rethink Action, n.d.; Britannica, 2025).

The island faces severe water shortages due to low groundwater levels and rising sea levels, which threaten land through erosion and groundwater salinisation. Additionally, Gotland is located in the Baltic Sea's "dead zone," where low oxygen levels are a significant problem in the offshore waters. Nutrient pollution from activities such as agricultural runoff, wastewater, and industrial discharges has expanded the affected areas and intensified eutrophication and oxygen depletion (ibid.; Conley et al., 2011). Over the past 110 years, the Baltic Sea dead zones have expanded from 5,000 km² to 60,000 km² (Carstensen, Andersen, Gustafsson, & Conley, 2014)

5.2 Introduction to the pilot region

The Swedish pilot region collects urine from toilets and urinals in both rural and urban areas, as well as from public and private buildings. By using an innovative technology, the urine is processed into a dry fertiliser designed to integrate with conventional farming equipment (Beneker, Gonzáles, Parfitt, & Senecal, 2023). The reclaimed nutrients from the urine are currently used to fertilise barley cultivation and Gotland's Bryggeri - a partner in the pilot - uses the barley to brew beer, thereby closing the loop in the circular solution for resource utilisation.

The Swedish pilot integrates sanitation and waste management practices to avoid that the urine enters into the sewage system, thereby mitigating coastal pollution and implications of eutrophication. Additionally, the pilot contributes to solving pressing issues such as nitrogen and phosphorus pollution from agricultural use of mineral fertilisers and inefficient decentralised sewage systems. Seasonal nutrient load peaks, driven by tourism, currently exacerbate eutrophication in both ground and surface water, making this initiative important for improving environmental conditions on Gotland. The Swedish pilot therefore aims to reduce local and global environmental challenges while developing a financially sustainable business model.

At this point, the urine fertiliser production process is still in development (TRL 6) but progressing towards larger-scale implementation. Initially, stabilised urine was

processed at around 60 litres per day, with energy availability being the main limiting factor. To address this, new systems are being developed to use waste heat from a cement factory and exhaust heat recovery, these were tested in winter 2024. Hushållningssällskapet, an independent agricultural advisory organisation, is currently conducting barley field trials on Gotland using the dry urine fertiliser (Beneker et al., 2023).

Additionally, research is ongoing into pelleting the fertiliser and removing micropollutants from the urine input. While these experiments are still at a start-up stage, they use existing technologies adapted for urine treatment, with plans to integrate them before the P2Green project ends. A recent study has also shown promising results in reducing pharmaceutical residues using UV treatment ensuring a high-quality safe fertiliser (Beneker et al., 2023)

The Swedish pilot involves the following partners: S360, SLU, GB and TD. Although this CBMC focuses on the operations and value chain actors of the Gotland pilot region, it is relevant to notice that the circular value chain and solution is created with the intention to scale urine-based fertiliser production to support sustainable agriculture in alignment with global efforts to transform food production systems, recycle nutrients and promote resilient agricultural practices (Beneker et al., 2023). By the end of 2026, the Swedish pilot aims to collect 150 m³ of urine, reclaiming an estimated 900 kg of nitrogen and 90 kg of phosphorus annually (Beneker et al., 2023). Moreover, by 2026, the goal is to produce commercially available beer, completing the value chain and serving as a proof of concept. This will demonstrate to other food and beverage producers that S360's fertiliser is a viable solution, paving the way for a wider range of crops to be fertilised with urine. (Beneker et al., 2023). Urine based fertilisers are legal to market in Sweden, however they must be certified to be commercialised (Beneker et al., 2023). S360 is currently raising funds for certification. Lastly, S360's operations are currently based in Gotland, Uppsala, and Malmö, with plans to expand urine collection over the next three years to other regions in Sweden and neighbouring countries like Norway (Beneker et al., 2023).

Figure 1 illustrates the circular supply chain, showing the transformation of urine from a wasted resource into beverages ready for consumption, thereby closing the loop from farm to fork.

Figure 1: Circular supply chain for the Swedish pilot

The model below (Figure 2) illustrates the value creation flow parameters between the partners. A monetary flow has been added to the model to represent hypothetical internal financial flows as a part of the possible revenue streams. It further illustrates financial value creation flows between the partners, which consists of either direct economic gains from participating in the circular value chain or potential financial flows that serve as revenue streams for the individual organisations. There are currently no financial flows stemming between the partners, meaning that the visualized revenue streams are hypothetical. Since the model only pertains to the partners, revenue streams from external customers and stakeholders are not represented. The flows are further elaborated in specific sections devoted for these topics.

Financial value creation flow

Monetary flow

Organizational value creation flow

Environmental value creation flow

Figure 2: Value creation flow parameters between partners in the Swedish pilot region

In the following section the assumptions and decisions made when developing the business model is described. Following this, the CBMC is described through its building blocks: *value proposition*, *value creation & delivery*, and *value capture*. Additionally, the organisational, financial, and environmental value creation flows are explored and integrated throughout the business model.

5.3 Assumptions and decisions

The following decisions and assumptions have been made for the development of the CBMC. The full circular business model canvas is illustrated in Appendix I: Circular Business Model Canvas: Gotland Pilot Region.

- The business model is made with a main focus on S360, as S360 is the main provider of the circular solution. S360's bio-based fertiliser is the link connecting partners, that already exist in the marketplace, and S360 is critical to the success of the circular business model.
- The value chain partnership and disruptive technology is not yet mature enough to have a fully implemented business model. This is due to areas of the value chain that is not yet finally materialised, namely the collection of urine and selling the final products to customers based on crops fertilised by S360's fertiliser. The CBMC and value creation flows described in the CBMC therefore present the envisioned business models and supporting buildings blocs, demonstrating how the technology and partnerships can evolve to develop viable circular business models.

- Due to the maturity of the fertiliser on the market some of the areas in the business model are based on assumptions made by the pilot partners. Moreover, some information is confidential and are therefore not described in full in the business model's cost structure which has been drafted from the data input provided by S360.
- Since the business model has not yet reached a maturity level where its products are being marketed revenue streams are based on planned, envisioned, and potential revenue opportunities.
- Throughout the business model, when environmental claims are made these may not be used for communication purposes unless these are documented, for example through a life-cycle analysis or similar documentation. Focus of this deliverable is the business models of the pilots, whereas work package 2 documents the environmental impact of the pilot regions.

5.4 Value proposition

The value proposition consists of five distinct value propositions that serve different customer segments both upstream and downstream provided by the pilot region value chain partners S360, TD, and GB.

It should be noted that a lifecycle analysis (LCA) must be done to document the impact of the value propositions described below before marketing either of the value propositions as sustainable, low environmental impact or similar. An LCA study will be performed in P2Green under work package 2 (D 2.3).

Table 2: Value proposition, Gotland pilot region

	Value proposition	Value created for customer segment
Upstream	Sanitation services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eco-friendly sanitation with urine collection for festivals and events. • Inclusive design with male, female, and unisex urinals. • Improved user experience through enhanced privacy and comfort. • Supports circular sanitation and strengthens sustainability branding.
Upstream	Urine treatment service (stabilisation and collection of urine)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficient and sustainable urine disposal for sanitation providers and municipalities.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Odor reduction and urine stabilisation through an innovative chemical treatment. • Simplifies waste management by replacing the need for customer-handled waste disposal. • Supports nutrient recycling and enhances environmental sustainability. • A cost alternative to public sewer disposal fees.
Upstream	Drying system services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small- and large-scale drying system installations, for local or commercial utilisation of urine • Converts urine into a marketable fertiliser. • Reduces environmental impact and contributes to regional food resilience. • Provides a sustainable, locally sourced fertiliser for personal use.
Production	Bio-based fertiliser	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy integration that is compatible with traditional farming equipment, eliminating the need for new machinery. • Supports efficient crop production while reducing environmental footprint and nitrogen emissions. • Improved food production resilience in times of crisis.
Downstream	Low environmental impact beer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Beer made with barley grown with urine-based fertiliser, reducing environmental impact. • Combines high-quality ingredients with eco-friendly barley for an enjoyable consumer experience. • Potentially offers a white-label beer option to promote urine recycling directly on the product.

Sanitation services, upstream

The first value proposition builds on TD's sanitation service capabilities to create value for festivals, events and other venues. At the first step of the circular nutrient value chain, TD provides sustainable sanitation solutions which include installation and maintenance of portable urinals and toilets, along with urine collection, ensuring a seamless eco-friendly waste management solution.

During the project, the partners have encountered issues related to the design of the female urinals, wherefore S360 are currently designing a retrofit unisex urinal. The new unisex urinal design improves privacy and user experience by introducing seating urinals. This innovation enhances comfort while being able to collect more urine to be recycled.

Festivals and event-owners benefit from a stronger environmental image, which helps them stand out in a competitive market, while contributing to a circular sanitation system.

Urine treatment service, upstream

The urine treatment service represents a value proposition offered by S360 towards sanitation service providers, such as TD. A prerequisite for this value proposition is to divert the urine into a separate flow which naturally occurs with urinals. To scale the volumes of urine collected, it might be necessary to invest in a separate vacuum pump (costs elaborated under cost structure). Whether to integrate this as a part of the urine treatment service of S360 or rely on the sanitation provider to undertake these activities are still to be decided.

However, at the core of this service is S360's innovative chemical stabiliser, a powder applied directly to urine collection tanks of the sanitation service provider, to initiate treatment, reduce odours, and simplify handling. When the chemical stabiliser and urine is mixed, the treatment is initiated, from where S360 manages the collection and transportation of the stabilised urine, entailing that the need for customers to handle disposal themselves is eliminated.

This solution serves as an alternative to costly and inefficient urine disposal, currently managed by public waste systems like the Region of Gotland. It enables customers to recycle nutrients, lower environmental impact, and enhance their sustainability profile, which can improve competitiveness, rather than wasting a nutrient resource.

Additionally, S360 has experienced interest directly from the organisers of different events, inquiring the possibility of having urine collected from their venues. Thus, the urine treatment service can also be limited to mere collection of urine thereby creating a reduced environmental impact of the specific event.

Drying system services, upstream

Another value proposition consists of a drying system developed in collaboration by SLU and S360, with associated services performed by S360. While not currently implemented as a separate offering in the Swedish pilot region, the drying system technology contains the potential to create value for sanitation providers or building owners. The value proposition can be designed around, either a small-scale family unit, or a larger scale installation.

For sanitation providers, the drying system allows them to concentrate and dry the urine without any interaction with S360, by renting or purchasing the system. In one scenario, they will be able to sell the output from the drying process as a liquid urine-based fertiliser themselves, thereby turning an otherwise wasted resource into financial profits. Alternatively, S360 will offer to collect the dried urine, turn it into pellets and be responsible for the marketing activities. Here, customers are released from the burdens related to selling the fertiliser, and experience benefits due to the reduced costs of urine disposal. A potential in this scenario is similarly to compensate the sanitation service provider financially for their efforts of drying and concentrating the urine.

For public buildings (or other venues such as sports arenas) the drying system would be installed permanently, meaning that urine will be concentrated and dried at the point of collection. This improves efficiency, by eliminating the need for transportation of fresh urine over longer distances, while it will reduce the environmental impact from the venue. Additionally, one potential client has also highlighted the value of contributing to support food resilience in the region, with their local supply of nutrients.

For private homes, the drying system could generate a locally sourced urine-based fertiliser that is able to be applied directly in the garden of the drying system owner.

Bio-based fertiliser, production

The fourth value proposition introduces a circular bio-based (urine) fertiliser designed to create value for farmers or hobby gardeners. Developed as a *turnkey* granulised solution, the fertiliser is compatible with traditional farming equipment, allowing integration into existing practices without requiring costly investments in new machinery.

For farmers, the fertiliser not only supports efficient crop production but also reduces their environmental footprint by minimising emissions of reactive nitrogen, a significant contributor to greenhouse gas emissions. This environmentally friendly approach enhances the farmer's public image and may open opportunities to sell their crops at premium prices and cater to new customer segments. Additionally, recent times of crisis has increased the focus on food production resilience, with this urine-based fertiliser posing as a local nutrient source to reduce dependence on global fertiliser markets.

Hobby gardeners benefit similarly, as the use of this fertiliser helps reduce greenhouse gas emissions while supporting sustainable gardening practices.

Low environmental impact beer, downstream

The fifth value proposition consists of a low environmental impact beer produced by Gotland Bryggeri (GB) from barley grown with urine-based fertiliser. There is no difference in taste of the malt compared to malt using other types of fertilisers. Thus, barley grown from urine-based fertiliser can be incorporated into production in the same way as the current ingredient. However, one essential element to enhance the value created from the value proposition, is to design the beer with special features. It should deliver a full package of beer-related experience for its customers, rather than just relying on promoting that the barley was grown from urine-based fertiliser. This entails that the beer will have a great diversified taste, based on special and quality ingredients with barley grown with urine-based fertiliser, and thereby position itself as a premium low environmental impact beer. Currently, GB produces a product line, the bull-dog series, already containing an eco-beer which poses as an obvious candidate for integration of the new malt. Negotiations with GB are ongoing, whether to rely on production of a standard beer catering to larger customer segments or relying on speciality versions catering to niche segments.

Another version of this value proposition could potentially be a white-label solution where S360 utilises GB's production capabilities. This type of arrangement will allow S360 to market the beer under their own brand, and promote urine recycling among the consumers, illustrating the full story directly at the bottle or can of beer.

It must be acknowledged that to ensure consumer acceptance, and to promote the beer as having a low environmental impact, life-cycle assessments must support these assumptions.

5.4.1 Customer segments

The business model offers four value propositions which provide value for different customer segments, as described in the **Table 3** below.

Table 3: Customer segments, Gotland pilot region

Customer segments	
Sanitation services catering to festival- and event-owners, construction sites and other public venues	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Need for cost-effective, reliable, and sustainable sanitation solutions to manage waste efficiently.• Prioritise sustainability and reputation, seeking solutions that minimise environmental impact without complicating operations.• Require hygienic, practical sanitation facilities that comply with regulations and welfare standards for attendees and workers.
Urine treatment service catering to sanitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Need for an effective and cost-efficient urine disposal option

<p>service providers, and event-owners.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seek sustainable waste management practices to enhance their environmental image.
<p>Drying system services to sanitation service providers, and stadiums, airports, camping sites, existing urine diverting housing complexes and other permanent installations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Require high-capacity, reliable technology to handle peak usage. • Seek sustainable waste management to enhance environmental initiatives and attract eco-conscious customers.
<p>Bio-based fertiliser to conventional farmers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need a dry granular fertiliser that integrates seamlessly with existing equipment and farming practices. • Require high-quality fertiliser that enhances crop growth, reduces emissions, and improves market differentiation. • High-volume demand but price-sensitive
<p>Bio-based fertiliser to hobby gardeners</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More flexible on pricing, paying per kilo rather than per ton. • Seek eco-friendly fertilisers that support soil health without harmful chemicals. • Willing to pay premium prices for documented sustainable cultivation benefits.
<p>Low environmental impact beer catering to Environmentally conscious consumers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local pride in Gotland, Consumers seek products that support the regional nutrient value chain and local businesses. • Vacation experience, non-local consumers associate Gotland with vacation, desiring products that evoke this connection. • Environmentally conscious, Expect sustainable production and premium taste with high-quality ingredients like hops. • Willing to pay a premium for a small-scale, locally produced beer that aligns with their values of quality and sustainability.

Sanitation services catering to festival- and event owners, construction sites and other public venues

Target customer segment is organisers of festivals, events, and construction sites who need cost-effective, reliable, and sustainable sanitation solutions. These organisers face the challenge of managing waste efficiently while ensuring a positive experience for attendees or workers while meeting environmental commitments.

Many event organisers prioritise sustainability and reputation, seeking solutions that minimise environmental impact without increasing operational complexity. Similarly, site managers require hygienic and practical sanitation facilities that comply with regulations and welfare standards.

Urine treatment services catering to sanitation service providers and event-owners

Following provision of urinals and toilets at various events, sanitation service providers seek an effective and cost-efficient option to dispose of the collected human excreta. Currently, agreements with the public water authority are established, meaning that representatives from the region pick up the urine at a cost for traditional wastewater treatment at the local WWTP. Thus, the urine treatment services target sanitation service providers that value environmentally friendly practices and wish to contribute to circular nutrient economy.

As mentioned above, the services can also be limited to the mere pick up of intermediate bulk containers containing urine. S360 has experienced demand directly from event-organisers who are responsible for sanitation at their specific events. Thus, the target customers of this value proposition are expanded beyond sanitation providers and also include event organisers with their own toilet facilities.

Drying system services catering to stadiums, airports, camping sites, existing urine diverting housing complexes and other permanent installations

The above-mentioned locations share the common characteristic that they experience continuous or high-volume usages at peak times, making reliable and high-volume waste management essential. For this customer segment the drying system service offers an alternative to traditional sewage connection to enhance their environmental initiatives and thereby enhance their environmental image. S360 is actively pursuing partnerships to install the urine concentrator technology in fixed locations over the coming years and are in dialogue with local governments, high-profile event organisers, airports, and residential communities equipped with urine diversion systems, all aimed at serving eco-conscious event planners and their audiences (Beneker et al., 2023). A prerequisite for the drying system to create value for these target customers is installation of UDTs to enable urine to enter the drying system separately. To drive adoption among households, financial support from the municipality in the form of price subsidies has been proven as an effective tool in developing countries (Otoo et al. 2018). This will help increase the volumes of urine to be used for fertiliser production, as it has already been separated directly in the toilet.

Bio-based fertiliser catering to conventional farmers

In Sweden, regulations permit the use of urine as fertiliser in conventional agriculture. This enables S360 to offer its urine-based fertiliser to conventional farmers, initially targeting those in Gotland, with the potential to expand beyond Gotland and across Sweden. Although organic farmers have shown the greatest interest in using this fertiliser, current EU organic farming regulations prohibit its use (Beneker et al., 2023).

Farmers require a dry granular formulation that is compatible with conventional farming equipment and practices. They need a high-quality fertiliser that supports robust crop growth, reduces emissions associated with production, and enhances the market differentiation of their produce, potentially enabling them to secure premium prices. Being commercial farmers there is a high-volume demand expressed by farmers (Beneker et al., 2023). Additionally, farmers are highly price sensitive as they operate in a competitive market. This makes scalability and cost efficiency critical considerations.

Bio-based fertiliser catering to hobby gardeners

To address above mentioned challenges in relation to the farmer customer segment, S360 must also target hobby gardeners. Whereas the farmers pay per ton, hobby gardeners pay per kilo and are therefore assumed to operate under greater price elasticity concerning fertilisers. With a fertiliser that documents soil cultivation without harmful chemicals, environmentally conscious hobby gardeners might be willing to pay premium prices.

Low environmental impact beer catering to environmentally conscious consumers

The target customer segment demands a low environmental impact beer that aligns with their values and regional connections. Consumers in Gotland seek products that support the local nutrient value chain and businesses, reflecting their patriotic commitment to the region. Meanwhile, consumers from other parts of the country associate Gotland with a vacation experience and desire products that evoke feelings of an escape from everyday life. In general, the beer is designed for environmentally conscious consumers who prioritise sustainability.

The customer segment consists of consumers with different levels of price-sensitivity. GB's small scale local production enhances its premium status, with regular customers who are assumed to be less price sensitive. Consumer sensitivities regarding the fertiliser's origin must be carefully managed by emphasising the beer's role in a circular economy, its local production and its low environmental impact rather than highlighting its unconventional fertilisation process.

These consumers may be willing to pay higher prices if the product delivers a complete package of benefits. They expect exceptional taste, provided by quality ingredients such as premium hops, as well as sustainable production practices – in this case this include

using a low environmental impact fertiliser for barley cultivation. Ultimately, the goal is to offer a high quality, eco-friendly beer that justifies a premium price by delivering an extraordinary overall experience of the beer among premium, sustainability-oriented consumers.

5.4.2 Customer relationship

As customers are crucial for TD, S360 and GB, this section explores the customer relationships and clarifies the type of customer relationships that TD, S360 or GB want, have or should establish for each of the above-mentioned customer segments to foster.

Sanitation service – automated service relationship

As the sole provider of sanitation services on Gotland, TD benefits from the absence of direct competition, however, maintaining high customer satisfaction remains essential for long-term success.

The customer relationship structured around the sanitation services offered by TD is characterised as an automated service relationship. Upon request, TD delivers and installs the needed sanitation options for its clients, allowing the customers to experience a smooth service with a complete solution from installation to disposal of urine. TD may retain customers by ensuring reliable, hassle-free and efficient service. This could include providing proactive support, and tailoring solutions to individual needs. A commitment to sustainability and continuous improvement through customer feedback could potentially strengthen long-term relationships.

Urine treatment services - personal assistance relationship

The relationship between S360 and the customers of their urine treatment service mainly contains characteristics of a personal assistance relationship. The sanitation providers, such as TD, will make S360 aware of their presence at a festival or an event, and arrange when the urine will be ready for collection. An employee from S360 will appear at the venue and be able to communicate directly with the sanitation provider, thereby contributing to maintaining a close and reliable relationship to retain the customer. When ready for collection, S360 transports the urine to their production facility, ensuring a convenient experience for the customer.

Drying system services - automated service relationship

For the customers of permanent installations of the drying system, the relationship will be based on a more automated service relationship. Ideally, the service will entail scheduled collections of urine on an automated basis, meaning that the process will be fully automated after installation of the system. This is a contributing factor in acquiring new customers due to perceived convenience through the minimal effort required of the customer when the process is up and running. Similarly, scheduled maintenance could be integrated to complement the relationship with personal assistance through maintenance contracts.

Bio-based fertiliser – dedicated personal relationship / self-service relationship

When providing customers with urine-based fertilisers, S360 can structure the relationships in different ways. For farmers, the establishment of a dedicated personal relationship will allow S360 to communicate directly to the customer on the use of the fertiliser. This will also create an opportunity to receive feedback on the functionality of the fertiliser and obtain insights into potential ways to improve the offering, to retain the customers. GB already possess strong relationships with a local farmer, through which they might be able to provide convincing arguments to change fertiliser practices.

The relationship with hobby gardeners will be indirect since S360 will not be in direct contact with the customer segment, due to sales activities being performed by relevant retailers. However, it would be beneficial to structure the relationship as a self-service relationship where the hobby gardeners are provided with all the necessary means (user-guides, product information, etc.) to help themselves in the use-phase. However, it must be acknowledged that education of the retailer distributing the product is a vital factor to support them in their advice toward the customers and thereby contribute to acquire new customers and boost sales.

Low environmental impact beer - personal assistance relationship

The type of relationship between GB and its customers is mainly characterised as a personal assistance relationship. By offering the beer at the local brewery in Gotland, the personnel of GB can influence the customer experience by communicating directly with the customer and provide information about the sustainable production process of the beer. Thereby, human interaction creates an opportunity to attract curious customers to try the beer. Additionally, GB possesses an already established and recognised beer brand, meaning that customers associate the brand with high-quality beer. Thus, the brand plays a vital role in the customer relationship to retain customers, and in boosting the sales of newly introduced products. This is especially evident in cases when beer is distributed through retailers where GB does not engage directly with their customers.

5.4.3 Environmental value creation flows

S360, as the technology and fertiliser provider, enables a flow of environmental value creation across partners, including value creation for internal partners such as TD and GB as well as external partners such as farmers, festivals, and municipalities. Each partner plays a role in the circular value chain and thereby in reducing environmental impacts through their interconnected activities.

From S360 and TD to GB

The environmental value flowing towards GB is a result of the full value chain collaboration, where GB incorporate barley grown with urine-based fertilisers into its

production. This reduces the brewery's supply chain emissions while being able to provide a low impact beer, expanding the environmental value generated to end consumers.

From S360 to TD

By receiving and treating urine from TD, S360 prevents the nutrients collected by TD from reaching wastewater treatment plants and ultimately entering waterways. This reduces the environmental impact of TD's operations, creating a flow of environmental value from S360 to TD.

From the pilot region to the region of Gotland

Reducing urine disposal into WWTPs are expected to create environmental benefits for Gotland by minimising nutrient discharge into wastewater systems. However, it is important to note that the quantification of the environmental benefits is subject to the LCA investigations conducted in WP2. Recycling the urine reduces pressure on the local WWTPs and avoids the discharge of nutrients to the aquatic ecosystems. Preventing nutrients from being discharged to water bodies helps mitigate eutrophication and the emergence of dead zones.

The improvement in natural water reservoirs is expected to enhance the region's ecosystems, representing a flow of environmental value from all stakeholders toward the region of Gotland, thereby supporting the municipalities to meet their climate and sustainability goals.

Additionally, conventional nitrogen removal processes at WWTPs contribute to greenhouse gas emissions, as nitrogen is often released as nitrous oxide, a potent greenhouse gas (Peters & Thompson, 2020). According to a study by Badeti et al. (2024), decentralised wastewater treatment with urine separation resulted in a 13% reduction in GHG emissions compared to traditional wastewater treatment systems.

By adopting nutrient recycling technologies, Gotland can reduce these emissions, aligning with broader sustainability goals while enhancing the region's environmental condition to the better.

While the collaboration in the value chain offers nutrient recycling with great benefits, potential environmental drawbacks require further investigation.

Potential environmental negative impacts may include pharmaceutical residues (for the micro-biome of the soil), energy use in processing, and transportation of urine and fertilisers. Further the environmental impacts depend on the choice of stabiliser, as some stabilisers have a greater environmental footprint than others. However, this issue is considered simple to address by switching to low impact stabilisers.

Additionally, an environmental concern in the manufacturing process is energy use, but efforts are considered by the pilot region to mitigate this by using waste, solar or wind energy.

It is important to note, that the environmental positive and negative impacts for the pilot will be assessed in depths in WP2, task 2.3, through a lifecycle assessment of environmental impacts.

5.5 Value creation and delivery

5.5.1 Key activities

The value chain includes urine collection, fertiliser production, barley fertilisation, and beer production. The key activities are categorised into upstream, production, and downstream activities, with fertiliser production as the core focus.

The commercialisation of bio-based fertiliser depends on two key types of technology. The first is urinals, such as those provided by TD, and toilets installed with urine-diverting retrofits, to enable urine collection. The second is the urine drying technology, where excreted urine is directed into a cassette that treats and concentrates it. Both technologies are included as R&D activities in collaboration between SLU and S360, which occurs before the circular value chain is initiated.

Upstream

A vital aspect of the upstream activities is enabling logistics and collection of the urine from festivals and other events. Upon requests from festivals and events, TD informs S360 about their upcoming setup at the given event, to coordinate collection following the event, and the exchange of chemical stabiliser. S360 produces a chemical urine stabiliser, which is placed in a urine collection tank to retain nutrients and control odours. The collection tank is delivered to the sanitation provider, in this scenario TD, who provides urinals at festivals and events. While TD already provide urinals, S360 are currently designing a unisex retrofit to be incorporated to their existing toilet boxes to increase willingness of both genders to use urinals. TD stores the urine in the collection tank containing the chemical urine stabiliser on-site. Due to the chemical stabiliser, the urine treatment process is initiated on site, before S360 collects the stabilised urine and transports it to the production facility.

To support the drying system value proposition, an essential upstream activity is sourcing the right components for future production of drying systems when this part of the business model is scaled. This approach will be based on a COTS (Commercial Off-The-Shelf) strategy, providing S360 with flexibility in production and the ability to deliver customised solutions tailored to customer needs.

Production

At the production facility, the stabilised urine is dried to increase its concentration. This drying technology has been developed collaboratively by S360 and SLU. Initially, the stabilised urine is concentrated using a specially designed drying system, achieving an

NPK ratio of 15-2-4 (nitrogen-phosphorus-potassium) with nutrient levels increased by over 25 times (P2Green Project, n.d.). The final production stage is granulation, where the dried and concentrated urine is formed into solid granulates, compatible with conventional farming equipment for practical agricultural application. Currently, granulation is performed by a German service provider, but S360 plans to invest in its own equipment for this step. The granulated urine-based fertiliser is then packaged and labelled at the production facility before distribution to customers.

Additionally, the production facility will undertake manufacturing and assembly of drying systems, based on their COTS approach.

Downstream

From S360's production facility, the fertiliser is distributed to customers, either directly to farmers or to hobby gardeners. In traditional linear value chains, the fertiliser would leave the value chain once received by farmers. However, in this model, the fertiliser is applied to farmland to fertilise barley production. Farmers then harvest the barley and ship it to the malting factory. Until now, S360 has managed malting, but in the future business model, farmers will ship the barley to the malting partner of GB. From here, the malted barley is utilised to brew low-environmental-footprint beer, thereby closing the loop from fork to farm.

In the future business model, the downstream activities related to the drying system will include sales and distribution activities. Collaborations with organisations like Norwegian, Cinderella, are relevant in this stage (elaborated under key partners).

Perspectives on key activities

Although farmers are not direct partners in the P2Green project, they are included in **Table 4** below to illustrate their role, as they already use the fertiliser through their existing collaboration with GB. Additionally, TD has established partnerships with local events and cities, which enhance urine collection logistics. These pre-existing partnerships create two already functional, but independent chains, with S360 now bridging the previously independent chains of urine collection and barley production for brewing.

Collaboration with various actors involved in urine collection is essential to ensure a consistent supply of inputs. Throughout the key activities, marketing, communication and sales are key activities carried out by all value chain partners. Each of the partners target different customers and benefits from sharing the product journey and the narrative of the closed loop value chain.

Table 4: Key activities, Gotland pilot region

Key activities	Description of key activities
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Key upstream activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Research and development of chemical stabilisation compound, drying system, and urinal retrofits (S360 and SLU)2. Import chemical input material, binding materials, and packaging materials (S360)3. Produce chemical stabiliser (S360)4. Coordinate collection and stabiliser exchange (TD and S360)5. Provide tanks for urine storage containing stabiliser (S360)6. Collect urine at festivals and events in urinals and UDTs (TD)7. Collect and transport urine from the point of collection to the production facility (S360)8. Store urine in airtight one cubic meter tanks (S360)9. Procure COTS-equipment for drying system (S360)
Key production activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none">10. Dry stabilised urine (S360)11. Mix concentrated urine with binding material (S360)12. Keep technology maintained (S360)13. Granulate dried urine (currently a German partner, future S360)14. Package and label fertiliser in bags (S360).15. Manufacture and assemble drying system (S360)
Key downstream activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none">16. Distribute fertiliser to customers (not identified)17. Apply fertiliser to fields (farmers)18. Harvest barley (farmers)19. Distribute barley from farmers to malting factory (not identified)20. Produce barley malt (malting factory)21. Distribute barley from malting factory to GB (not identified)22. Brew beer (GB)

	23. Market and distribute beer (GB).
	24. Distribute drying system (S360 and partner)

5.5.2 Key resources

The key resources are listed in **Table 5** and elaborated below.

Table 5: Key resources, Gotland pilot region

Key resources	Description of resources	Status
Physical resources	Urinals and toilets for urine-diverting retrofits	Available through TD
	Urine storage tanks	Available through TD
	Urine drying system	Available through S360
	Production facility for technology and treatment	Available through local cement factory
Human resources	Scientific workers	Available through SLU
	Operating personnel	Available through TD and S360
	Sales force	Missing by S360
	Brewers	Available through GB
Intellectual resources	Knowledge of:	
	• R&D of the drying system	Available through SLU & S360
	• Confidential process for the chemical stabilisation compound	Available through SLU & S360
	• Best granulation practices	Available through external German partner and S360.
	• Well-reputed brand	Available through GB
Financial resources	Soft funding	
	• Research foundations (EU projects, Swedish	Available through S360 but with a time limit

	<p>Research Council for Sustainable Development, Vinnova (Swedens innovation agency)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Start- up grants (SLU-Holding)	<p>Available through SLU but with a time limit</p>
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Physical resources

To be able to source the urine several key physical resources are needed. TD provides the fleet of urinals and portable toilets that enable on-site collection, along with intermediate bulk containers for storage containing chemical stabiliser provided by S360 for stabilisation.

Another key resource is the technology and production facilities used to transform urine into fertiliser. This includes the urine-drying system, which concentrates urine into a solid form. However, the production facility is currently under development. Initially, the stabilised urine was processed using wind and solar power, but this limited the potential for scaling operations due to restricted energy availability (Beneker et al., 2023). To address this, the production facility operated by S360 started exploring alternative energy solutions. One proposed solution would utilise waste heat from a nearby cement factory, while another would recover heat from exhaust gases. As such, although the technology is developed, the pilot region is still missing the production facility that enables the circular solution.

GB possesses key physical resources through their beer brewing facilities, as well as their on-site store at the brewery. These resources are essential for transforming the agricultural output into a consumable product that reaches end consumers.

Human resources

Knowledge-intensive human resources are essential for the technologies and processes of the business model. There are currently three full time employees at S360, with connections to SLU. SLU represents the core of the R&D activities performed in close collaboration with S360. As a university spin-off, the combined knowledge of S360's specialised employees in combination with the expertise of SLU students and personnel covers different aspects of the production process, drying system technology and the composition of the chemical stabilising compound. The human resources of S360 further provide experience on best practices related to granulation of fertiliser, e.g., which equipment to use and how to form the granulates. The process of granulation is further dependent on the expertise of S360's German granulation partner.

Additionally, the many years of experience of TD personnel and GB's brewers help optimise and refine both urine collection and beer production, contributing to efficient upstream and downstream processes.

Intellectual resources

The intellectual resources are the foundation of the business model, especially the specialised expertise of the teams at S360 and SLU. Their ongoing research, development, and deep knowledge of the performance of the drying technology, and agricultural application represent a key resource for both the current operations and the future evolution of the business model.

TD also possess crucial intellectual resources for the business model through their customer databases. Being the only portable sanitation provider in Gotland, their years of presence at the local 'Medieval Time week' and music festivals mean that they possess already established relationships with clients which are important for sourcing of urine. Furthermore, GB owns a well-reputed brand that bring legitimacy, and associations of quality to the business model. Being a daughter company of the Swedish brewery of Spendrups, similarly contributes with recognisability and positive associations related to environmental efforts.

Financial resources

The financial resources supporting the start-up phase have primarily come from soft funding aimed at implementing the urine-based fertiliser technology. So far, this has included a combination of research and innovation funding as well as start-up grants. The research and innovation funding has primarily focused on the implementation of the technology and product development, ensuring the feasibility and effectiveness of the fertiliser production process. The start-up grants have been used to cover key business development costs, including intellectual property (IP) searches, legal fees, and support for business model development in general. The soft funding is crucial for building the market especially since the market demands a large scale of operations before revenue can be achieved.

5.5.3 Key partners

The key partners in the Swedish pilot region are:

Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU) is a Swedish agricultural university providing knowledge and research to the business model. The university initiated the development of the technology that turns urine into fertiliser several years ago. Thus, SLU holds key competencies for research and development and are heavily involved in the further development of the technology to support the business of S360.

Sanitation360 (S360) is a Swedish university spin-off company originating from SLU. S360 acts as the pilot coordinator and technology provider for urine reclamation. S360's

mission is to turn scientific innovation into practical, commercial products that make sanitation more sustainable and environmentally friendly. S360 provides knowledge of the chemical compound used to stabilise and are active in both the upstream and production stages. In collaboration, S360 and SLU provide the technology for urine dehydration and S360 further produces the dried urine granulates, which are delivered to local farmers for barley production.

Touch Down Gotland (TD) is a Swedish company that provides sanitation services such as portable toilet and urinal rentals. Through TD's services, existing network and maintenance contracts, urine is collected and stored with S360's chemical compound to begin the stabilisation process of the circular nutrient value chain. TD operates at various locations across Gotland, including public toilets in Visby, in nearby military facilities, festivals and other events.

Gotland Bryggeri (GB) is a local brewery and daughter-company of Swedish, Spendrups Bryggeri AB. GB provide brewery facilities and capabilities for beer production using barley grown with bio-based fertilisers from S360. Throughout P2Green, the barley will be assessed for its comparability to conventionally grown barley for beer brewing. By validating the suitability of barley grown with urine-based fertilisers for commercial beer brewing, GB will close the value chain by delivering final products to consumers.

Table 6 provides a list of key suppliers, distributors, and other key stakeholders for the Swedish pilot:

Table 6: Key Partners - Gotland pilot region

Resources provided or activity performed	
Key suppliers	Supplier of chemical material <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Input material for chemical stabiliser production.
	Supplier of packaging material <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Packaging materials including S360-branded bags, labels, etc. for granulised fertilisers.
	Local cement factory <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Provider of waste heat and area for production facility
	Granulation provider (currently a German partner) <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Granulates the dried urine into fertiliser (In the future, S360 intends to manage this process in-house)• Advise on granulation practices, equipment etc.
	Malting company (currently a German partner, soon GB partner company)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malting capabilities <p>Local festivals or events</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitators of urine collection, and platforms for communication. <p>Toilet manufacturers (currently missing)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production of urinal retrofits for portable toilets using S360s design.
<p>Key distributors</p>	<p>Distributor of urine</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transportation from urine collection to production of fertiliser will be performed by third-party transportation provider, or S360 <p>Distributor of fertiliser to customers (currently missing)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distributors will provide distribution and marketing of the fertiliser to customers e.g., relevant farming associations <p>Distributor of barley/malted barley to GB (currently missing)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distributors will provide transportation between farmers, the malting factory, and GB. <p>Distributor of drying systems (currently missing)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distributors will undertake marketing practices related to drying systems. • To be able to scale urine recycling for household level systems or distribute larger scale systems for companies like TD, it will be necessary to engage a partner willing to distribute the drying systems. • Organisations like Norwegian Cinderella, with years of experience with incineration toilets in the Scandinavian market, are obvious candidates for distributing household level systems. Their main job will be to undertake activities related to sales and distribution of household level systems, and larger scale systems for sanitation providers like TD.
<p>Other key partners</p>	<p>Local farmers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While local farmers will pose as customers when the business model is operating, they are currently intaking the role as subcontracted partner that provide valuable agricultural hectares for field trials (Beneker et al., 2023) <p>Hushållningssällskapet</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As an independent agricultural advisor, Hushållningssällskapet conducts barley field trials on Gotland using dry urine fertiliser. The trial evaluates four treatments: urine pellets, commercial

fertiliser, unconcentrated liquid urine, and a control with no fertiliser (Beneker et al., 2023). Thus, they are crucial to provide future testing and validation with farmers.

Gotland Municipality (relationship established with TD, but not S360)

- Agreements on urine treatment and legal interpretations.

Municipalities in other Swedish regions (relationships initiated)

- Municipalities, e.g., Malmö, Stockholm, and Uppsala, will provide political decision-making power to support adoption of S360 practices.

5.5.4 Channels

The Swedish pilot region partners employ multiple channels that act to communicate with customers and deliver the different value propositions. These channels are either owned or will potentially be owned by the pilot region partners, while other channels key to the business model might be owned by external partners outside the pilot region.

The key channels of the Swedish pilot are divided into the following channel categories:

- Channels that are vital to raise awareness about the nutrient recycling solution, the bio-based fertiliser, and the white label beer.
- Channels that are vital to enable customers of the bio-based fertiliser to evaluate its functionality.
- Channels that are vital to allow customers to purchase and distribute both the sanitation services, bio-based fertiliser and beer.

Raising awareness

The purpose of the key channels is to communicate and raise awareness of the nutrient recycling solution where urine is collected from festivals to produce bio-based fertiliser. These channels are essential to gain support from both public actors and the citizens in general.

Local festivals and events provide essential external high-traffic platforms to inform visitors about the reuse of their urine. Similarly, TD owns a key awareness channel by being present at venues with many visitors throughout an event. This poses an opportunity to establish awareness campaigns directly at the urine collection points. The units provided by TD can be used for posters and other branding material to raise awareness and create interest around the problems being addressed in the project.

Public awareness campaigns should educate people on the environmental impact of conventional wastewater treatment. Many citizens are unaware of the phosphorus and nitrogen released into the sea due to current sanitation systems. The widespread “flush

and forget” mindset leads users to overlook the fact that conventional chemical toilets contribute to resource waste and environmental harm. Additionally, the misconception that wastewater treatment plants remove all pollutants before discharge needs to be addressed. Changing these perceptions is key to increasing public willingness to contribute urine for nutrient recycling, ultimately boosting the volume of nutrients reclaimed.

Another effective communication channel is owned by GB, who can market and promote low environmental impact beer through their well-reputed brand in their own- and partner shops. This approach connects end-consumers to the circular value chain by linking an established and respected beer brand to the nutrient recycling process. Showcasing a tangible product strengthens the storytelling impact and enhances consumer engagement.

P2Green and collaborations with other EU projects serve as additional platforms for raising awareness and building capacity among municipalities, farmers, the public, and other key stakeholders in the Swedish pilot region (Beneker et al., 2023)

Enabling evaluation

Different channels are key to enable the different customer segments to evaluate the value proposition of the Swedish business model, thereby providing validation and practical support for potential customers.

Specifically related to the value proposition of the urine-based fertiliser, the innovative nature and early maturity, means that SLU owns a vital channel to help evaluate the functionality of this fertiliser given its role in investigating and publishing results on e.g., the protein values of the barley (Beneker et al., 2023). This helps potential farming customers to evaluate the performance of the fertiliser.

Additionally, the external advising partner Hushållningssällskapet also owns a key channel to communicate about the functionality and efficiency of the urine-based fertiliser. Hushållningssällskapet represents a third-party organisation that conducts independent field trials with existing farming equipment. Thus, their results related to the use of urine-based fertiliser enables farmers, and hobby gardeners, to evaluate its benefits and negatives and build trust around the value proposition.

Another key channel for the evaluation of both the urine-based fertiliser value proposition, and the sustainable beer value proposition is a suitable certification scheme on safety. While Swedish farmers are currently allowed to use urine-based fertilisers, certifications showing that the fertiliser is ‘safe to use’ is required by GB to be able to show their stakeholders and end-consumers that their beer is safe to consume. Thus, such a certification scheme will allow both farmers and the end-users to evaluate the safety of using and consuming urine-based products. However, identifying suitable certification schemes is currently being investigated.

Purchase and distribution channels

Different purchase and distribution channels are key to allow customers to purchase the products and services and deliver the value propositions offered in the Swedish business model. These channels ensure availability and facilitate transactions with customers that purchase sanitation services, urine-based fertiliser and beer.

Allowing customers to purchase urine treatment services relies on a direct purchase and distribution channel owned by Sanitation 360. In Gotland, TD purchases the services directly from Sanitation 360 who deliver the needed stabiliser and provide the collection of urine. Outside the pilot region, Sanitation 360 has been contacted by events inquiring about urine collection, thereby showcasing the potential of this direct purchase and distribution channel outside the pilot region. However, due to limitations in capacities, Sanitation 360 is currently not able to fulfil such demands.

For the urine-based fertiliser Sanitation 360 owns an important direct sales channel to allow local farmers to purchase the fertiliser. Interactions with local farmers have shown positive indications that they are willing to purchase the fertiliser directly from S360, and since the volumes of urine are still relatively low there are currently limited risks that the market will be saturated with the supply from Sanitation 360. However, given the assumption that the volumes of urine will increase in the future, it has been assessed critical to engage and partner with relevant farming associations to expand the purchase and distribution channels toward more interested farmers. Engaging in networks of farmer agents already trusted by farmers, and imposing them to trial the fertiliser will potentially help them understand about its usage and safety, and poses as an opportunity to yield stronger sales results (Coates et al. 2020)

Hobby gardeners represent another customer segment of the urine-based fertiliser. To allow this segment to purchase the product, different strategies can be applied. One obvious purchase and distribution channel will be owned by external garden boutiques, centres or even suitable supermarkets directly in contact with the target segment.

The last key purchase and distribution channels is related to the beer produced from barley grown with urine-based fertiliser. These channels are owned or facilitated by GB, Spendrup Brewery and Systembolaget. In Gotland, beer-consumers can purchase beer directly at the location of GB, while the beer is also sold and distributed through the sales channels of Spendrups Brewery, the mother company of GB. Additionally, much of the beverages produced by Spendrups, and thereby also GB, is sold through Systembolaget, a Swedish monopoly retail chain who sells beverages to a wide variety of beer consumers.

5.5.5 Organisational value creation flows

Collaboration

Collaboration is the overarching key organisational value that is determining for the success of the circular solution. However, collaboration also requires an extra effort from the partners to be able to succeed with the circular solution. Collaboration is operationalised through the following value creation flows among the partners:

Synergy effects

The partners encompass the ability to provide diverse competencies, knowledge and know-how of a particular part of the value chain. Besides specific knowledge, the partners also provide physical resources that enhance their market offerings and are an integral part of their own business model. S360 bridges the partners and in order to succeed with the circular solution, these different partners, representing unique competencies, knowledge and networks from different parts of the value chain together create synergies that enables the circular solution, while benefiting all partners. For instance, TD, which already collects urine and faeces as part of its traditional business model, contributes to the circular value chain by supplying urine to S360 instead of sending it to WWTP. TD's established infrastructure, expertise and know-how of how to operate sanitation services, and its established customer base enhance overall efficiency of the circular value chain. Similarly, SLU benefits from applying its research in a real-world setting, bridging the gap between academic study and practical application. SLU's competencies, laboratory facilities, and fundraising expertise add significant value. GB also contributes with knowledge of how to brew beer, an existing customer base and how to market beer through its strong local brand, which supports the pilot's goals and promotes the circular system. While using urine-based fertiliser in beer production can enhance GB's environmental image, it also carries the risk of uncertain social acceptance.

Gatekeeping

Gatekeepers provide valuable access to resources, information, and opportunities. Both TD and GB act as intermediaries by leveraging their established networks of suppliers and customers. This facilitates a steady flow of resources to S360, supported by existing contracts with festivals and events that ensure a supply of urine and enable beer production. In addition, GB's strong connections with farmers in Gotland may help to scale the solution effectively. Moreover, the involvement of a university as a public institution further strengthens collaboration by increasing local authorities' interest and willingness to participate. This connection is vital, especially in areas where municipalities face restrictions when working with private companies.

Willingness to engage

Although TD and GB already operate business models that are not dependent on S360, S360 is dependent on the partnership with these organisations due to the established businesses and networks they possess. If a partner is not willing to engage into the circular partnership S360 will not succeed because there will be a missing link in the

value chain. As such, willingness to engage with each other is a key organisational value that must be present among the partners to succeed with the circular solution.

5.6 Value capture

5.6.1 Revenue streams

The circular business model seeks to capture value through different revenue streams ranging from sanitation services, sales of urine-drying systems, bio-based fertiliser, and premium beer sales. However, the business model faces hurdles in achieving financial sustainability and scaling up due to high costs, misconceptions about pricing, and regulatory challenges. For instance, urine is subject to legislation that determines its classification, which is relevant for the potential transactions between TD and S360. If classified as a by-product under the Waste Framework Directive, Directive (EC) 2008/98, this imposes restrictions on the ability to have monetary transactions related to the transfer of urine from TD to S360. These influences how a potential revenue stream between TD and S360 can unfold. The structure of the revenue streams indicates areas with possibilities for short term revenue which can help finance areas with long term profit potential.

Overall, the partners in the pilot region facilitate different revenue streams based on their existing core competencies belonging to a particular market. However, as opposed to a traditional linear business model, the revenue streams must work in conjunction to make the circular system profitable for all partners, with specific attention to S360 as the technology provider, rather than benefiting only one actor of the value chain. There will be a particular focus on revenue streams which have been emphasised by the partners as critical or necessary to make the circular business model successful.

The following revenue streams have been identified by the partners:

Table 7: Revenue streams, Gotland pilot region

Revenue stream	Description
Sanitation service at a premium e.g., pollutant avoidance fee (Festivals to TD)	A critical value capturing mechanism is to enforce premium payments on the sanitation services offered to event-organisers. The argument supporting additional fees to be imposed for the services of TD is related to the strengthened sustainable image that the event-organisers benefit from, due to TDs involvement in a circular nutrient value chain. Certification schemes for festivals such as “Greener festival certification ² ” are crucial drivers to provide incentives for the festivals to be willing pay a premium fee for the use of low impact sanitation services.

² <https://www.agreenerfuture.com/greener-festival-certification>

	<p>S360 are currently discussing environmental certification of events with different organisers. This is crucial when exploring the possibility of introducing extra charges for sanitation services as a viable revenue stream. With support from the LCAs conducted in the project, these charges could represent ‘pollutant avoidance fees’, where users pay for the extra costs related to recycling of urine rather than traditional disposal.</p> <p>The extra fee that the festivals might pay for the sanitation service provided by TD, could ideally be redirected to S360, who is responsible for collection of urine (see next revenue stream). Alternatively, this fee could be shared collaboratively between the two partners.</p>
Urine treatment service payments (TD or municipality to S360)	<p>Another critical revenue stream is designed to capture value from S360’s urine treatment services and is closely related to the extra charges for sustainable sanitation services. As mentioned in the introduction to this section, current legislation entails that urine is classified as a by-product meaning that S360 cannot generate a transaction based on the urine itself. However, they are allowed to generate revenue from the collection service, provision of stabilisers, transportation, and the similar services they provide.</p> <p>In the current setup of Gotland, TD does not incur any increased costs when participating in the circular value chain, which provides an argument that one way to finance such payments could be to transfer the pollutant avoidance fees received from festivals, onto S360 to compensate them for their efforts. However, in the event that TD invests in a new vacuum pump to divert the urine, parts of the pollutant avoidance fee could be retained to compensate their increased costs of operation.</p> <p>TD, as a paying customer of urine treatment services, could ideally be substituted by the municipality. The value of S360s offering lies in avoided pollution, where the WWTPs receive the main benefits since they avoid processing of urine, and subsequent discharge of nutrients to the ecosystem. While these are arguments supporting public authorities as paying customers of the services, the specific arrangements of such a value capturing mechanism are not in place. Governmental subsidies are further elaborated under revenue stream 6.</p>
Sales or rentals of drying systems	<p>Sales or rentals of the drying system technology represents another critical revenue stream to ensure profits from S360’s</p>

(Sanitation service providers or building owners to S360)	<p>operations. The value capturing mechanism can be structured in two ways: S360 could rely on transactional sales meaning that customers gain full ownership of the technology. An estimated price of €500 per unit is expected to constitute a transactional revenue stream for small-scale systems, while installation of large-scale systems will be offered at €10,000.</p> <p>Alternatively, S360 establishes leasing arrangements, where customers are allowed to use the drying system for a fixed period in return for a pre-determined fee. The latter option will ensure that S360 generates recurring revenue to secure a continuous cashflow, while organising the offering with Product-as-a-Service characteristics means that customers avoid having to pay upfront CAPEX, which poses a potentially high barrier for adoption (Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, 2019).</p> <p>Positive feedback from potential customers outside the Swedish market indicates interest in the market for the offering.</p>
Low-price fertiliser sales (Conventional farmers to S360)	<p>A critical revenue stream is related to the transactional sales of urine-based fertiliser for conventional farmers. This customer segment is positive towards bio-based fertilisers, however they are price sensitive due to their focus on crop yields, and demand large volumes of fertilisers. Thus, the fertiliser pellets customised for use in an agricultural setting must be sold at competitive prices per tonne.</p> <p>Recent trends within the fertiliser markets, are the emergence of carbon- and fossil free fertilisers, often marketed at premiums compared to conventional mineral fertilisers. Thus, with support from the LCAs, a future potential is to impose higher prices and target more environmentally conscious farmers who are willing to pay premiums to lower their environmental impacts.</p> <p>It is therefore validated that the farmers are willing to use the product, however, S360 is currently not able to meet the demand of the farmers.</p>
Premium fertiliser sales (Hobby gardeners to S360)	<p>Due to the limited profit potential, and difficulties in meeting farmer volume demands, premium fertiliser sales for hobby gardeners are introduced to capture value from the recovered nutrients of urine. The fertiliser will be marketed to hobby gardeners, a customer segment being less price sensitive than the conventional farmers. Hobby gardeners</p>

	<p>often pay for fertilisers per kg, which creates an opportunity to charge premium prices.</p> <p>While Swedish gardeners are familiar with urine as a fertiliser, it is not yet validated that hobby gardeners are willing to pay premium price for the urine-based fertiliser.</p> <p>However, it must be noted that sales for hobby gardeners is not the goal of S360's operations. Thus, hobby garden sales must be balanced with revenue from farmers to support the purpose of S360. Instead of being the main source of income, it represents an additional and needed revenue stream to generate positive margins from S360's fertiliser production.</p>
<p>Government subsidies (Government to S360 / farmers)</p>	<p>Government subsidies recognising avoided pollution, reduced nitrogen removal costs, lower N₂O emissions from wastewater treatment, and incentives for farmers to use less CO₂-intensive fertilisers are assumed by S360 to be critical for the success of the business model. However, subsidies are not yet in place and require validation and support from municipalities or WWTPs. A prerequisite when establishing these subsidies will be to calculate the costs per litre of treating urine, which is currently investigated by S360. Early estimates show that the value of avoided pollution of wastewater is expected to amount to €100 per m³ from an estimated processed volume of 500m³</p> <p>Estimates from S360 suggest that farmers typically pay around €2 per kilogram of nitrogen as fertiliser, whereas removing the same amount from wastewater can cost approximately €10. This stark contrast underscores the inefficiency of traditional nutrient management systems, and that potential savings are often not fully recognised within municipal budgets due to their integrated structure.</p> <p>A key challenge is determining who should bear the cost of S360's activities. According to the pilot they provide benefits to society and government bodies by:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Preventing nutrient pollution and associated environmental costs.2. Reducing nitrogen removal costs in WWTP by decentralising urine treatment.3. Lowering N₂O emissions from wastewater treatment.4. Reducing the CO₂ footprint of farmers by offering a less carbon-intensive fertiliser.

5. Reducing operational costs of the WWTP related to urine treatment
6. Potentially eliminates the need for large capital investments in the construction of new treatment plants.

For some of these revenue streams to be viable, S360 would need to enter WWTPs' area of operations. This would require agreements where WWTPs formally recognise S360 as an alternative urine treatment solution. Different revenue streams from government subsidies may be envisioned.

Subsidisation of Bio-based fertiliser

Governments might subsidise bio-based fertilisers, e.g., through price subsidisation in the same way that mineral fertilisers are often supported (Otoo et al. 2018). While this area requires further investigation, it will improve the competitiveness against conventional options.

Carbon and nitrogen credits

The reduction of carbon and nitrogen emissions obtained through the circular value chain opens an opportunity for credit solutions. Carbon credit claims supported e.g., by the World Bank have proven to be essential revenue streams in other nutrient recycling business models (Otoo et al. 2018).

S360's operations reduce N₂O emissions from WWTPs and nutrient pollution of waterways, which make nitrogen credits a potential revenue stream. These credits represent the environmental benefits of nitrogen reduction and should be financed by governments or municipalities. Thereby S360 will receive payments from the municipality or WWTP for the avoided costs of removing nitrogen in the wastewater treatment plants which would provide an important and reliable revenue stream.

Alongside nitrogen credits, CO₂ credits present another revenue opportunity. Urine dehydration reduces N₂O emissions from wastewater treatment, and the resulting fertiliser has a lower CO₂ footprint (pending LCA quantification due month 42 (D2.3)), supporting broader climate and environmental goals and could be implemented by governments or municipalities.

Additional revenue streams that could enhance the business model include:

Table 8: Additional revenue streams, Gotland pilot region

Additional revenue stream	Description
Disposal fees (TD to S360)	An additional revenue stream for S360 is closely associated with the second revenue stream described above, and stems from eliminating the fees that TD and other sanitation provider currently pays to the municipality of Gotland for urine disposal. In the new circular value chain, the original disposal of urine is eliminated, meaning that such a fee could be redirected as volume dependent payments towards S360. Pay-to-dispose fees pose as an additional, but not crucial revenue stream due to the current fees ranging from only 2,000 to 4,000 SEK (approx. 175 to 350 EUR) for emptying an 8,000-litre tank.
Stabiliser sales (sanitation service providers or events to S360)	Apart from the payments linked to the urine treatment services, where stabilisers are included in the offering, there is an opportunity to sell the mere stabiliser for interested customers. Sales of urine stabiliser is expected to be offered at €1 per pouch with the potential to be paid on a monthly basis as a subscription fee.
Premium beer sales (beer consumers to GB)	<p>To capture value from the beer production using sustainable barley and creating a specialised beer experience, premium beer-payments can be introduced. Such payments entail that consumers will bear some of the costs related to nutrient recycling, but for these payments to benefit S360 the premium price must be transferred to farmers and subsequently S360, for instance through higher prices paid by GB for the barley.</p> <p>A method to overcome a price transmission, is to rely on a white-label solution. In this scenario, GB produces the beer, while S360 market it under their own brand. This would be a means for S360 to generate a direct cash flow that will support the scaling of the technology, and directly enjoy the margins related to the premium price.</p>

5.6.2 Financial value creation flows

This section examines the financial value flows within the system. It is important to note that one key stakeholder, farmers, is not currently represented as a partner in the Swedish pilot region. As a result, the financial flows to and from this stakeholder have not been assessed. In this circular business model, all partners depend on the

successful commercialisation of the fertiliser to generate revenue and create financial value between each other, forming a mutually beneficial cycle.

All partners currently operate their own independent business models without relying on S360. However, S360 depends on these partners to create financial value, which it achieves by facilitating financial value flows between the collaborating partners. By aligning incentives and distributing value across stakeholders, the system enables cost avoidance and revenue generation while promoting sustainable practices.

Below are suggestions of how to create internal financial value creation flows between the partners in pilot.

Operationalising financial value creation flows between partners

From S360 to TD: Avoided costs

Currently, the sanitation service provider, TD, receives payments from cities and festivals for delivering sanitation services and may be able to charge a premium for these services, particularly at festivals, where the added environmental benefits could justify a "pollution avoidance fee." This fee could be redirected to S360 directly from the festivals. TD must also pay disposal fees to the Region of Gotland when handling urine collected at festivals. By delivering the urine to S360, TD can avoid the need for public disposal of urine, thereby eliminating these fees and improving its financial efficiency and redistributing the avoided costs to S360.

GB to S360: Revenue from white label beer

In a white label model, GB produces the beer, while S360 markets it under their own brand. Thereby GB enables S360 to market a beer product, cultivated with the bio-based fertiliser. This arrangement enables S360 to generate direct cash flow, supporting technology scaling and allowing them to capture the premium price margins.

GB to S360: Sales of beer at a premium

When GB markets the beer, consumers indirectly contribute to covering nutrient recycling costs. For S360 to benefit, it is essential that the premium price is effectively transmitted through the value chain.

5.6.3 Cost structure

The cost structure of the Swedish pilot region is divided into capital expenditures (CAPEX) and operating expenses (OPEX). Having a value-driven business model that focus on environmental value creation by reducing the negative effects of nutrients discharged into the waters of Gotland, entails that the actors across the pilot region incur other expenses which are not present in traditional fertiliser value chains. One of the main challenges of the system is that each stage of the value chain is currently too small in scale to ensure profitable operation of the business model. Therefore, S360 is active in coordinating all stages of the business model from urine collection to the food

production, to make sure that the system works efficiently and as a method to maintain steady cashflows. Currently, S360 is in a situation where growth in size is needed both to co-fund future projects, but also to get products onto the market. The cost structure for the start-up phase of the business model is showcased in this section, while the specific financing structures for both the start-up phase and scale-up phase scenarios are estimated in the section related to the financing structure. The cost structure of CAPEX and OPEX is illustrated in the **Table 9** below:

Table 9: Cost structure of CAPEX and OPEX, Gotland pilot region.

CAPEX / OPEX	Estimated amount (EUR)	Percentage of total expenditures (%)
Total CAPEX	650.000	81%
Total OPEX (yearly)	150.000	19%

The different cost items that constitute both CAPEX and OPEX are elaborated in the following **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden..** Due to confidentiality, the specific cost elements are not elaborated in monetary amounts.

Table 10: Cost items for CAPEX and OPEX, Gotland pilot region

Cost category	Key items
Capital expenditures (CAPEX)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start-up costs Machinery (truck, reactor, etc.) Urinals, toilets Retrofitting of toilets Other investments 100.000
Operating expenditures - Fixed (1 year)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rental costs of production space Human resource requirements Maintenance costs Electricity consumption reactor
Operating expenditures – Variable (1 year)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Urine management (direct labour and transportation of urine)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Storage of fresh urine (assuming storage of 200 L/0,2 m3 urine per day)• Direct labour reactor• Electricity consumption reactor• Chemical stabiliser (assuming yearly production of 2,000 kg. of dried urine)• Granulation provider service costs (assuming 50 m3 (2025-goal) fresh urine collected)
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The CAPEX of S360 are essential physical key resources that support urine collection and production of fertiliser. For the first year of the business model, the costs are significantly impacted by the purchasing of an additional truck to increase the volumes of urine collected. Together with the costs related to develop the reactor, CAPEX accounts for a significant amount of costs.

The main OPEX of S360, are fixed due to the human resources needed to operate the production facility, along with depreciation costs of the reactor. However, variable costs also account for a significant amount of OPEX with the main activities driving these expenditures being urine management costs (direct labour and transportation), chemical stabilisers used as input material, and costs of operating the reactor. The divisions between fixed and variable costs are illustrated in the following tables on a yearly basis:

Along with the variable OPEX stated above, S360 also incur costs related to the binding material, storage of dried urine, packaging supplies, although not significant relative to the other costs.

While these activities and physical resources contribute to creating superior value, the increased expenses in these areas put high demands on the Swedish pilot region's ability to capture this value efficiently through its revenue streams.

For the business model there is a potential to improve the economies of scale when S360 is able to source enough urine to operate the reactor at its capacity of 200 litres of fresh urine per day. Having a value-driven focus does not entail that the organisations should not focus on optimising its costs, meaning that future scaling of urine-collection practices creates opportunities to reduce costs of the final fertilising products to increase competitiveness and profitability of the business model.

5.6.4 Financing

To identify suitable financing sources and the corresponding financing partners, it is essential to develop an overview of the necessary inherent investment needs, i.e. funding requirements of the Swedish pilot region.

Following the circular business model for the Swedish pilot region, the focus thereby is also on S360 regarding financing, as this company is the main provider of the circular solution – the bio-based fertiliser. S360 is the connection between the partners (TD & GB) which are already established in their respective markets and already operate profitable business models.

Funding requirements

In this chapter we provide an overview of the funding requirements of the key partners involved in the Swedish Pilot Region.

Generally, implementing a circular urine reclamation model requires financial investment in the stages presented in **Table 11** below.

Table 11: Funding requirements in the stages of the CBM, Gotland pilot region

Stage	
Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Development and deployment of urine-stabilising toilets• Collection and storage facilities• Urine drying systems
Operational costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Maintenance costs• Logistics and transportation of stabilised urine and fertiliser pellets
Research and development (R&D)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Optimisation of stabilisation, drying, and blending processes
Awareness and capacity building	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Engaging municipalities, farmers, and end-consumers in the adoption of the biofertiliser model
Market development	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ensuring the acceptance and competitiveness of urine-derived fertilisers among farmers and breweries vs. existing mineral fertilisers

Funding requirements will change and evolve throughout the different stages of the circular business model. A key challenge in financing circular businesses is aligning

funding instruments with these different stages of development. For example, grants and venture capital are well-suited for proof-of-concept and early commercialisation stages, where risk is high, and revenue generation is uncertain. In contrast, debt financing, such as concessional loans and green bonds, becomes more viable at the scaling phase when revenue streams are more predictable, and investors seek lower-risk opportunities. Grants and venture capital are often necessary at the proof-of-concept stage, while concessional loans, guarantees, and green bonds become relevant as the business scales.

The following **Table 12** provides an overview of the identified funding requirements for each of the three development stages of the business model as well as the range of suitable funding options available at these different stages.

Table 12: Funding requirements, Gotland pilot region

Stages of development			
Stage	Proof of concept & design development	Testing & pilot implementation	Scaling & optimisation
Corresponding TRL	1-4	5-7	8-9
Stage objective	Validate the core idea or product.	Bring the product to market and start generating revenue.	Expand market presence, revenue, and operations.
Investment in:	R&D, Start-up costs, feasibility studies, market research, concept validation, basic prototyping, lab testing	Product development, pilot infrastructure, customer validation, logistics, regulatory approvals	Full-scale infrastructure, marketing, logistics, regulatory compliance, and scaling operations
Estimated funds required	€ 20,000 - € 200,000	€200,000 - € 800,000	€800,000 - €5,000,000
Types of funding	Public & Private Grants, Angel Investors, Venture Capital	Grants, Equity, Crowdfunding, subordinated loans	Equity and debt financing, Blended-finance

Requirements of financing partners	Strong founding Team, Large (growing) Market, Differentiated Product/Technology	Proven Revenue Model, Clear path and timeline to profitability	Stable, profitable business with recurring Cash-flows
Position of key technology/ partner at start of P2Green		S360 (urine-drying technology)	
<u>Target</u> position of key technology/ partner			S360 (urine-drying technology)

The identified key partners of the circular business model are (i) S360, (ii) TD and (iii) GB. According to their specific role in the circular business model, each partner will be required to invest and bear operational costs which results in individual funding requirements. The main investment needs are centred around the necessary technology, which is the production of the bio-based fertiliser by S360.

S360

As the technology provider, S360 requires funding for infrastructure & equipment, i.e. purchase and installation of urine-separating toilets and urinals, collection tanks and storage systems, and transport vehicles for urine logistics (*this might shift towards TD*). Investments are also required for the processing facilities, which include construction or upgrading of facilities to stabilise and process urine into dry fertiliser pellets as well as investment in dehydration, chemical stabilisation, and pathogen removal technology. Additionally, R&D and regulatory compliance which means research on nutrient preservation and optimal processing techniques as well as certification and compliance with Swedish and EU agricultural regulations for fertiliser production. Finally, operating expenses such as staffing for collection, transport, and processing operations as well as maintenance of collection and treatment infrastructure also need to be considered.

TD

TD handles urine collection logistics and fertiliser distribution. Its funding needs include fleet & transport upgrades, i.e. acquisition and modification of specialised vehicles. The setup of storage & supply chain infrastructure which means handling facilities, logistics tracking systems and operating expenses like fuel, vehicle maintenance, and staffing.

GB

GB applies the bio-fertiliser in barley cultivation and produces sustainable beer. As GB is an established and profitable brewery, its funding needs regarding the circular business model are limited and include the purchase of subcontracts, materials and equipment.

5.6.5 Barriers to entry and key readiness factors

In general, the financing of circular business models presents unique challenges to investors (as described in Background – chapter 5.4). In order to access financing, each key partner of the Swedish Pilot will have to overcome specific barriers to entry and achieve certain key readiness factors.

Barriers to entry

These barriers especially arise from the interconnected roles of the key partners S360, TD and GB and the inherent challenges of scaling a circular economy solution for reclaiming urine to produce bio-fertiliser and brew beer on Gotland.

Regulatory and compliance barriers

- Urine classification as waste: In Sweden, urine is legally classified as waste, requiring complex permitting and compliance processes. This creates uncertainties, particularly for S360 as the primary processor and fertiliser producer.
- Food safety and certification: The Swedish pilot is currently investigating suitable certification schemes to showcase that the urine-based fertiliser is safe to use. This is particularly important for GB and its end-consumers. Absence of certification could hinder commercialisation.

Market readiness and acceptance

- Cultural taboos: The use of urine-derived fertiliser can trigger negative perceptions, potentially affecting the reputation of GB and marketability of the final product. Ensuring acceptance by consumers and farmers remains a significant challenge.
- Farmer hesitance: Farmers accustomed to mineral fertilisers may resist switching to an unconventional fertiliser derived from human excreta, particularly without clear cost benefits.

Financial and economic barriers

- Dependence on public funding: The business model relies on grants and subsidies to cover initial investments. Uncertainty about the continuation of such funding increases financial risks.

- Infrastructure and technology costs: Establishing urine collection, stabilisation, and processing systems require substantial capital investments, with no immediate guarantee of profitability.

Operational and logistical barriers

- Value chain complexity: Coordinating across diverse stakeholders — sanitation, agriculture, and brewing — can lead to inefficiencies. The model's reliance on partnerships means any disruption can impact the entire chain.
- Scalability limitations: Expanding beyond Gotland may face legal, logistical, and acceptance-related barriers, making replication of the model challenging.

Strategic and competitive barriers

- Reputation risk: For GB, associating its brand with urine-based products could be detrimental if public sentiment turns negative. Mitigating this requires careful communication strategies.
- Lack of established markets: The niche market for urine-based fertiliser lacks established distribution channels, adding to the challenge of commercialisation.

Key funding readiness factors

Securing funding for scaling and optimisation is essential for long-term success of the Swedish circular business model. This section identifies the key funding readiness factors for the involved partners.

Technical readiness and scalability

The urine stabilisation and drying system of S360 is at TRL 6, with efforts underway to increase scalability. To demonstrate funding readiness, partners should:

- Complete technological development to reach TRL 8–9.
- Provide evidence from field trials.
- Validate integration with conventional farming.

Market readiness and demand validation

Validating market demand is crucial. While initial collaborations are promising, scaling requires:

- Expanding partnerships with agricultural stakeholders.

- Conducting broader field trials and gathering customer feedback. Evidence of demand from farmers, breweries, municipalities, secured supply agreements or letters of intent from retailers.
- Identifying and completing suitable certification processes to enhance marketability.

Financial sustainability and revenue streams

A clear revenue model is vital. Key steps include:

- A transparent revenue structure demonstrating how each part of the value chain (sanitation services, biofertiliser sales, barley production, and beer sales) contribute to overall profitability.
- Exploring agreements with municipalities and wastewater treatment plants.

Regulatory compliance and risk management

Navigating regulations is critical due to the legal classification of urine. Partners need to:

- Engage policymakers for supportive regulations.
- Secure certifications for fertiliser commercialisation.
- Mitigate risks related to pharmaceutical residues.

Stakeholder engagement and social acceptance

Acceptance by stakeholders and the public is essential. Efforts should focus on:

- Community engagement and education, raising awareness about urine-derived products.
- Strengthening partnerships with municipalities and sanitation providers.
- Marketing products as eco-friendly and high-quality.

Once the Swedish Pilot has fulfilled some of these key readiness factors, a wider range of financing opportunities will become available.

5.6.6 Funding options and funding sources

Considering the funding requirements and stage of development of the key partners as described in the previous chapter, this chapter explores various funding sources and proposes potential financing partners for each key partner in the Swedish circular business model, as presented below.

Table 13: Funding options and funding sources, Gotland pilot region

Key partner	Funding type	Funding partner	Description / Access requirements
S360, TD	Grants	Vinnova (Sweden's Innovation Agency)	<p>Offers access to grants for innovation projects in circular economy, e.g. sustainable bio-based products.</p> <p>Applicants must be Swedish legal entities or organisations with a branch or place of business in Sweden.</p> <p>Companies should not be in financial difficulty.</p> <p>Specific eligibility criteria may vary depending on the call for proposals.</p> <p>Amount varies based on grant program.</p>
S360	Grants	Formas (Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development)	<p>Applicants must adhere to Formas' general terms and conditions. Projects should align with Formas' areas of responsibility, including environment, agricultural sciences, and spatial planning.</p> <p>Detailed eligibility criteria are specified in each call for proposals.</p> <p>Amount determined based on the specific call for proposals and project needs.</p> <p>Covers up to 100% of eligible costs for research organisations.</p> <p>For other entities, the funding rate depends on the nature of the project and the applicant's category.</p>
S360, TD, GB	Grants	Horizon Europe	<p>Is the EU's key funding programme for research and innovation. It tackles climate change, helps to achieve the</p>

			UN's Sustainable Development Goals and boosts the EU's competitiveness and growth.
S360	Grants	EU Innovation Fund	Projects focusing on innovative low-carbon technologies, energy-intensive industries, carbon capture and utilisation (CCU), carbon capture and storage (CCS), renewable energy generation, and energy storage. Amount varies based on project size; supports both large-scale and small-scale projects.
S360, (TD)	Grants	EU LIFE Programme	Focused on environmental protection, resource efficiency, climate change mitigation and adaptation, and the transition to a circular economy. Co-financing projects that align with its environmental and climate objectives. Amount typically, from €1m to €5m for projects with durations of 3 to 5 years. Co-financing rate of typically 60% but up to 75% possible.
S360, TD	Grants	Naturvårdsverket, <i>Klimatklivet</i> (Swedish Environmental Protection Agency)	Occasionally offers funding/grants for environmental innovation/research projects in different areas.
		Region Gotland (Local Public Funding)	Science Park Gotland: ongoing support for scaling and market development.
GB	Grants	Energimyndigheten (Swedish Energy Agency)	Supporting sustainable sanitation projects with funding for technology demonstration.

		EU Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD)	Funding to agri-food and forestry sectors, in particular rural areas. Also, part of EU CAP (common agricultural policy).
	Incentives	Jordbruksverket (Swedish Board of Agriculture)	Sustainable farming incentives
S360	Crowdfunding	FundedByMe	Crowdfunding platform based in Stockholm
S360, (TD)	Equity, Loans & Blended Finance	Nordic Environment Finance Corporation (NEFCO) (the Nordic Green Bank)	Supports the growth of Nordic SMEs whose solutions have a positive impact on the environment or climate. Potential loans, grants or co-funding for proven green solution/technology that is ready to be scaled up internationally. Amount max. €5m.
S360	Blended finance (Grants & Equity)	EIC Accelerator (European Innovation Council)	Open to startups and SMEs with high-impact innovations aiming to scale up and create or disrupt markets. Amount max. €2.5m in Grants; Equity investments from €0.5m to €10m.
TD	Loans and equity investments	European Investment Bank (EIB) – Circular Economy Financing Initiative	Projects must contribute to the circular economy and demonstrate economic viability. Applicants can be private or public entities within EU member states. A thorough due diligence process is conducted to assess project feasibility and impact. Amount varies depending on the project size and financing needs. Typically finances up to 50% of the project cost.

TD, S360, GB	Loans, Venture Capital, Grants	Almi Företagspartner	State owned company supporting Swedish SMEs undertaking green investments that align with the EU's environmental objectives. Amount not specified but also offers mini loans; tailored to the company's needs.
	Venture Capital	Industrifonden, Gullspang Invest	Investments in start-ups, innovation, and transformative projects

Other potential sources and financing partners to explore for grants or exchange of experience and learning:

- Swedish Investors for Sustainable Development (SISD) network members specialised in sustainable investments (part of the Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency – Sida)
- Swedish Agency for Economic and Regional Growth (Tillväxtverket) which offers knowledge, networks, and opportunities for investments
- Nordic Circular Hotspot network for a sustainable and circular economy in the Nordics

S360

S360 is the Pilot coordinator and technology provider for urine reclamation and fertiliser production. S360 is in the start-up phase and currently reliant on soft funding from EU Horizon programs, research foundations (EU, Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development, Vinnova), and startup grants from SLU-Holding and Science Park Gotland. As S360 moves toward commercialisation, securing additional funding for product development and scaling operations is essential.

While still in the second stage of development (Testing & Pilot implementation), S360 could continue relying on soft funding from EU Horizon programs, Vinnova, SLU and Gotland, combining with new funding from crowdfunding platforms, other research-driven grants from organisations such as Formas, or other local players such as NEFCO to fund technology development and early market entry.

Reaching the third stage of development (Scaling & Optimisation), S360 could consider the following funding: equity investment from EIC Accelerator, EIB's Circular Economy Financing Initiative, EU Life Programme (Circular economy and quality of life sub-programme), venture capital investments from e.g. Almi Företagspartner, or Industrifonden.

TD

TD operates a well-established and profitable business model centred around renting out toilets and urinals. In the pilot region, investments are primarily focused on acquiring and retrofitting toilets, installing collection units, and upgrading infrastructure. A financing need would only be required if TD were to integrate urine collection into its operations. However, due to EU waste regulations, urine collection is currently handled by S360.

As TD is already a well-established and profitable business, it currently has limited funding needs and could rather benefit from agreements with municipalities and festival organisers for sustainable sanitation solutions, corporate sponsorships (partnerships with event organisers promoting sustainable waste management solutions), as well as loans and leasing for equipment financing.

GB

GB is a well-established brewery utilising urine-based biofertiliser-grown barley for beer production. Since GB has been in operation long before joining the P2Green project, no significant capital expenditures were necessary. The costs associated with the project are rather low and cover subcontracts, materials, and equipment purchases.

Similarly to TD, as GB is already a well-established company, GB could benefit from marketing partnerships and branding sponsorships with sustainability-focused beverage brands and retailers, as well as more mature financing sources such as sustainability-linked loans.

Among the primary partners in the Swedish pilot, S360 is the principal entity requiring financial support, as it remains in the start-up phase. Initially, S360 could continue to rely on soft funding from EU and Swedish programs while exploring equity investments focused on the circular economy or venture capital after scaling up. In contrast, TD and GB, being well-established companies, could benefit from corporate partnerships, equipment leasing solutions, sustainability-linked loans. However, given that the circular business model is still in its early stages and a work in progress, all three partners must fulfil certain key readiness criteria to access broader funding opportunities.

5.7 Financing structure for the Swedish pilot

Based on the identified funding requirements and sources of financing, we created the following financing structure for the Swedish pilot region. The following Sources & Uses

Table 14 illustrates a feasible financing structure for the early testing and pilot phase of the pilot:

Table 14: Financing structure – testing & pilot phase, Gotland pilot region

Pilot Region: Sweden (Testing & Pilot Phase)						
Uses			Sources			
		in EUR	in %		in EUR	in %
S360	Start-up costs	100.000	13%	Vinnova	Local Grants	
	Machinery (truck, reactor, etc.)			SLU Holding		
TD	Urinals, Toilets			Formas		
All	Retrofitting			NEFCO		
	Other Investments			Local Grants (Sweden)	250.000	31%
	Total Capex	550.000	69%			
S360	Rent, personnel costs, maintenance			EU Innovation Fund	EU Grants	
	Storage, transportation, electricity			EU Horizon Program		
	Chemical stabilizer, granulation provider			EU Grants	500.000	63%
	Shipping & malting barley					
GB	Kegs & keg cleaner				Alternative financing	
	Packaging (bottles, caps)					
	Hop & other ingredients					
All	Other Working Capital			Fundedbyme		
	Total Opex	150.000	19%	Crowdfunding	50.000	6%
Total		800.000	100%	Total	800.000	100%

The total funding requirement at this stage was estimated to come to €800k. This estimation is based on (i) the provided data we received from the key partners via the questionnaire, (ii) the CAPEX & OPEX considerations and (iii) our own estimates.

As TD and GB already operate profitable businesses, the major funding and financing needs are concentrated on the technology provider S360. The above financing structure for the pilot region could be supplemented by using additional financial instruments like leasing, guarantees (e.g. InvestEU SME program) and revenue sharing agreements among the pilot partners.

Diversifying the funding sources will help spread risk across capital providers and increase the flexibility for the pilot region partners.

5.7.1 Key considerations for moving forward

The project is still in early stages with many moving parts and parallel work streams. However, certain areas are particularly critical from a financing perspective. Among the key readiness factors discussed previously, we have identified the following five as essential for advancing to a more mature stage where a broader range of financing sources may become accessible:

- Clarification of legislation at EU and national level through engagement with policymakers and ensuring regulatory compliance is crucial, as the legal classification of urine plays a vital role in the project's success and potential expansion
- Finalised technological development and official third-party certification processes to enhance/ensure marketability as well as clear differentiation from conventional fertilisers

- Clear market demand: Evidence of demand from farmers, breweries, municipalities, for both urine-based fertiliser and for sanitation and urine treatment services. This could include secured supply agreements or letters of intent from retailers. While Sweden is a relatively mature market for fertiliser technologies and farmers show significant acceptance of urine-based fertilisers, the food industry still needs some convincing, which is also why the above-mentioned certifications are vital.
- Proven financial sustainability and clear revenue model leveraging multiple potential revenue streams
- Transparent financial reporting and cash flow projections driven by a strong management team

Once the business model advances on the above factors, matures and reaches its scaling phase, the funding will be able to shift from relying on grants to focusing on equity investments and venture capital to fund more expansive operations.

The following **Table 15** illustrates a possible financing structure following the scale up of the project.

Table 15: Financing structure, scale up and optimisation phase, Gotland pilot region

Pilot Region: Sweden (Scaling & Optimization Phase)						
Uses		in EUR	in %	Sources	in EUR	in %
S360 & TD	Machinery (truck, reactor, etc.)	3.500.000	70%	EIB's Circular Economy - Financing Initiative	Equity & VC	50%
All	Urinals, Toilets			Industrifonden		
	Maintenance					
All	Other Investments			Equity / VC	2.500.000	
	Total Capex					
S360	Rent, personnel costs, maintenance	1.000.000	20%	NEFCO	Local & EU Grants	
GB	Storage, transportation, electricity			EU LIFE Program		
	Chemical stabilizer, granulation provider					
	Certification, R&D					
All	Shipping & malting barley	EIC Accelerator	Blended Finance	Blended finance	1.000.000	20%
	Kegs, Packaging (bottles, caps)					
All	Hop & other ingredients	Almi Företagspartner	Loans	(Green-)Loan	500.000	10%
	Other Working Capital					
Total Opex		1.500.000	30%			
Total		5.000.000	100%	Total	5.000.000	100%

The total funding need of €5.0m has been estimated based on the investment requirements of the current development stage and our own estimates. The allocation of the required financing towards individual financing sources as shown above is just one of many possible options. It is also not mandatory to use or include every type of capital as suggested. The aim here is to illustrate that a combination of different suitable financing sources is recommended in order to diversify the associated risks for investors, but also to establish a robust structure that would be able to support further growth of the business model.

S360, TD, and GB might also consider pursuing a more collaborative financing approach by structuring joint financing agreements to reduce individual risks. For example, S360 could co-finance infrastructure with TD, or they could all share revenue from the fertiliser, sanitation services and beer sales to create more attractive financing options for investors.

For the two key partners TD and GB which already operate an established business, the following additional funding options could be considered:

TD (Urine collection logistics and fertiliser distribution)

TD has a more established business model, but integrating urine collection adds some complexity. Funding options could include:

- Corporate sponsorships and partnerships: TD could form partnerships with municipalities, festival organisers, and large event companies to provide sustainable sanitation services.
- Leasing and loans: For upgrading their fleet and infrastructure, TD could access leasing options for equipment or loans from local banks or institutions to finance the required vehicles and infrastructure upgrades.
- EU waste regulations: Explore any regulatory incentives or specific funds available under EU waste management or circular economy policies.

GB (Barley cultivation & beer production)

GB, being a well-established brewery, has relatively low capital expenditure needs but could still benefit from sustainability-driven financing. Financing options could include:

- Marketing partnerships and branding sponsorships: GB can tap into the growing consumer demand for sustainable and circular economy-focused products by partnering with sustainability-focused beverage brands and retailers.
- Sustainability-linked loans: If GB has already met certain sustainability criteria, it could access more favourable loan terms under sustainability-linked finance options.

The financing structures as illustrated above would allow each partner to secure the funding they need while also fostering collaboration between them. They combine traditional financing (debt/equity) with innovative sources (crowdfunding & blended financing) and provide access to future funding from various financing partners.

5.8 Conclusion

The circular business model in the Swedish pilot region demonstrates a comprehensive value chain approach to nutrient recycling. The integration of diverse stakeholders including sanitation-, technology providers and a brewery demonstrates a closed-loop system in which the possibility of economic activities aligns with sustainability goals.

The business model is characterised by multiple potential revenue streams across upstream and downstream activities. This enhances resilience and adaptability, which are crucial factors for a successful business model (Casadesus-Masanell & Ricart, 2014). The multiple potential revenue streams align with the principles of a successful circular business model, where different parts of the value chain reinforce one another, supporting the overall goal of scaling the urine recycling technology (Ibid). However, as the pilot is still in its early stages, the commercial feasibility and long-term sustainability of the model remain to be demonstrated.

Strengths

With strong engagement from S360 and SLU, the pilot actively explores different revenue opportunities to generate sufficient capital for the substantial upfront investment required for this circular value chain to come into full effect.

The presence of dedicated individuals in the pilot is also instrumental in driving the project forward. This is also present when establishing industrial symbiosis, a part of CE, in which one company's waste becomes another company's input where success often depends on committed actors (Chertow & Ehrenfeld, 2012). Adaptability is another strength, as evidenced by the pilot's willingness to address market barriers. For example, when urine-diverting toilet is not marketed on Gotland, the pilot is looking into how to source this part of the value chain themselves.

Operating within the relatively closed system of Gotland presents both opportunities and challenges. The limited number of local partners may hinder scalability, but the absence of direct competitors - such as alternative urine collectors - reduces market pressure.

Additionally, because Sweden is a frontrunner in nutrient recycling, with a relatively mature market for fertiliser technologies (Aliahmad, Kanda, & McConville, 2023), there is already significant acceptance of urine-based fertilisers among farmers and hobby gardeners. This was demonstrated by the pilot's outreach efforts, which are backed up by scientific research. However, while the agricultural sector is generally receptive, the food industry remains hesitant, underscoring the need for safety validation and certifications to secure broader market acceptance (Ibid).

Despite technological advancements, urine recycling business models have struggled to reach mainstream adoption since their introduction in the 1990s, primarily due to a lack of customers and high operational costs (Ibid). The Swedish pilot faces similar challenges in its early development phase, including scaling limitations, as collecting sufficient urine for large-scale operations presents logistical difficulties. Expanding the customer base for sanitation and urine treatment services is essential in this regard to advance the business model beyond its current reliance on festivals and events to include other sourcing opportunities. The potential to integrate drying systems as a distinct offering would also contribute to increase the scales of urine-based fertiliser production.

Due to the characteristics of the Swedish context, the overall structure of a *cross-subsidising* revenue model poses great opportunities to achieve a financially viable business model (Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, 2019). With farmers being the main target segment of the urine-based fertiliser, the business model relies on a highly price-sensitive segment to achieve profits. Thus, to be competitive S360 must determine the price per kg/ton of fertilisers at a level generating a thin or even nonexciting profit margin. In the long run this could cause cashflow problems and risk the scaling of the technology to reach economies of scale, creating a vicious cycle that reduces the probability of gaining competitiveness against mineral fertilisers. Instead, by

introducing a value proposition catering to less-price sensitive customers, such as hobby gardeners, S360 could cross-subsidise their non-profitable operations to achieve an overall positive cashflow.

Besides the sales of bio-based fertilisers, the pilot region contains several additional revenue streams which can be pursued to increase the viability of the business model. In terms of financing, S360, being in its start-up phase, requires funding and can initially rely on EU and Swedish soft funding while considering equity investments or venture capital later. TD and GB, as established companies, may explore corporate partnerships, equipment leasing, or sustainability-linked loans. As the circular business model is still developing, all three partners need to meet key readiness factors to access broader funding sources.

Challenges

In Sweden, urine is permitted as a fertiliser. However, for the technology to scale successfully, a well-coordinated robust value chain is essential to support the business model. Financial incentives to invest in the pilot business model are currently limited, such as the avoided pollution cost, which is a key value proposition, is currently not recognised or compensated by authorities. As a result, there is little to no financial incentive at this stage (Beneker et al., 2023). High initial costs and dependencies on subsidies further make financial sustainability uncertain, as the substantial investments required, coupled with investor scepticism, hinders access to long-term funding. Investment from investors has proven difficult so far, since the lack of a proven market for the offerings provided by S360 makes it difficult to win investor confidence. This, combined with the pilot's reliance on soft funding, remains a critical vulnerability.

Another key challenge, common in circular business models, is the complexity of logistics required to collect and transport urine, which contrasts with the steady and reliable supply chains of conventional fertiliser production. Evident from the Swedish pilot region, is the need for constant coordination across the entire value chain and involvement from S360 taking on a key coordinating role to maintain a circular flow of nutrients. Additionally, maintaining control is crucial to secure profitability of closed loop value chains (Lewandowski, 2016). In this relation, the efforts of S360 have contributed to secure control over as many key touchpoints as possible and has shown necessary to mitigate the pitfalls of circular value chains by innovating and streamlining upstream activities which are crucial for future scaling.

The Swedish pilot has access to urine needed for production, however a constant flow of urine is challenged by the current lack of a functioning production site. This leads to a halt in the production, making it difficult to market and sell the products but at the same time, the Swedish pilot is missing the financial resources to invest in the production facility. Financial resources could come from long lasting relationships and contracts with customers, which should be an area of focus and requires sales. However, at this point the Swedish pilot region is missing the sales force to be able to market and sell

the fertiliser to farmers and hobby gardeners. These financial resources tied up in contracts would strengthen the possibility to scale the production facility.

Although there are several value propositions catered to different customer segments, they are yet to fully mature. For example, to be able to scale the offer connected to value proposition 1, *sanitation services*, investments in unisex urinals and trucks for urine separation must be undertaken as neither S360 nor TD currently own these resources. Additionally, value proposition 3, *drying system services*, relies on potential customers to take on some of the responsibility of urine drying, a role that has until now been exclusively managed by S360's operations.

Moreover, to be able to provide- and scale the production of low environmental impact beers, the business model relies on breweries, such as GB, to integrate it into their product portfolios. The environmental focus of Spendrups' management is a key factor in this regard, driving the adoption of such a product within the food industry. Additionally, it requires that GB's supplying farmers are willing to purchase and use the urine-based fertiliser. Naturally, the decision-making of farmers is characterised as a non-controllable variable from the perspective of S360. However, different factors may improve the likelihood of farmers adopting this type of fertiliser. One factor is obtaining a certifications that secure the safety of using the urine-based fertiliser. This will ensure that farmers can showcase to customers such as GB, that the safety of the barley can be trusted for consumption. A second factor is related to the relationships between farmers and the breweries such as GB or their mother company, Spendrups. Since the breweries have already established relationships with farmers in place, they possess the power to demand that some percentages of the malt they purchase should be based on urine-based fertilisers. However, this would require that the breweries become willing to pay a potentially higher price for their supplies. While this shift may come with higher upfront costs, internalising the environmental costs of traditional fertilisers, such as pollution, environmental degradation, and health impacts, can make the case for higher prices. As these external costs are accounted for, conventional fertilisers will become more expensive, while more sustainable alternatives, like urine-based fertilisers, will become more competitive.

Recognising and internalising these externalities in the current system is crucial for building a sustainable and competitive business model. This will make the solutions proposed in the pilot regions have the potential to emerge as competitive alternatives in the marketplace.

Addressing barriers related to securing consistent financial revenue streams will be important when transitioning from a pilot phase to a fully operational, self-sustaining circular business model. In terms of revenue streams and value propositions, the business model currently relies on a wide range of activities. A key improvement would be to validate more of the assumptions underlying the model, such as whether customers perceive the proposed value as expected. Additionally, it would be beneficial to identify and focus on the most promising revenue streams while addressing

bottlenecks that hinder scaling. Strengthening financial stability will require securing reliable funding sources, whether through performance-based subsidies, strategic partnerships, or direct sales. Finally, optimising operational efficiency, particularly in urine collection logistics and fertiliser production, will be essential for achieving scalability and cost-effectiveness.

6 Introduction to the pilot region: North German Plain

6.1 The potential of the North German Plain

The North German Plain consists of regions in Northern Germany, respectively Berlin, Hamburg, and Eberswalde, along with surrounding rural areas in the federal states of Brandenburg and Lower Saxony.

The North German Plain is increasingly confronted with challenges related to climate change and environmental challenges. The area is characterised by intense land use and persistent challenges of nutrient pollution which are discharged into the environment through fertiliser runoff from agriculture and effluents from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) in urban zones. These nutrient loads have led to severe water quality degradation across the region. Around 90% of the coastal water bodies of the Baltic of North Sea are classified as being in moderate to poor ecological and chemical condition, reflecting a broader regional imbalance (Umweltbundesamt, 2017)

Meanwhile, the urban growth in Berlin is straining existing wastewater systems, especially with new large-scale industrial facilities adding to the nutrient burden. Adding to the complexity is the energy-intensive nature of nutrient removal in WWTPs. These processes can account for as much as 20% of total municipal energy consumption (Simha & Ganesapillai, 2017), raising both environmental and economic concerns.

By improving nutrient recycling, reducing wastewater treatment, and aligning with circular economy principles, the region can become a pioneer in sustainable nutrient and water management, addressing current problems while setting a precedent for innovation-driven environmental recovery.

6.2 Introduction to the pilot region

The North German Plain pilot demonstrates two solutions transforming sanitary waste to biobased fertilisers and thereby closing nutrient cycles for nitrogen and phosphorous. In the pilot, several partners collaborate in a circular value chain by separating and collecting urine and faeces from portable toilets from urban settlements and through two different methods turn the collected resources, urine and faeces, respectively, into safe biobased fertilisers for agriculture. The urine is turned into a liquid fertiliser, whereas the faeces are turned into compost.

The collaborating partners in the North German Plain region aim to solve urgent environmental challenges, such as water scarcity, high nitrogen and micropollutants emissions to surface water leading to eutrophication and contamination of ground water as well as soil degradation.

By producing fertiliser and compost from urine and faeces the pilot partners aim to demonstrate multiple benefits upstream and downstream. It reduces the need for usage of drinking water used for flushing toilets, removes the micropollutants from source separated sanitary waste and mitigates nitrogen and phosphorous emissions released

to natural water bodies such as the Elbe and Weser River basins. Through the collaboration, the pilot region aims at reclaiming approximately 1.140 kg of nitrogen and 320 kg of phosphorus per year. The biobased fertilisers are currently used in trial fields to cultivate rye and barley (P2Green Project, n.d.).

In terms of barriers, the national legislative framework currently presents significant challenges in the North German Plain region hindering a materialisation of the business model as the commercialisation of the biobased fertiliser is currently prohibited.

6.3 Two circular business models

The North German Plain region represents two ways of recycling sanitary resources. The Swiss technology provider VunaNexus (VN) produces a liquid fertiliser based on urine and the company Goldeimer (GE) produces compost based on faeces. The North German Plain region is described as one pilot region and several of the same organisations are the same for both fertiliser's value chains. It is the same partner that collects both resources and another partner, Vagtshoff farm (VH), is currently using both fertilisers for test trials. However, turning the sanitation into fertiliser undergoes two different processes by two different companies and since these two are not needed together to produce fertiliser there is also a possibility of the two companies acting without the other. For this reason, two business models are developed for the North German Plain respectively, one for the liquid fertiliser (VN) and one for the faecal compost (GE).

However, the flow model below illustrates the value creation flow parameters between the partners on a pilot region level. Along with the monetary flow added to represent hypothetical internal financial flows as a part of the possible revenue streams, a customer environmental value creation flow has been added to reflect KWB's dual role as project partner and building owner. Due to the close connections of the two circular business models, the environmental and organisational value creation flows are presented jointly in the sections to come, while financial value creation flows are presented separately.

Figure 3: Value creation flow parameters between partners in the German pilot region.

7 Circular business model: VunaNexus x KWB

7.1 Introduction

This business model offers the possibility to transform urine into liquid urine-based fertiliser, through their Aurin branded treatment technology, as an alternative to traditional sewage systems, by preventing urine from entering the sewage system and ultimately being wasted. The original business model envisaged VN, the technology provider, to install Aurin treatment systems in an Ecovillage in Hanover (EVH), where urine diverting flush toilets would be installed. However, due to external challenges, EVH had to leave the P2Green project and KWB joined instead, as a representative for a regional recycling hub (including human urine and feces from dry toilets), fully owned by the county of Barnim. All analysis and findings presented are based on the updated German pilot region configuration as defined in the P2Green 2nd Amendment (May 2024), which includes KWB as a project partner and excludes previously included Ecovillage as a partner.

In the current arrangement, KWB hosts the physical installation of Vuna's Aurin treatment system. The project partner Finizio delivers collected urine to this site, where it is processed into Aurin — a liquid, urine-based fertiliser marketed under the VN brand. The treatment plant supplied by VN is in the process of being scaled up to Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 7. Fertiliser produced as part of the P2Green project is currently being tested in field trials at the Vagtshoff farm.

VN is currently in operation in Switzerland and France, outside P2Green, where Aurin is approved for use in Austria, Switzerland, France and Lichtenstein. However, the collection and production of fertiliser in a set up in Germany is still in its development phase, solely being tested in P2Green. Current regulations do not allow commercialisation, and even though the technology has proven operational in outside of Germany, the fertiliser may not be sold until legal conditions change. However, VN expects that regulatory adjustments will eventually enable market entry.

As a result, the scaling of this envisioned business model is currently limited by legal restrictions. The following section describes how the circular business model is expected to function if the legal barrier was removed.

Figure 4 illustrates the envisioned circular process, where biobased fertiliser derived from urine helps close the loop from farm to fork.

Figure 4: Circular supply chain - VN x KWB part of the North German Plain

In the following section the assumptions and decisions made when developing the business model is described. Following this, the CBMC is described through its building blocks: *value proposition*, *value creation & delivery*, and *value capture*. Additionally, the organisational, financial, and environmental value creation flows are explored and integrated throughout the business model. The CBMC describes how the business model is expected to function if the legal barrier was removed. The full circular business model canvas is illustrated in Appendix II: Circular Business Model Canvas: VunaNexus.

7.2 Assumptions and decisions

- The business model is developed with its main focus on VN, as VN is the provider of the technology producing biobased fertiliser. VN is the link connecting partners, that already exist in the marketplace, and VN is critical to the success of the circular business model.
- Although the original business model aimed to deliver the Aurin treatment system to building owners, this arrangement has not been realised through P2Green. Since

this deliverable aim is to develop a business model for the pilot region, it involves both KWB and VN, which represents a unique and context specific scenario of the business model, rather than the intended scalable solution.

- In the business model, KWB will take on a dual role. On one hand, they simulate the role of a building owner, thereby acting as a customer investing in the Aurin treatment system which was originally assigned to EVH. On the other hand, it must be recognised that KWB adds additional value to the business model beyond that of a traditional building owner, through their operations as a local resource recovery site. Because they have already established partnerships with the local sanitation service provider, Finizio, and the public authorities of Barnim County, they serve as a platform connecting these entities with the technology provider, VN. Therefore, KWB fulfil a role that benefits all parties, along with the public authorities by acting as a waste management provider for the local county. This role has implications for the value capturing mechanisms proposed under revenue streams, where payments towards KWB is included despite not forming a distinct value proposition of the business model. In the outlook section, the business model will be discussed from a scaling perspective, exploring how it can evolve beyond this unique context.
- The biobased fertiliser is currently hindered by legislation in Germany that prevents the commercialisation of fertilisers derived from urine or faeces. As a result, a fully implemented business model is not yet possible. As a result, the CBMC illustrates the envisioned business model building on VN's current operations in Switzerland and France.
- Due to the maturity of the fertiliser, and this not being on the market yet, some of the areas in the business model are based on assumptions made by the pilot region partners hence costs and revenues are based on both actual and estimated costs drafted from the data input provided by the technology provider VN which is presented as percentages.
- Throughout the business model, when environmental claims are made these may not be used for communication purposes unless these are documented, for example through a life-cycle analysis or similar documentation. Focus of this deliverable is the business models of the pilots, whereas work package 2 (D2.3) documents the environmental impact of the pilot regions.

7.3 Value proposition

The value proposition consists of two value propositions that serve different customer segments.

Table 16: Value proposition, VN x KWB part of North German Plain

Value proposition		Value created for customer segment
Upstream and production	Aurin treatment system	<p>Building owners (public and private) & real estate developers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offers a permanent installation solution. • Generates revenue through fertiliser sales. • Saves costs to sewage connection fees. • Improves environmental image, supporting sustainability goals. • Reduces CO₂ emissions by bypassing traditional WWTPs. <p>Construction sites, and waste management sites.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offers a customisable, container-based solution. • Potential for ROI for otherwise wasted resource.
Production	Aurin fertiliser	<p>Hobby gardeners</p> <p>Locally sourced, circular fertiliser supports the local environment.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appeals to eco-conscious consumers. <p>Municipalities and public authorities</p> <p>Enhances sustainability by using locally sourced fertiliser for public green areas.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports environmental goals and showcases eco-friendly practices. <p>Farmers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduces exposure to global fertiliser price fluctuations, especially during price hikes. • Offers competitive performance in NPK and trace elements, improving soil and plant health. • Reduces CO₂ emissions compared to mineral fertilisers.

Aurin treatment system, upstream and production

Aurin treatment system is a decentralised solution for processing urine, targeted at building owners, real estate developers, public utilities, and construction sites. The system allows clients to turn a waste product into a valuable resource, while also improving their environmental image.

The Aurin treatment system offers two installation options: a permanent system for buildings or a customisable container-based solution. The container-based solution represented a new approach to operate the Aurin treatment system but create similar benefits for clients, such as KWB, as it does for building owners.

Customers invest in the system upfront, covering the CAPEX for installation. In return, the customers earn revenue from Aurin fertiliser sales marketed by VN, with the potential for a return on investment (ROI) within 10-15 years. Additionally, the system eliminates the need for sewage connections, offering savings on fixed and variable sewage fees, especially in the German market.

When KWB or another ‘building owner’ installs the Aurin treatment system it will require a significant amount of capital to be tied with the facility. However, in cases where building owners must adhere to a CO2 limit or budget, the Aurin treatment system provides a solution to help meet these requirements.

The environmental benefits include utilisation of nitrogen and phosphorus (N&P) instead of discharging them into nearby waters, and reducing CO2 emissions by avoiding energy-intensive wastewater treatment processes (Tristan, 2021). For commercial clients, particularly real estate developers or other building owners, ecological technology helps them achieve eco-building standards like BREEAM³, adding greater value to the building by enhancing the building’s environmental credentials.

Aurin fertiliser, production

Aurin fertiliser is a liquid urine-based fertiliser authorised in Austria, Switzerland and Lichtenstein. It targets farmers, hobby gardeners, and public institutions, such as municipalities. For hobby gardeners and municipalities, the main appeal lies in the local sourcing of the Aurin fertiliser, which contrasts with mineral fertilisers that are energy intensive to produce and transported over long distances. This local, circular nutrient flow supports eco-political motivations, enabling gardeners and municipalities to contribute to the local environment by using a sustainable, locally produced fertiliser in their gardens and public green spaces.

Farmers also benefit from the local nature of the Aurin fertiliser, but their main focus is on its efficiency and performance in boosting agricultural yields. While the price of Aurin

³ Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method (BREEAM) is a certification system used to specify and measure the sustainability performance of buildings, helping to meet sustainability goals over time (BREEAM 2025)

fertiliser cannot yet compete with mineral fertilisers on a per ton basis, it provides stability during global price fluctuations of mineral fertilisers.

7.3.1 Customer segments

The business model offers two value propositions which appeal to several customer segments as described in the **Table 17** below.

Table 17: Customer segments, VN x KWB part of the North German Plain

Customer segments	
Aurin treatment system catering to building owners, sanitation providers and venues	<p>Building owners (public and private) & real estate developers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsible for waste management in new buildings. • Seek alternatives to traditional sewage systems to reduce installation and operational costs. • Interested in sustainable solutions that align with environmental goals. <p>Construction- and waste management sites</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manage wastewater. • Need efficient solutions for urine treatment and nutrient recycling. • May benefit from adding Aurin treatment system to their service portfolio. • Handle temporary sanitation for large crowds (e.g., workers or visitors). • Need scalable, cost-effective urine management solutions. Interested in alternatives to traditional sewage infrastructure for high-volume, short-term use.
Aurin fertiliser to farmers, hobby gardeners, municipalities and fertiliser producers	<p>Farmers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on productive farms with profitable crop yields. • Pragmatic approach to fertiliser procurement, prioritising effectiveness over origin. • Need large volumes and trust-building for efficient fertiliser use. • Often rely on specialists like agronomists for fertiliser guidance. <p>Professional- and hobby gardeners</p>

- Interested in using locally sourced, sustainable products for small-scale gardening.
- Motivated by being part of a circular nutrient flow.

Municipalities and public authorities

- Responsible for fertilising public green areas.
- Prefer locally sourced fertilisers to reduce dependence on conventional, long-distance transported fertilisers.

Fertiliser producers

- Interested in nitrogen sources with diverse trace elements
- Further testing needed

Aurin treatment system catering to building owners, sanitation providers and venues

Building owners (public and private) and real estate developers

Building owners and real estate developers are responsible for choosing the systems that will support the functionality of a building, including sanitation. Building owners include sports arenas, airports, and other publicly owned buildings facing unique challenges in managing high volumes of human excreta. Their main challenge is the high costs and logistical complexity associated with connecting buildings to the traditional sewage system. These customer segments need cost effective alternatives that streamline building operations and reduce long term infrastructure expenses. The Aurin treatment system provides a decentralised solution that eliminates the need for sewage connections. Thus, the Aurin treatment system offers a more sustainable and economically viable option during the early stages of construction, due to customers not being forced to pay sewage connection fees, and the recurring fees based on the volumes of wastewater produced in the building (elaborated under value capture).

Construction- and waste management sites

Temporary venues, such as construction sites also face challenges related to management of human excreta. These entities require systems that can handle high traffic and provide efficient sanitation without relying on conventional sewage infrastructure. They need a solution that reduces logistical complexities, minimises environmental impact, and is adaptable to temporary or evolving locations. The Aurin container-based treatment system addresses these needs by offering flexible and decentralised sanitation.

Additionally, waste management sites, whether public, private, or a hybrid of both, are responsible for servicing local communities through the recycling of various waste

streams. The Aurin treatment system presents an opportunity for waste management sites to diversify their operations onto nutrient recycling by handling human excreta in a more sustainable and efficient manner. The successful implementation of the Aurin system could pave the way for these organisations to introduce nutrient recycling on a larger scale, driving new revenue streams and helping them align with evolving environmental standards.

Aurin fertiliser

Farmers (B2B)

Farmers represent an important future target segment for the Aurin fertiliser, representing a business to business (B2B) customer. Currently, VN has sold very limited amounts to farmers wanting to test the fertiliser in trials. Farmers focus on running a productive farm with profitable crop yields and are therefore often pragmatic in their approach to fertiliser procurement. They do not care much about the fertilisers place of origin, if it can provide satisfying amounts of nitrogen per kg. to contribute to their margins which are often already relatively low.

Professional and hobby gardeners (B2C)

Currently, the most accessible customer segment for Aurin is professional- and hobby gardeners representing a business to consumer (B2C) customer. This is due to the scale of fertiliser they are able to produce. This segment values local and sustainably sourced products to fertilise gardens or crops. By using Aurin, this customer segment gains a sense of self-expression and emotional through contributing to the green agenda as part of a circular nutrient flow.

Municipalities and public authorities (B2G)

Municipalities and public authorities represent a business to government (B2G) customer. Just as hobby gardeners, the main benefits for municipalities or other public authorities, that fertilise green areas of the local community is contributing to the CE and local job creation by using a locally sourced and produced fertiliser.

Fertiliser producers (B2B)

A potential customer segment is identified as fertiliser producers, who need nitrogen sources as input material for the production of fertilisers. The Aurin fertiliser contains the potential to be used as input for conventional fertiliser production or biochar enrichment due to its diverse trace elements. However, further testing is needed for this segment to become viable.

7.3.2 Customer relationships

As customers are crucial for VN, this section explores the customer relationships and clarifies the type of customer relationships that VN should establish for each of the above-mentioned customer segments to foster.

Aurin treatment system – automated service relationship

The relationship between VN and their customers will be based on automated maintenance contracts. Normally, these contracts will vary between 3-5 years with VN's personnel performing maintenance of the Aurin treatment system when needed. One critical element of this relationship is the lock-in effect created by the patented nitrite sensor. This sensor allows VN to guarantee that the reactor is functioning as without it, the reactor would not function properly. Due to the patented nature of the nitrite sensor, VN remains the exclusive provider of system maintenance. Thus, the customers cannot operate the system on their own and rely on the capabilities and maintenance contracts with VN.

Similarly, VN is currently the only organisation in Europe having the license to sell the Aurin fertiliser, meaning that customers are locked in with VN, by relying on their abilities to generate revenue from the fertiliser which represent direct ROI for the client. This approach also ensures that the Aurin treatment system can be sold at the lowest price possible, because revenue is created from both fertiliser sales and maintenance contracts.

A unique feature of the maintenance contracts is the possibility of reduced costs for the customer. The contract will contain a fixed yearly fee to be paid, but if VN manages to sell fertilisers at certain thresholds, the client will be offered to pay less in maintenance fees. This also feeds into the last crucial element of the customer relationship, which is the focus on trust building with the client. VN aims to be transparent on everything they do and try to showcase for customers that they are attempting to be financially viable and not exploiting their customers financially.

Aurin fertiliser – personal indirect relationships

The relationship between VN and their customers of the fertiliser depend heavily on the sales channel used. VN has an opportunity to serve the few local farms that already collaborate with KWB or a few municipal customers through dedicated personal relationships, where clients are taught about the use and benefits of the Aurin fertiliser. However, dedicated personal relationships with all B2B or B2G customers will likely not be viable when entering the wider German market, where two different strategies can be applied, having consequences for the customer relationships. The first strategy is related to the western part of Germany which is still operated under the agricultural chamber system. Here, VN should approach the agricultural chamber of a specific region, since this entity often performs the knowledge transfer to farmers by engaging with them in workshops, training sessions, etc. For the eastern part of Germany, no agricultural chamber exists, meaning that VN should approach different agricultural consultants directly, since these are in direct contact with the farmers of this part of the country. With both strategies the customer relationships will be more indirect, requiring VN to educate the consultants of the chamber, and the consultancy agencies about the benefits of the fertiliser, to promote it among possible farming clients. Similarly, the

relationship between VN and the B2C customers will rely on indirect relationships, with intermediaries playing an important role in communicating about the use and benefits of the fertiliser. In all instances, creating a well reputed brand will be important for VN to create recognition and loyalty among the customers.

7.4 Value creation and delivery

7.4.1 Key activities

The value chain includes urine collection and treatment through urine diverting flush toilets leading to an Aurin treatment system that transforms urine into Aurin fertiliser leading to sales and marketing of Aurin with the goal of closing the nutrient loop in the Barnim county. Therefore, the key activities of the German pilot are categorised into upstream, production, and downstream activities, with upstream and fertiliser as the core focus due to the legal barrier in marketing and selling the fertiliser in Germany.

Upstream

The first actions of the key upstream activities are performed by KWB and involve the active management of collaborations between sanitation providers, in this case Finizio, technology provider, VN, involving governance of their permission to operate on the premises. These activities are vital to allow Finizio to dispose of the urine collected from festivals, events or public areas and to allow VN to install their Aurin treatment system as KWB's premises. Moreover, KWB undertakes the management of internal logistics at their premises. By carrying out these activities, KWB replaces the need for public wastewater treatment, thereby fulfilling an essential function within the sanitation infrastructure.

Production

When urine is disposed it enters the Aurin treatment system which initiates the fertiliser production phase. Here, the urine is stabilised through a nitrification process in the built-in reactor, from where the urine is then processed through active carbon filters with the remaining liquid being pasteurised and concentrated in an industrial distiller. This process generates two outputs. One is reusable distilled water and the second is the Aurin fertiliser. The fertiliser is bottled into small bottles (500ml – 20L) for hobby gardeners, and intermediate bulk containers for B2B and B2G customers. Alongside production, the Aurin treatment system and its infrastructure are maintained by VN. However, the system is designed to minimise the need for maintenance, making this primarily relevant in situations where the system is not working properly.

Downstream

The key downstream activities include marketing and sales activities performed by VN, alongside distribution of the Aurin fertiliser to the customers. These distribution activities will be dependent on key partners of the business model, which will be elaborated in the following sections.

Table 18: Key activities, VN x KWB part of the North German Plain

Key activities	Description of key activities
Key upstream activities	1. Governance of permission to dispose of urine and operate Aurin treatment system at the premise of KWB (KWB)
	2. Collection of urine at festivals, events or public venues (Finizio)
	3. Disposal of urine at the premises of KWB (Finizio)
	4. Management of logistics at the production premises (KWB)
Key production activities	5. Aurin fertiliser production (VN) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Stabilisation and carbon filtration of urine (VN) b. Pasteurisation and concentration of stabilised urine (VN)
	6. Bottling and packaging of the fertiliser (VN)
	7. Maintenance of infrastructure and Aurin technology (VN)
Key downstream activities	8. Marketing and sales activities (VN)
	9. Distribution of Aurin to customers (external partners)

7.4.2 Key resources

The key resources are listed in **Table 19**.

Table 19: Key resources, VN x KWB part of the North German Plain

Key resources	Description of resources	Status
Physical resources	Source-separating toilets	Available through Finizio
	Container-based facility	Available through KWB
	Aurin treatment technology	Available through VN
Human resources	Technical personnel	Available through VN
	Sales force	Missing by VN
Intellectual resources	Nitrite sensor patent (IP rights (licensing but not ownership)	Available through VN

	Aurin sales license	Missing by law
	Brand equity	Available through VN
	Partnerships with sanitation provider and public authorities	Available through KWB
	Customer database for urine collection	Available through Finizio
Financial resources	Grants and R&D money including P2Green funding	Available but with a time limit
	Commercial activities outside P2Green (>€1M).	Available through VN

Physical resources

The most critical physical resources of the business model are the Aurin treatment system provided by VN, along with the premises of KWB with specific areas and facility devoted to Aurin treatment system.

Human resources

VN provide key human resources with their technical personnel possessing the needed expertise to install and maintain the Aurin treatment system. The system is monitored remotely by VN personnel, with an additional on-site technical employee available to assist whenever needed. It is assessed that a sales force to reach agricultural chambers and consultants will be necessary to promote Aurin fertiliser in the German market.

Intellectual resources

The nitrite sensor under development and currently at TRL 7 (Beneker et al., 2023) is patented by VN, and act to protect the capabilities of the Aurin treatment system from imitation. In addition, the Aurin fertiliser is the only certified urine-based fertiliser in Europe, and VN is the sole organisation with a license to sell it. These intellectual properties are vital, serving as lock-in mechanisms that foster long-term customer relationships since VN must be involved in the marketing of Aurin fertiliser. Furthermore, VN possesses an already established brand in the Swiss market, generating a potential to spill-over when scaling for other European markets like the German and brings legitimacy to the products and services of the business model.

Although not an official P2Green partner, Finizio bring an important intellectual resource to the business model. Through their established urine collection practices, they

possess a customer database of festivals, events, and public actors which is crucial to sustain a continuous flow of nutrients.

Financial resources

The financial resources related to the pilot region consists of grants, such as R&D grants. Additionally, VN is backed up by funds from the P2Green project, and the European Space Agency, while their operations in Switzerland generates vital financial resources through commercial activities related to the Aurin treatment system.

7.4.3 Key partners

The key partners in the VN x KWB part of the North German Plain are:

Kreiswerke Barnim (KWB) is a German regional waste and recycling management organisation acting as the pilot coordinator. They govern and control the physical premises and facilities for the Aurin treatment system, and the partnerships with public sanitation provider, Finizio, along with public authorities.

KWB provides different services to the local county of Barnim, ranging from household waste collection, street maintenance, provision of renewable energy, and through P2Green, their recycling activities now include nutrient recycling. KWB is a 100% public county-owned company, although operating in a traditional commercial manner, receiving no public support and competing with other private actors. The main motivation of their engagement in P2Green is to contribute to showcase Barnim as a lighthouse for sustainable development in an economically viable fashion.

VunaNexus (VN) is a Swiss company originating from the Swiss Federal Institute of Aquatic Science and Technology (EAWAG). VN provides the treatment technology through their Aurin treatment system, which will be located at the premises of KWB during the project. The main activities performed by VN is related to production of the urine-based Aurin fertiliser and the subsequent management of marketing and sales to reach customers.

Vagtshoff Farm (VH) is a farm located in the lower saxony near Hamburg, that provides an agricultural area (6 ha) for fertiliser application used to test the performance of the Aurin fertiliser.

Table 20 provides a list of key suppliers, distributors, and other key stakeholders for the VN x KWB German pilot:

Table 20: Key partners, VN x KWB part of the North German Plain

Resources provided or activity performed

Key suppliers	Finizio <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Finizio will supply urine from Berlin and the surrounding areas and undertake transportation to the KWB site. However, all agreements related to logistics have not yet been finalised meaning that KWB currently perform some of the necessary activities. When the business model is fully operating, these issues must be solved to make the logistics automatic and efficient.
	Technology component suppliers <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Existing relationships with suppliers of components to build and maintain the Aurin treatment system will ensure that the system can be scaled and operated continuously.
	Bottle- and intermediate bulk container suppliers <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Existing relationships with suppliers of bottles and intermediate bulk containers will ensure that Aurin can be packaged for distribution to customers.
Key distributors	Third-party transportation providers <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Transportation of Aurin to intermediaries and customers will be performed by third-party transportation providers. While no agreements have been made as it is not allowed for marketing, the use of intermediate bulk containers allows the urine to be transported by most transportation providers.

	<p>Goldeimer</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• GE poses as a potential distributor of the Aurin bottles. There is an opportunity to utilise their capabilities and resources related to marketing and sales which are already present in the P2Green consortium. While not being a must, their well-established online web-shop represents an obvious candidate for reaching customers. Currently, discussions are ongoing to organise this arrangement. <p>Intermediaries of fertiliser for Business to Business (B2B) segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• The current flow rates of urine are only sufficient to engage 2-3 local farmers. KWB already has existing trust-based relationships with these farmers, including aligned expectations on the volumes of fertilisers to be delivered. However, when scaling and expanding the market shares it will become relevant to engage with relevant intermediaries of fertiliser (agricultural cooperations, -chambers and -consultants) rather than relying solely on direct relationships with farmers (elaborated under key channels). <p>Retailers for Business to Consumer (B2C) segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Garden retailers will be necessary to reach individual gardeners, however, the most obvious solution would be to initiate this part of the distribution system through collaboration with GE.
<p>Other key partners</p>	<p>Public water authorities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Collaboration with public water authorities is critical for the business model, because the authorities own the wastewater of the county. Thus, they possess the power to terminate the business foundation depending on whether human excreta are defined as wastewater or not. While no collaboration is currently in place, this is critical for the future operation and scaling of the solution, to ensure that VN gets financially compensated for their treatment capabilities like any other WWTP. When initiating collaboration, it is important to address the potential conflict of interest related to the WWTPs receiving less amounts of urine, which might lead to decreases in their operational efficiency. <p>Leibniz Institute of Vegetable and Ornamental Crops (IGZ)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Responsible for the amounts of fertiliser to be applied to maximise crop yield for the specific types of grain in collaboration with VH and VN.

Building certification providers

- While not being critical for the current setup in KWB, being integrated to and appreciated by building certifications will contribute to increase the motivation of building owners to invest in the Aurin treatment system for future scaling of the system. VN is currently in discussions with Swiss certification providers on how to make this feasible.

Legislative bodies (regional, national, EU)

- Support and collaboration with legislative bodies is important, as they possess the authority to implement legal measures that can enable the business model. Currently, existing legal frameworks hinder the product's marketing.

7.4.4 Channels

The key channels of the German business model are divided into the following channel categories:

- Channels that are vital to raise awareness about the circular nutrient value chain, the Aurin treatment system and the urine-based Aurin fertiliser.
- Channels that are vital to enable customers of the Aurin fertiliser to evaluate its functionality.
- Channels that are vital to distribute, deliver and allow customers to purchase the Aurin fertiliser
- Channels that are vital for the after-sales support.

Raising awareness

The small Aurin fertiliser bottles (500 mL) play an important role in raising awareness around utilisation of urine for agricultural or garden purposes. The overall goal of the business model is not necessarily to flood the fertiliser market with these bottles. Rather, they act as an important communication tool to educate consumers. Thus, the business model will rely on VN's production of Aurin bottles to promote the circular nutrient loop, with the specific communication channels being owned by the retailers such as GE making it available in their webshop. The aligned visions of GE and VN makes a communication collaboration relevant in this respect. As addressed in the previous section, education of agricultural consultants and agricultural chambers is also vital to help raise awareness of the Aurin fertiliser.

Enabling evaluation

To enable customers to evaluate the value proposition of the Aurin fertiliser, external third parties play an important role. In Germany, specialists, consultants, and agronomists possess know-how and build trust relationships with farmers and advise them on e.g., how much fertiliser they need per hectare. Thus, it is most likely that producers of fertiliser, such as VN, has no direct interaction with farmers. In this sense, third-party organisations own a vital channel to teach customers about the use and benefits of the fertiliser.

In P2Green, VN already conducted research of Aurin application with the IGZ (Leibniz Institute of Vegetable and Ornamental Crops) who are undertaking further testing. IGZ decides the amounts of fertiliser to be applied to maximise crop yield for the specific types of grain in collaboration with VH. Publication of such results by IGZ would provide a means to enable farmers, especially, to evaluate the functionality of Aurin. Additionally, the agricultural chambers possess certification power, which would also help customers assess and evaluate the features of the fertiliser.

For the Aurin treatment system, a possible evaluation channel is related to the third-party building certifications such as BREEAM. Being integrated with such certification schemes will contribute to increasing the legitimacy of the system and thereby help potential customers to evaluate the benefits of investing in such a system.

Purchase, delivery, and distribution channels

In the short term, KWB's existing relationships with farmers, represent a possible purchase channel for the Aurin fertiliser produced in the P2Green. However, when scaling and expanding the market, different German agricultural intermediaries own vital purchase channels to move beyond direct relationships with farmers. When aiming to scale for nearby countries such as Switzerland, farming cooperatives own important purchase channels since such cooperatives dominate large parts of the markets, and import, produce, and resell fertilisers for farmers. In other contexts, partnering with agricultural industries have proven essential to take advantage of already established fertiliser distribution networks (Otoo et al. 2018).

As mentioned earlier, GE own a possible channel to allow individual gardeners to purchase the Aurin fertiliser. Their established webshop already serves customers with products catering to the relevant target segments of Aurin, meaning it poses an obvious opportunity to be utilised for future sales. Alternatively, garden retailers own relevant externally owned purchase channels with a possibility to integrate Aurin to their product portfolio.

In relation to distribution, no agreements with third-party transportation providers have been organised yet. However, the use of either intermediate bulk containers or bottles for Aurin fertiliser eases the identification of relevant partners, due to the well-established transportation methods for these containers. It must be noted that the

economic viability of distribution depends on the volumes and distances to customers. Shipping from remote locations, e.g., islands, will not always make sense.

After sales support channels

For the Aurin treatment system, VN own the channel in which customers will be provided with after sales services. Often this element will be integrated into maintenance contracts. In relation to the Aurin fertiliser, farming consultants, and advisors own the most obvious after-sales support channel, due to education and training often being part of their services toward farmers. For individual gardeners, this job will most likely be undertaken by the intermediary distributing the Aurin bottles. Thus, VN is required to ensure that these intermediaries are educated and have access to the right information to perform such services.

7.5 Value capture

7.5.1 Revenue streams

The circular business model of the VN x KWB part of the North German Plain region will capture value through different possible revenue streams. In many instances, the partners will each be responsible for their own specific value capturing mechanisms and how they organise their revenue streams, while for some revenue streams it will depend on organisational agreements between the partners and public entities. Together, the revenue streams should be able to capture the value created by all partners, from facilitation of urine management to fertiliser production and sales for the circular business model to be viable. Currently, no revenue streams exist within P2Green, meaning the following sections will be based on possible and envisioned revenue streams.

Table 21: Revenue streams, VN x KWB part of the North German Plain

Revenue stream	Description
Aurin treatment system sale (KWB/building owners to VN)	<p>The building owners pay for the installation of and the Aurin treatment system and gain formal ownership of the system. The building owners are paid back by fertiliser sales stemming from the collected urine from their specific buildings and are expected to gain ROI within 10-15 years.</p> <p>Investments in the Aurin treatment system represent a crucial transactional revenue stream to ensure economic viability during the initial phase of the business model's lifecycle. The payment for the system is characterised as a traditional asset sale, where the customer gains formal ownership of the system. To ensure competitiveness and willingness to buy the system, the technology sales aim only to cover the CAPEX incurred by VN. Thereby these sales</p>

	<p>are not contributing to secure profitable margins within the business model. VN, in return, covers the OPEX of the system including the activities related to operating the facilities (ensuring an effective production, as opposed to maintenance which is covered by the client), while at the same time carrying out the tasks related to the bottling, marketing and sales of the Aurin fertiliser.</p> <p>In the very long term, under the assumption that an operating business model is continuously optimised and proving that the system can produce enough fertiliser, there is an opportunity to phase out this revenue stream. In such a scenario, VN would bear the costs of installing the system, for example, at a construction site or an airport. This approach will ensure that the customer benefits from free connection to the system, while VN will benefit from the revenue stream generated from fertiliser sales.</p>
Maintenance contract fees (KWB/building owners to VN)	<p>One critical revenue stream to ensure profits from operating the Aurin treatment systems is the maintenance contracts between VN and the customers of the system. With very limited margins on the transactional technology sales, the maintenance contract is characterised as a 3–5-year subscription like agreement that will lock-in the customers to VN services and ensure recurring revenue related to the use of the system.</p>
Aurin fertiliser sales (B2B, B2G, and B2C clients to VN)	<p>Another critical element of VN’s value capturing mechanisms is the transactional sales of Aurin fertiliser. These revenue streams are separated based on the different target segments. When selling for farmers or customers such as municipalities, the revenue stream will be related to delivery of intermediate bulk containers of Aurin, and in the beginning of the project flow directly between the user of the fertiliser and VN. The aim is to market Aurin at a minimum of €4 per litre.</p> <p>Regarding the sale of the small Aurin bottles, the revenue stream will typically come from intermediaries who purchase the fertiliser to be included in their product range, likely at a purchase price that also ensures they will achieve a margin on the sale. In this context, it will be essential to negotiate fair prices that also ensure VN achieves a profitable margin on the product. This will likely be easier if GE is engaged, with an opportunity to leverage the already established relationship between the two organisations.</p>

Revenue-based royalties as ROI-payments (from VN to KWB / other Aurin treatment system customer)

A unique element of VN's business model is to ensure that their customers benefit from their investments in the Aurin treatment system and the nutrient input they facilitate. Through built in agreements, VN guarantee that their client receives a reward given that sales or revenue per litre of fertiliser reach certain levels. This reward can take the form of either a direct revenue-based royalty or adjustments in maintenance contract fees.

With a direct revenue-based royalty, it means that when reaching a certain number of sales per litre of fertiliser, the customer will receive an agreed percentage of the revenue generated from their urine contribution of the fertiliser sales. Alternatively, the reward will be deducted from the fixed maintenance contract fee paid. The aim is that VN will provide ROI in the scope of 10-15 years.

Payments of royalties or deductions in maintenance fees works under the assumption that VN will be able to generate sufficient levels of revenue from the fertilisers, which is still uncertain. Thus, establishing certain thresholds for when the rewards will be activated, is an important feature to ensure that VN will not be financially burdened if fertiliser sales are pressured.

Even though much of KWB's motivation to participate in the business model is political and ideological, the revenue-based royalties are a critical revenue stream to ensure that their efforts are financially viable.

Additional revenue streams that could enhance the business model include:

Table 22: Additional revenue streams, VN x KWB part of the North German Plain

Additional revenue stream	Description
<p>Integrated utility payments (From public water authorities to KWB/VN)</p>	<p>Another crucial revenue stream for the business model will be payments from public utilities related to the value that is generated from the joint services of KWB and VN. The arguments in the following section will be based on the concept of avoided costs, meaning that the public authorities will benefit financially from the activities of this circular business model that substitute parts of their current treatment processes.</p> <p>For KWB these payments are critical for the services they provide to the county. By investing in the Aurin treatment</p>

system, KWB removes a load of nutrients from the local WWTP, thereby moving a treatment service traditionally performed by public water authorities to KWB. From an economic perspective, this poses as an argument that KWB should be compensated financially. Like other services that KWB provides for the county, they should be paid based on the benefits they generate.

For VN, similar arguments are valid given that their system contributes to reduce the amount of CO₂ emitted from the WWTPs. Additionally, based on similar cases in other countries, discussions are ongoing with the public wastewater agency of Paris, related to the possibility of being compensated for pre-treatment of wastewater based on nitrogen per kg. removed from the system. This illustrates that public entities experience environmental value both related to CO₂ and nitrogen emission reductions from the treatment system and shows that integration to public frameworks is moving in the right direction.

The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) points towards the importance of the right combination of tariffs (revenues from the water bill), taxes (allocations from the public budget), and transfers from the international community to fund water services and infrastructure (Leflaive & Hjort, 2020). In this context, cost recovery through tariffs is highlighted as a best practice to cover costs related to operation and maintenance costs of the service provision. Additionally, the importance of reflecting the cost of pollution in water bills is emphasised as an important means to raise users' awareness about the negative environmental externalities of household wastewater, while it also incentivises water utilities to adopt more environmentally friendly practices (Ibid). Thus, the exact arrangement to finance KWB and VN, and integration to the public utility financing system, will depend on the local public frameworks.

**Pay to dispose fees
(Sanitation service
providers to KWB)**

The last revenue stream of the German business model is pay-to-dispose fees received by KWB when sanitation service providers such as Finizio use their premises to dispose of urine. Currently, these sanitation providers pay disposal fee for the WWTPs when disposing of urine, whereby a similar fee, depending on the amounts of urine, will be an important revenue stream for KWB's short term profitability. Thus, it represents a payment for the disposal,

	and associated value received through the ability to promote their offerings as more sustainable.
Aurin sales as nitrogen input for fertiliser production (fertiliser producers to VN)	Looking ahead, VN sees potential in expanding its customer base to include fertiliser producers, which could contribute to closing the loop in the agricultural value chain. Aurin could be sold as an input for conventional fertiliser production or biochar enrichment, offering additional benefits due to its diverse trace elements. Fertiliser producers requires further testing and product development to become a viable segment.

7.5.2 Financial value creation flows

There are currently no financial value creation flows stemming between the partners in the German pilot. In this system, all partners depend on the successful commercialisation of the fertiliser to generate revenue and create financial value between each other, forming a mutually beneficial cycle. However, the successful commercialisation is currently relying on public authorities legalising selling fertiliser based on urine.

Below are suggestions of how to create internal financial value creation flows between the partners in pilot. Note that in the business model, KWB represents a 'building owner' and is treated as such, as this is the core concept of the model. However, KWB currently operates as a resource recovery site that hosts the technology.

Operationalising financial value creation flows between partners

From VN to KWB / building owners: Return on investment

The installation of the Aurin treatment system at the premise of KWB / building owners is intended to generate financial returns on investment based on Aurin fertiliser sales. While selling the Aurin treatment systems with a margin, the revenue from the fertiliser is then shared with the system's buyer.

With an income generated by VN from selling the fertilisers, it is expected that there will be a 10–15-year ROI when building owners such as KWB invest in the installation of the Aurin treatment system.

From VN to KWB / building owners: Eliminated sewage connection taxes

Based on VN's experiences in the Swiss market, financial value is created for building owners as the installation of the Aurin treatment system circumvent the requirements of paying the sewage tax. On the German market, sewage connection taxes are imburshed in two ways. Firstly, the buyer of a property must pay a connection fee to connect with the already established sewage network. Secondly, fees are imburshed on the users of the sewage system based on the volume discharged into the sewer. This volume is currently measured through freshwater consumption. Thus, when installing the Aurin

treatment system, it eliminates costs in two ways: By avoiding payments of fees for connection to the local sewage network, and by avoiding volumes of wastewater to be discharged to the sewers. The volume of urine not discharged into the sewage network forms a key argument for paying VN for the amount of nitrogen that is not released into the network. However, at present, the system does not measure the volumes of urine discharged, so the actual environmental and financial savings remain unknown.

7.5.3 Cost structure

VN is already well established in Switzerland with a tested financial structure and proven technological capabilities. Therefore, economic data from their existing, fully operational, and scaled-up operations will serve as a reference for the cost structure in the P2Green pilot as an example of VN's system working at capacity.

For the VN x KWB part of the North German Plain, the cost structure is divided into two main categories, capital expenditures (CAPEX) and operating expenses (OPEX). The initial phase when starting out in a new market, in this case Germany, is heavily driven by capital investments necessary to set up the production facility. Major cost items include the processing reactor, distillation and associated technical components, as well as investments in items like intermediate bulk containers. For instance, when referencing a scaled-up operation in Switzerland, CAPEX accounts for approximately 91% % of total expenditures.

Operating expenses cover recurring costs essential for day-to-day operations. These include electricity, depreciation, handling, and maintenance costs. In the Swiss model, OPEX makes up 9 % of total costs. Although smaller than CAPEX, these expenses are crucial as they impact the cost per unit nitrogen. The percentage break down shown in **Table 23** is based on the expenditures associated with operating a scaled-up version in Switzerland by VN.

Table 23: Cost structure of CAPEX and OPEX - VN x KWB part of the North German Plain

CAPEX / OPEX	Estimated amount (EUR)	Percentage of total expenditures (%)
Total CAPEX	280.000	91 %
Total OPEX (yearly)	26.345	9% %

The activity categories under CAPEX and OPEX include the cost items detailed in **Table 24** below. Due to confidentiality, the specific cost elements are not elaborated in monetary amounts.

Table 24: Cost items under CAPEX and OPEX - VN x KWB part of the North German Plain.

Cost category	Key items
Capital expenditures (CAPEX)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Processing reactor • Intermediate bulk containers
Operating expenditures - Fixed (1 year)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depreciation of technology • Electricity • Handling and maintenance • Covering all small components priced below €300, such as activated carbon and other minor materials. It also includes expenses for remote monitoring and occasional on-site interventions, which are expected to occur only twice per year.
Operating expenditures – Variable (1 year)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small components priced below €300, such as activated carbon and other minor materials. • Remote monitoring and occasional on-site interventions, which are expected to occur approx. twice per year. • Transportation costs • Packaging and label costs • Conditioning cost • Distribution/ Marketing

The high initial investment costs, implies that the VN business model relies on economies of scale to reduce the cost per litre of Aurin produced, thereby making the system profitable and competitive with conventional alternatives. The financial data of VN indicates that as the annual volume of collected urine increases and consequently the amount of fertiliser produced rises, the production cost per litre of Aurin and per unit of nitrogen decreases. This cost reduction allows for higher margins and enables the product to be sold at a lower price, making it more accessible to price-sensitive segments such as farmers.

Within the P2Green scope, the fertiliser is expected to be produced at approximately 15 to 20 euros per kilogram of nitrogen, which is roughly 20 times higher than the cost of mineral fertilisers produced via the Haber-Bosch process⁴. However, scaling up production is critical. For example, in VN projects that treat larger volumes - such as a planned operation processing 4 cubic metres of urine per day - production costs fall to around 5 euros per kilogram, making the product competitive with other low-CO₂ alternatives such as, YARA's (Norwegian fertiliser cooperation) fertiliser. The production costs per unit nitrogen is the most important metric to lower to be cost competitive with the production costs pr unit N of the mineral fertilisers.

The short amortisation periods for these systems are a major consideration for the pilot cost structure as they drive overall costs. Unlike the long-established Haber-Bosch plants, which are often amortised over 50 years, the Aurin systems, being housed within a building, must be amortised in 10 to 15 years. This constraint increases the unit cost due to the higher relative capital recovery required within a shorter timeframe.

The distiller, which is currently purchased and accounts for half of the system cost, may in the near term be produced in-house in a location with lower production costs, thereby reducing overall expenses. To achieve a cash flow positive business model, it is necessary to sell at least four Aurin treatment systems per year, as these are expected to become the major revenue driver. Consequently, the focus must remain on driving the sales of these systems.

High electricity and maintenance expenses further contribute to overall costs. Since electricity is a vital input, it imposes a ceiling on how much expenses can be reduced, underscoring the need for efficient capital use in other areas. VN assumes a high energy cost of around 35 cents per kilowatt-hour for their financial plans to prepare for worst-case scenarios. As a new technology, the system suffers from a lack of optimisation compared to the Haber-Bosch process, which has benefited from many years of refinements and effectivisation. This further emphasises the need for supporting these technologies through subsidies for the recovery of nitrogen in these systems, and to be able to scale it to a level where it is competitive with the mineral fertilisers such as a Haber-bosh based fertiliser.

7.6 Conclusion

The part of Metropolitan Region of North German Plain focusing on the recycling of urine presents a business model transforming urine into the biobased fertiliser Aurin addressing nutrient losses, and water scarcity in the region.

As a technology provider, VN's value propositions targets actors in different directions of the circular value chain, from building owners as a source of necessary input for fertiliser production, to fertiliser users seeking an environmentally friendly alternative to

⁴ The Haber-Bosch process is the leading technique for synthesising ammonia by combining nitrogen and hydrogen primarily used in fertiliser production (Mohamed & Bicer,2022)

their current farming or gardening practices. The business model not only closes nutrient cycles for nitrogen but also tackles environmental challenges by eliminating the energy intensive process of conventional nitrogen-based fertiliser production and conserving water through source separating toilets.

VN's model is built around a decentralised urine treatment system which is intended to be installed in various public or private buildings. The collaboration that forms the business model ensures collection of urine which not only eliminates the cost of waste disposal for sanitation service providers but also reinforces local circularity by converting waste into a biobased fertiliser. The produced liquid fertiliser will be marketed under the Aurin brand is positioned to appeal to customers who value sustainability and locally sourced products, including both farmers and hobby gardeners.

The business model involves partnerships across the entire circular value chain that utilises existing collaboration between the local waste management organisation KWB and sanitation service providers and public authorities, while at the same time creating new partnerships with the technology provider, VN. A key aspect of the circular business model approach is ensuring an effective profit-sharing arrangement between KWB and VN, both of which are crucial actors in the value chain - an area where circular business models are often rejected (Lewandowski, 2016). In this regard, VN's built-in mechanism that ensures ROI for the involved building owner serves as an excellent example of how to benefit stakeholders contributing urine, rather than focusing solely on self-profit. Furthermore, revenue is expected to be generated from various sources related to technology and fertiliser sales, as well as from disposal fees, and integrated utility payments based on the value created for public authorities in Barnim.

Strengths

Market conditions present both challenges and opportunities for this particular circular business model. Spikes in fertiliser prices, exacerbated by geopolitical instability have highlighted the need for alternative fertiliser sources to secure food resilience. This external pressure is likely to drive more political and industry attention for local solutions. Additionally, major retailers have expressed interest in low-carbon fertilisers to help reduce their supply chain emissions. If retailers utilise their purchasing power to encourage suppliers to adopt sustainable fertilisers, market demand for biobased could see a boost.

A strength in the business model further lies in the network of partnerships that underpins the model. Being a part of the North German Plain entails that collaboration between partners VN, KWB, GE, and VH ensures both important knowledge sharing, supply of raw toilet matter, access to production facilities, established distribution channels, and re-collection of nutrients, thus representing all vital parts of a successful circular value chain. By planning to generate revenue from the Aurin treatment system from different sources, including building-owners or waste management sites, along

with revenue generated from both B2B, B2G and B2C sales, the business model spread risk across multiple customer segments, rather than relying on one source of cash-flow.

A key advantage lies in the decentralised nature of the Aurin treatment solution with the potential to be installed in strategic locations such as counties, urban hubs, airports, stadiums, construction sites, etc. Such integration not only enhances the efficiency of nutrient recycling but also integrate the solution into local infrastructure, making it a standard component of modern urban planning. Specifically for the county of Barnim, the large proportion of non-sewered households creates an opportunity for VN to become a crucial part of the area's waste management system, positioning KWB as a key player in the market for human excreta management. Introduction of fees for unsegregated waste or price subsidies for UDTs have been imposed in other cases to incentivise adoption of waste stream segregation at households (Rao et al. 2016), an approach which could help increase the volumes of urine to be collected in the county.

VN is currently exploring the establishment of a cooperative for fertiliser producers, based on a model of solidarity whereby larger producers support smaller ones. This arrangement would enhance the scalability of the fertiliser market, enable producers to pool production for large orders, and transfer operational risk from VN to the cooperative. In return, VN would receive a percentage of sales as royalties or through a similar revenue-sharing mechanism.

In terms of financing VN and KWB, may leverage EU and German funding opportunities to support their growth and research. This is elaborated in the joint pilot section: Funding requirements for the North German Plain .

Challenges

One of the greatest challenges facing this business model is the legal status of the fertiliser. In Germany, fertilisers derived from urine and faeces is not yet approved for commercial sale, limiting the possibility to establish a viable business case. Currently, use is only permitted in controlled agricultural trials, meaning regulatory approval will be essential for marketing and scaling up production. The innovation therefore requires obtaining a regulatory allowance, a process that is complicated by lobby work favouring conventional, water-based processes. Different legal levels (European, German federal, and State Regulations) add layers of complexity, often hinging on individual decision-makers who may resist change. In this relation, a unified framework that expressively state when and how this type of fertiliser is allowed pose as a vital push-factor of bio-based fertilisers.

Another key challenge is the absence of an existing system to build upon. The company must be active at all levels: 1. developing collection systems and stabilising the urine, 2. producing a urine concentrate, and 3. producing fertiliser from the concentrate. All processes are costly and consume energy, which affects the price of the final product and reduces the competitiveness against mineral fertilisers. While the main value lies in pollution prevention, engagement at all levels is required, from consumers to

wastewater utilities, which makes the financial viability of the business model challenging. Understanding what motivates building owners to invest in these systems and effectively communicating the financial and environmental benefits will be crucial. Similarly, validation tests among farmers, municipalities, and hobby gardeners would enhance the understanding of their needs and preferences to improve the Aurin offering regarding its nutrient values and best-practice use. Moreover, by involving the public authorities as a complementary customer that pays for the services of micro pollutant, nitrogen and phosphorous removal, it will allow VN finance treatment systems themselves and increase the likelihood of adoption among customers to become an integrated part when new buildings are constructed, and new urban neighbourhoods are developed.

Furthermore, difficulties are faced when aiming to convince farmers of the value created by the liquid urine-based fertiliser, particularly in terms of price and scale. The limited and variable production capacity of bio-based fertiliser currently makes it unappealing for both larger individual farmers, and large farming cooperatives, which require significantly higher volumes. Without increasing the output of fertilisers, it will therefore be difficult to attract large buyers and integrate the bio-based fertiliser into existing agricultural supply chains. To make Aurin even more appealing once legislation and volume of production permits is to create opportunities for Aurin to be used as input in conventional fertiliser production.

An additional challenge lies in demonstrating that large-scale urine collection systems can be commercially viable. While there is strong interest and optimism in the concept, potential partners remain sceptical about whether all collected urine can be successfully processed and sold. Proving that the market demand exists on a scale is essential to securing investments in larger installations and moving from pilot projects to a successful adoption.

Currently energy and maintenance costs are high as the technology is still new and small-scale. Over time, with more experience and optimisation, these costs are expected to drop, making the product more competitive with mineral fertilisers.

At the same time, recognising and internalising the environmental and social costs associated with conventional fertilisers, such as nutrient runoff, water contamination, and greenhouse gas emissions, can shift the economic balance. These external costs are often excluded from market prices but are nonetheless real burdens on society. By accounting for these externalities, the solutions proposed in the pilot region may emerge as competitive alternatives.

Finally, the business model must overcome the typical hurdles of new product adoption. Initial enthusiasm and novelty factor may help attract early interest, but the next step requires transitioning from niche appeal to mainstream agricultural acceptance. This means demonstrating long-term value for the customers, securing regulatory approval, and ensuring stable supply and demand to make the Aurin bio-based fertiliser a

competitive alternative to conventional nitrogen-based fertilisers. These challenges emphasises that the business model is to overcome regulatory, economic, and infrastructural hurdles for a broader market adoption and scaling of the technology, allowing for the establishment of a successful business model.

8 Circular Business Model: Goldeimer

8.1 Introduction

This business model transforms faeces into compost. By collecting and treating dry toilet contents, mainly from festivals and public urban toilets, a humus-rich compost fertiliser is produced by mixing it with green waste, bentonite, and biochar during composting. GE contributes to the project with a thermophilic container-based composting plant for faeces, which is set up at Vagtshoffs farm (VH) (TRL 7 as of 2025). VH provides industrial waste heat and biochar for the treatment process, as well as agricultural fields for fertiliser application (Beneker et al., 2023).

The business model is characterised by having operational control over the entire value chain offering value propositions tailored to different customer segments across the value chain. A unique feature of the business model is the combination of two parts of the GE corporation. Goldeimer Services GmbH represents the commercial part of the business model responsible for sales of e.g., own-branded toilet paper, litter, portable toilets, etc. Oppositely, Goldeimer Gemeinnützige GmbH represents the activities related to collection of faeces at festivals and operation of its own compost facility. The architecture of these two parts is that the profits from Goldeimer Services GmbH are transferred to Goldeimer Gemeinnützige GbmH as donations, thereby supporting the start-up phase of the composting business model.

Although GE's business model outside P2Green is already developed, the production of compost fertiliser is still in its research phase, solely being tested in P2Green field trials. Current regulations⁵ do not allow commercialisation of faecal compost, and even though the technology is ready, and the operational scale is sufficient (Beneker et al., 2023), the compost cannot be sold until legal conditions change. Although GE expects that regulatory adjustments will eventually enable market entry, it is not possible at the current moment to scale the envisioned business model.

Figure 5 illustrates the process where compost derived from faeces close the loop from fork to farm.

⁵ Legal barriers include municipal statutes based on the Water Household Act (WHG §55/56), the Circular Economy Act (BioAbfV§3) and lastly the FertiliserAct (DüMV Annex II, Table 7). Counteracting the principle of the waste hierarchy: Prevent, Reuse, Recycle, Recover, Dispose of the federal Circular Economy Act (KrWG § 6(1)). (Beneker et al., 2023)

Figure 5: Circular supply chain for the GE part of the North German Plain

The following section outlines the key assumptions and decisions made during the development of the business model. It then presents the CBMC through its core building blocks: *value proposition*, *value creation* and *delivery*, and *value capture*. Additionally, the organisational, financial, and environmental value creation flows are explored and integrated throughout the business model. The CBMC describes how the business model is expected to function if the legal barrier was removed. The full circular business model canvas is illustrated in Appendix III: Circular Business Model Canvas: Goldeimer.

8.2 Assumptions and decisions

- The business model is made with its main focus on GE, as GE is the provider of the compost and GE is critical to the success of the circular business model.
- Although the original business model aimed to deliver the Aurin treatment system to building owners, this arrangement has not been realised through P2Green. Since this deliverable evaluates the business model in the pilot region and KWB, a resource recovery organisation, is a pilot partner, the current model is unique to the P2Green project rather than the intended scalable solution. In the business model described in this report, KWB is representing a building owner, filling the role originally assigned to EVH. In practice, KWB operates as a resource recovery site and serves as a platform connecting the local sanitation service provider Finizio with the Aurin treatment system provided by VN to produce the fertiliser for field trials at

VH. KWB adds distinct value to the project through its connections with both Finizio and Barnim County.

- The bio-based fertiliser is currently hindered by legislation in Germany that prevents the commercialisation of fertilisers derived from urine or faeces. As a result, a fully implemented business model is not yet possible. The CBMC therefore illustrates the envisioned business model showing how technology and partnerships may evolve if the legal barrier was removed.
- Due to the maturity of the fertiliser, and this not being on the market yet, some of the areas in the business model are based on assumptions made by the pilot partners. Moreover, some information is confidential or sensitive and are therefore not described in full in the business model's cost structure. Because of this, costs and revenues are based on both actual and estimated costs drafted from the data input provided by the technology provider VN which have been assessed and presented as percentages.
- Throughout the business model, when environmental claims are made these may not be used for communication purposes unless these are documented, for example through a life-cycle analysis or similar documentation. Focus of this deliverable is the business models of the pilots, whereas work package 2 (D2.3) documents the environmental impact of the pilot regions.

8.3 Value proposition

The value proposition consists of five value propositions that serve different customer segments.

Table 25: Value proposition - GE part of the North German Plain

	Value proposition	Value created for customer segment
Upstream	Sanitation services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides festivals with a complete sanitary solution, including toilets, toilet paper, and excreta recycling. • Enhances the festival experience by adding a unique and engaging toilet experience which raises awareness about nutrient scarcity • Offers a sustainable, waterless, and chemical-free solution, producing only nutrient-rich compost.

<p>Upstream</p>	<p>Fun and educational toilet experiences</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creates ‘sanitation camps’ with music, games, books, and interactive learning. • Clean and well-maintained dry toilets that enhance festivalgoers' toilet experience. • Provides an engaging and educational experience on global sanitation. • Offers a high-service alternative to free chemical toilets through a pay-per-use model. • Enhances the festival experience by adding a unique and engaging entertainment option.
<p>Production</p>	<p>Excreta treatment service</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accepts dry toilet waste from external sanitation providers for composting. • Provides a branding opportunity for providers contributing to the project. • Offers a meaningful and cost-effective alternative to standard waste disposal
<p>Downstream</p>	<p>High-end compost (KIT)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides high-quality, locally produced faecal compost that enriches soil and boosts plant growth. • Exceeds average compost nutrient levels, offering phosphorus, potassium, and nitrogen as an NPK alternative. • Acts as both a fertiliser and soil improver, supporting organic farming and enhancing soil resilience. • Closes the nutrient loop, promoting a sustainable, circular composting solution for responsible waste management.
<p>Upstream, Production and Downstream</p>	<p>Consultancy services</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specialised consulting services on producing high-quality compost from dry toilet waste for portable toilet companies, municipalities, and farmers. • Experts to support implementation of dry toilets across Germany. • Expertise on planning and operating the recycling process, from waste collection to compost production.

Sanitation services, upstream

The sanitation camps provide complete sanitary services that represents a value proposition not only for festival- and events attendees, but also for the festival. With over 20 toilet cabins, festivals are offered a complete and high-quality sanitary solution from toilets and toilet paper to excreta recycling once the event concludes. Furthermore, the sanitation camp represents an additional entertainment option to the portfolio of activities happening at a festival. This creates more entertainment for the festival attendees without the monetary burdens of paying for more artists.

The value proposition stands out with two unique selling points, differentiating them from competitors in the market. First, the unique and entertaining toilet experience, offering insights and information about the broader issue of nutrient scarcity, contributes with entertainment as well as image of the festival. Second, GE's solution is waterless and chemical-free, with the only by-product being nutritious compost, making it an environmentally friendly alternative to conventional toilets.

Fun and educational toilet experiences, upstream

The first value proposition is targeted towards attendees at festivals and other public events. The value proposition is to make a trip to the loo enjoyable while both educating about the wasted valuable resources in current sanitation schemes and the global sanitation crisis - allowing the users to contributing to a circular economy. Since 2013, GE has established 'sanitation camps' consisting of 80 mobile dry toilets, primarily in the sleeping areas of music festivals. Each toilet block features music, and the sanitation camps offer games, books, and information on global sanitation and nutrient challenges through interactions with GE-hired personnel with opening hours from 07:00-23:00.

The toilets follow a pay-per-use model (elaborated under revenue streams), meaning that it competes with free toilets at the festivals, which is often provided in larger numbers.

Excreta treatment service, production

The third value proposition is developed to create value for sanitation service providers following collection of faeces in festivals or public toilets. In this phase, they need to dispose of the collected excreta, and GE offer a solution that is more environmentally friendly than the alternative disposal in wastewater treatment plants. GE provides the service of faeces disposal, where the received toilet contents from external sanitation providers is used as input in GE's compost facility. Value is created for dry toilet content providers by offering them a convenient disposal option, and branding opportunity through their contribution to recycling of nutrients from human excreta. Since they already need to dispose of their dry toilet waste at a cost, participating in the project provides a more meaningful and potentially beneficially alternative.

High-end compost product (KIT), production

GE produces a high-quality, locally produced faecal compost called KIT (Kompost aus Inhalten von Trockentoiletten) that enriches soil and enhances plant growth. The unique value proposition lies in its role of closing the nutrient loop, offering gardeners a sustainable, circular compost solution for environmental stewardship, and the self-expressive benefits from a pioneering image. Though, with KIT currently restricted from commercial sale, it is being tested in the P2Green field trial and will be marketed to hobby gardeners once legislation allows.

Designed to exceed average compost nutrient levels, it provides sufficient phosphorus and potassium to qualify as a fertiliser, sometimes containing nitrogen, making it an NPK fertilising alternative. Beyond fertilisation, it functions as a soil improver, supporting organic farming practices by enhancing soil structure and long-term resilience.

Consultancy services, upstream/production and downstream

The fifth and final value proposition is built around consulting services to advise other sanitation service providers, municipalities and farmers on the activities covering every step of the recycling process from implementing dry-toilet waste to quality tested compost. This includes advise on how to operate a composting system, plan and receive the right permissions, produce high quality compost from dry toilet waste, and quality testing of the treatment facility, and products. Additional services involve advising clients on local sourcing opportunities for raw dry toilet material, as GE possesses a variety of relevant contacts in this area. The aim of the value proposition is to help companies, municipalities, and farmers set up their own systems and make dry toilets more widespread across Germany.

The consulting services are designed to create value for sanitation service providers by offering autarky in disposal of toilet waste, since they will own their own treatment facility, and not be dependent on WWTPs to accept their collected faeces. Additionally, owning an in-house composting facility will create self-expressive benefits of an improved environmentally friendly image.

Farmers and municipalities will benefit from increased resilience of a local supply of fertiliser. As the compost flows that will be produced by GE's own composting facility likely are too small for the larger farmer markets, an in-house composting facility will help farmers supplement their fertilising use. A prerequisite of this offering is GE's ability to facilitate contact with other sources of faeces due to the limited amounts of GE's own toilet fleet. Furthermore, GE provides a service of marketing professionally packaged compost via their web shop, meaning that instead of applying it to their fields, farmers are offered to sell their produced KIT, thus providing an additional source of income.

This value proposition will be provided once the regulation allows the marketing of faeces compost.

8.3.1 Customer segments

The business model offers five value propositions which provide value for different customer segments, as described in the **Table 26** below.

Table 26: Customer segments, GE part of the North German Plain

Customer segment	
Sanitation services catering to festivals and other event organisers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Festivals, or other event organisers who value superior, informative and entertaining sanitation options. • Need to provide clean, high-quality sanitation facilities for attendees. • Seek to improve the festival's environmental and social image, making it more attractive and sustainable. • Require reliable, well-established sanitation solutions to complement existing infrastructure. • Demonstrated strong demand, with 125 festivals served since 2013 and over 1.4 million users.
Fun and educational toilet experience catering to festival goers using the sanitation camps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attendees at music festivals and public events who value cleanliness, comfort, entertainment, and sustainability. • Need access to high-quality, hygienic sanitation facilities. • Seek a more enjoyable and engaging toilet experience compared to standard festival options. • Willing to pay a premium (€2 per use or €20–€25 per day) for better service. • Interested in supporting sustainable solutions and contributing to the circular economy.
Excreta treatment service catering to sanitation service providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dry sanitation providers interested in supporting the environmental sanitation agenda • Needs disposal of the sanitation waste from the festivals and events they service
High-end compost product (KIT) catering to hobby gardeners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hobby gardeners who value premium-quality, nutrient-rich compost with environmental benefits. • Include urban gardeners, balcony owners, and sustainability enthusiasts. • Need to fertilise their plants or crops to maintain a healthy garden or balcony environment.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seek effective, eco-friendly soil enhancers to improve plant growth, especially relevant in regions with degrading soil quality. • Interested in supporting the circular economy through sustainable gardening to obtain a self-expressive pioneering image.
<p>Compost product (KIT) catering to organic or environmentally conscious farmers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers who value organic or environmentally friendly source of nutrients and compost. • Depend on future legislation, scales, and potential inclusion into regulations.
<p>Consultancy services catering to farmers, municipalities, and other dry toilet providers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sanitation service providers, farmers, and municipalities, who value advise on all stages from dry-toilet waste to quality tested compost. • Need support with technical components, planning, permission processes, operations, and quality-testing. • Seeking expert guidance on composting activities. • Sanitation service providers looking to reduce reliance on traditional treatment systems and adopt greener practices. • Farmers interested in setting up on-site composting facilities for supplementary fertiliser production and create additional sources of future income. • Municipalities aiming to implement CE initiatives through improved sanitation solutions and create a local source of fertiliser.

Fun and educational toilet experience catering to festival attendees using the sanitation camps

GE addresses the needs of festival attendees who are willing to pay a premium for high-quality sanitation facilities at festivals. This segment has been validated by their current operations, where customers pay approximately €2 per use of our dry toilets or a daily flat rate of €20–€25 at German festivals. Beyond the convenience of clean, well-maintained toilets, festival attendees enjoy an entertaining experience that transforms a routine activity into an engaging event, all while contributing to the circular economy.

The sanitation services catering to festival organisers

With GE sanitation camps, organisers can provide a superior experience to their guests that includes not only clean and well services facilities but also additional entertainment

and information. The improved service contributes to an enhanced environmental and social image for the event, making it more attractive and sustainable. This customer segment has proven to validate the value of the offering, as the demand from organisers is high. Throughout the years, the customer segment of festivals has matured to embrace sustainable solutions, meaning that dry-toilets and the associated services have are sought after with a good reputation. GE's upstream sanitation services are already well-established and successfully running in the market as they have served 125 festivals since 2013 having over 1.4 million users of their sanitation services (Goldeimer, nd.).

Excreta treatment service catering to sanitation service providers

An additional customer segment includes dry toilet sanitation providers, similar to Goldeimer, that serve festivals and events and incur costs for the disposal of their toilet matter. This customer segment can benefit from the GE solution that offer both a disposal option and opportunity to enhance their brand by contributing to the reuse of the faecal matter through GE.

Compost product (KIT) catering to hobby gardeners and farmers

Hobby gardeners (B2C)

A key customer segment for GE is hobby gardeners, who value premium quality and environmental benefits of the nutrient rich compost. Target segments in areas with poor and degrading soil quality is highly relevant through KIT's ability to improve the chemical properties of the soil. Due to limited production capacity, GE has shifted focus from the larger farmer segment to hobby gardeners. Marketed via the GE web shop, the compost appeals particularly to urban gardeners, balcony owners, and those interested in sustainable farming practices in general. Hobby gardeners benefit from improved plant growth, a pioneering image by contributing to a circular economy.

Farmers (B2B)

A potential customer segment of KIT is organic or environmentally conscious farmers, who currently experience a lack of nutrient alternatives. However, this customer segment rely on GE's ability to increase the scales of the compost production, and for KIT to be included in the Organic Farmers regulations.

Consultancy services catering to sanitation service providers, farmers, and municipalities

The consultancy services cater to farmers, municipalities, and sanitation providers. These groups are expected to seek expert guidance on technical components, planning, permission processes, and the operation of converting dry toilet waste into quality compost. Portable toilet companies, for instance, can gain independence from

traditional treatment systems of WWTPs and adopt greener practices to benefit the image of their company.

Farmers are characterised by a high degree of price-sensitivity which induces their fertiliser buying behaviour to be focused on the cost-effectiveness of the offering. Thus, due to the limited scales of GE's operations the opportunity to target large farmer markets are limited. Instead, GE targets farmers interested in establishing on-site compost facilities, to create a locally sourced side-stream of nutrients that can supplement their fertilising needs. Alternatively, their investments in an in-house treatment facility can be used to create additional income streams of selling the fertilisers. Similarly, municipalities benefit from an in-house owned compost facility which align with CE initiatives while supporting local collectors of faeces by providing them a convenient and sustainable disposal option. Production and application of KIT is especially relevant for farmers and municipalities in regions with degrading soil quality, to enhance the chemical properties of the soil.

8.3.2 Customer relationships

This section explores the customer relationship of GE and how they interact and maintain the relationship with its various customer segments.

Sanitation service – co-creation relationship

The sanitation camp and subsequent handling of human excreta is managed through a two-fold relationship with festivals. Usually, sanitation service providers must order fences, electricity, fresh water, etc. for their allocated areas directly from festival organisers at relatively high costs. However, the relationships between GE and festivals build on a mutual agreement that both parties co-create value for each-other meaning that GE is provided with materials (including festival tickets) for free, which also means that GE do not charge festivals directly (further elaborated under revenue streams).

Fun and educational toilet experience – personal assistance relationship

The relationship between festival attendees and GE is characterised by a personal assistance approach. The key to retaining their customers, making them pay another visit, lies in delivering a high-quality, clean and unique sanitation experience, driven by exceptional service. Visiting the sanitation camps should feel like a pleasant, entertaining and engaging experience, where the staff ensures that the facilities are well-maintained and enjoyable to use.

Key for these customer relationships are the front-office personnel who are hired on a volunteer basis, and compensated through festival tickets, food, and backstage crew accommodation. Thus, training and educating these individuals on communication of sanitation issues, and customer engagement is crucial to secure a consistent experience when interacting with the GE brand. Beyond GE's non-profit vision and storytelling, this customer segment value clean, functional, and odour-free toilets. Their

willingness to pay for each use of the sanitation camps depend on the perceived quality of the experience. Therefore, the on-site personnel play a vital role in maintaining a positive sanitation experience is crucial as pay-per-use fees currently represent GE's most significant revenue stream.

Additionally, QR codes for compost discounts will be available for festival attendees who contribute to the project by using the sanitation camp. This initiative not only attracts new customers for the compost but also strengthens engagement with existing users of the sanitation camp by enabling them to purchase the final product of the closed nutrient loop.

Excreta treatment service – automated relationship

The excreta treatment service is based on a personal assistance relationship; however, interactions between GE and the sanitation provider are expected to be minimal, focusing primarily on the delivery of the dry toilet matter.

High-end compost product (KIT) - mix between personal assistance and automated services

As the compost is not marketed yet due to the legislative limitations, this customer relationship is envisioned. The relationship between hobby gardeners and GE will be characterised as a mix between personal assistance and automated services. Since hobby garden customers might also use GE's sanitation camps at festivals, they can communicate with GE representatives about the product and the purchasing process. However, when entering the purchase stage, customers will be enabled to manage and order the compost product by themselves, through GE's online webshop where the QR-codes received at the sanitation camps help entering the purchase channel. Throughout the process, hobby gardeners are provided with the possibility to receive personal assistance through GE's online customer services for a seamless experience. Additionally, obtaining certifications that verify the safety of the compost will be important in building customer trust, and drive demand for the compost product.

While the limited scale of production means that GE is not able to meet farmer demands, it is anticipated that relationships with individual farmers will be established. These relationships will be driven more by symbolic value than actual customer retention, primarily through the provision of compost for application in the fields to close the loop from fork to farm and support the narrative of the business model.

Consultancy service relationships – dedicated personal assistance relationship

The consulting service will build on dedicated personal relationships between GE and the sanitation service providers, farmers or municipalities. Each customer will have unique needs and belong to a specific local context requiring GE to dedicate a customer representative to develop an understanding of their requirements. When establishing a compost recycling facility, it requires coordination of contact with the local municipality,

authorities, construction companies, etc. to obtain building permissions, and construct the actual facility. GE helps customers navigate in these areas through a close relationship anticipated to form over a longer period.

8.4 Value creation and delivery

8.4.1 Key activities

Once it becomes legal to commercialise faecal compost, the value chain ranges from providing sanitation and collecting faeces to nutrient recycling processes and consulting services. Therefore, the key activities of the German pilot are categorised into upstream, production, and downstream activities.

Upstream

The key upstream activities of GE's business model relate to the tasks around festival services. GE currently operates at around 10–15 festivals per year, where they are given 1–4 toilet blocks, each with 12 dry-toilets. These dry toilets have been assembled by technical staff at GE's headquarters, from where they are stored until needed at an event.

A prerequisite of GE's festival activities is training and education of volunteers to enable these to set up the sanitation camps and run *edutainment* sessions about sanitation and nutrient challenges. Following setup, GE collects and stores the dry matter from the toilets in bins used for solid waste logistics. Once the festival concludes, the collected waste is transported via third-party transportation providers to the GE treatment facility, where it will be unloaded and turned into nutrient rich compost in the production stage.

Furthermore, to support the consulting services, GE must also educate and train employees on technical aspects, planning, regulatory approval processes, and overall operation of the compost system.

While not directly related to the festival operations, it must be noted that due to the balanced structure of GE's non-profit, and for-profit operations, key upstream activities also involve procurement of materials such as bathroom supplies, dry-toilets and other GE-branded articles. Hence, well-managed procurement allows GE to derive profits from their e-commerce activities in the downstream stage, to support their non-profit part of the business.

Production

The key activities related to production mainly involves management of inbound logistics of faeces and the operation of the compost recycling facility. Since 2015, GE has run a material and logistics hub at VH in Hanstedt which is also used for the P2Green field trials. The farm provides space for their composting plant, which have now been approved by local authorities.

The process of turning the excreta into compost is initiated when human excreta from festivals enters the recycling facility. Once it arrives, the bins are unloaded and fed into the first stage of the treatment system, which overall involves three key steps, with the first two being container-based.

1. **Sanitisation treatment:** The dry toilet content goes through thermophilic composting, to eliminate pathogens.
2. **Decomposition & recomposition:** The organic matter is broken down in an oxygen-controlled composting system (*Earthflow*), which is an automated process that replaces the previous more labour-intensive heap composting method.
3. **Extraneous material extraction:** This final step removes unwanted materials (Beneker et al., 2023).

GE has invested in the machinery and technology supporting these key processes which are provided by Compost Systems. The resulting product is a nutrient rich faecal compost product referred to as KIT.

A parallel key activity includes consulting customers in turning dry-toilet matter into nutrient rich compost through in-house operation of a compost facility. These activities are highly dependent on the specific needs of the customer and varies from client to client.

Downstream

The downstream activities cover the handling of KIT following production. The KIT is currently applied directly in field trials at VH to grow rye and barley crops and supporting further research while awaiting regulatory approval for commercial marketing. These trials represent crucial knowledge obtained as R&D. Once regulation approves, the compost will be transported to a third-party packaging facility, where it will be properly packaged and labelled. From there, it will be marketed and sold through GE's existing online shop. With an established online sales platform and marketing expertise, GE will sell compost products directly to consumers. A few shipments will be sent to farmers to support the narrative of the business model.

Another crucial aspect of GE's downstream activities is maintenance of their own compost facility, and the continuous customer-support of their consulting services.

Table 27: Key activities, GE part of the North German Plain

Key activities	Description of key activities
Key upstream activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Education of employees on sanitation crisis, transition topics and consulting services (GE) 2. Dry-toilet and sanitation camp set up at festivals (GE) 3. Info- and edutainment at Sanitation Camps (GE) 4. Collection of faeces in dry toilets (GE) 5. Transportation of collected faeces to compost facility (third party transportation provider)
Key production activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. Unloading trucks and bins with collected faeces at VH (third party transportation provider) 7. Operation of compost facility GE) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Processing. Sanitisation of dry toilet contents by thermophilic composting b) Processing: Earthflow – highly automated and oxygen-controlled faeces composting c) Screening of KIT compost-product 8. Consulting of clients (GE)
Key post-production activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 9. Shipment to third party packaging facility (GE) 10. Packaging and labelling (external partner) 11. Webshop operation, sales and marketing (GE) 12. Shipment from packaging facility to customers (external partner) 13. Maintenance of compost facility (GE) 14. Consultancy services (GE)

8.4.2 Key resources

The key resources are listed in **Table 28**.

Table 28: Key resources, GE part of the North German Plain

Key resources	Description of resources	Status
Physical resources	Composting plant	Available through GE,

	Dry toilet fleet (currently 72, expanding to 100 toilets)	VH and Compost Systems
	Compost spreading machines	Missing but initiated by GE. Potentially available through agricultural cooperative
Human resources	Educated and engaging festival-volunteers.	Available through GE
	Back-end employees (building toilets and running logistics)	Available through GE
	Sales force, marketing and advisory team	Available through GE
Intellectual resources	Research and field results	Available VH and GE
	Know-how and experience	Available through GE
Financial resources	P2GreeN funding	Available but with a time limit
	Revenue from Goldeimer Services GmbH to Goldeimer Gemeinnützige GmbH's composting facility	Available through GE
	Equity	Available through GE

Physical resources

One key physical resource is GE's dry-toilet fleet consisting of 72 dry-toilets, currently planned to be expanded to 100 units. The dry-toilets are essential to ensure a steady flow of input for composting.

Another essential physical resource is the composting plant which is now approved for operation by the municipality. The plant includes the *Earthflow* container, an automatic composting system able to be customised with different user-needs, provided by the partnering company, Compost Systems. The maximum capacity of the composting plant is up to 300 tonnes per year. Currently, the input received from festivals and other providers can, in best case, provide a maximum input of 40 % of the total plant capacity. Thus, there is existing potential to increase the scales of compost production.

Human resources

The success of GE's business model requires human resources at different stages. The key human resources are divided into volunteers and employees (paid staff). First, volunteer seasonal workers are a prerequisite to operate GE's sanitation camps at events and festivals. At larger events like the Hurricane Festival, a crew of about 50 individuals are responsible for operating the toilets, engaging with festival attendees through edutainment, and ensuring the functioning of the service. Second, paid workers handle the construction, logistics, and maintenance of the toilet fleet. Aside from GE's festival operations, educated and trained consultants are crucial to advise customers on the nutrient recycling process.

Intellectual resources

GE has extensive knowledge of the operational aspects of faeces composting. This includes expertise in system setup, permit applications, and the technical operations, which will be utilised in their consultancy services.

Regarding intellectual property, GE does not intend to pursue patents or protect its innovations, as this is not aligned with its mission. Instead, GE is committed to share its knowledge to drive the sanitary transformation, preferably at a global level. This includes enabling other festival and sanitation providers to transition from chemical toilets to dry toilets and establish their own treatment facility or support non-commercial festivals to operate their own dry-toilets.

Further key resources are GE's well-known brand, an already established webshop, and marketing experience.

GE further benefits from partnerships with a local agricultural cooperative, allowing access to a precision compost spreader which is important for applying the compost effectively in farming settings.

Financial resources

The financial resources for Goldeimer Gemeinnützige GmbH is covered by public funding related to P2Green, the revenue transfer from Goldeimer Services GmbH and from equity. The funding from EU project grants support research and development efforts, reinforcing GE's capacity to scale and innovate.

8.4.3 Key partners

The key partners in the GE part of the North German Plain region are:

Goldeimer (GmbH) is a German social non-profit company founded in 2014 in Hamburg. GE provides dry toilets for festivals and events as well as toilet-related products that support the transition towards sustainable sanitation through their web shop. Their product range includes disposable toilets, toilet paper, and soap, alongside workshops on sanitation and hygiene.

GE is omitted to supporting and driving an industry wide adoption of circular sanitation solutions and is actively engaged in addressing sanitation challenges in the Global South. In GE, all actions must feed into the topics of the global sanitation crisis where German citizens are urged to donate money for better sanitation in exposed areas and sanitary transition. This dual focus on social impact and environmental sustainability supports their mission as a purpose-driven organisation. In GE, success is not measured in monetary terms, but by the ability to foster widespread implementation of sustainable sanitation practices.

In P2Green, GE is overseeing the entire value chain from the collection of excreta at festivals to the marketing of end products once legislation permits. As the sole key stakeholder and coordinator, GE plays a crucial role in managing various aspects of value chain providing education, faeces collection, centralised compost production, and marketing through GE's web shop.

Vagtshoff Farm (VH) in lower saxony near Hamburg serves as the provider of land for the P2Green field trials, industrial waste heat and biochar for the treatment facility, and act as the landlord for the compost facility. While VH provides the land on which the infrastructure is built, GE covers the construction costs. VH supports the R&D activities of the business model with agricultural equipment to harvest of the crops during field trials. Initially, VH represented a typical farmer purchasing fertiliser in the business model. However, due to insufficient quantities for the farmer segment, and the shifted focus to the Business to Consumer (B2C) market, VH now plays a more research-oriented role, serving as a field trial site for the nutrient rich compost.

Table 29 provides a list of key suppliers, distributors, and other key stakeholders for the GE pilot:

Table 29: Key partners, GE part of the North German Plain

Resources provided or activity performed	
Key suppliers	<p>Festival/event organisers and sanitation service providers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • These actors facilitate the collection of dry toilet matter to supply the compost production.
	<p>Supplier of dry toilet components for the festival setup</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GE provides all materials needed; however, straw is provided by GE's supplier
	<p>Supplier of input material for treatment facility</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suppliers will provide non-toilet biomass and clay-rich soil for production of KIT.
	<p>Compost Systems</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Compost Systems will supply the main components of the treatment technology. This further includes straw, bin lifting device, bin washing facility, wheel loader, and smaller technological equipment for the compost system. <p>Suppliers for the online shop</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• WEPA (toilet paper)• The GE toilet paper is produced by WEPA who also undertakes sales activities in their B2B sales network to food retailers and drugstores. GE receives a license fee each year for the packaging to be customised to GE's brand• Werkhaus provides allotment garden and tourism toilets for GEs web shop sales• Stückerjürgen provides plastic parts for GE toilets• EGOS provides toilet litter, also part of GE's online offerings.
<p>Key distributors</p>	<p>Third-party transportation providers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Third-party transportation providers will distribute faeces input from festivals to compost facility <p>Fulfilment centre</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• The handling of the purchasing processes related to shipping of the KIT and other GE products to B2C customers happens via a fulfilment centre. When a customer of KIT places an order, the fulfilment centre handles picking up, packaging, and shipment of the products. The shipping itself is managed by DHL go Green. The packaging costs are currently estimated at a price of €2 per 20 l bag.
<p>Other key partners</p>	<p>Key authorities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Authorities within environment, buildings, water and other areas are involved in the process of gaining permission to operate a composting plant. Thus, effective partnerships with these actors are essential for GE's own composting plant, and for their consulting services. <p>Machinenring</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Machinenring is a farmer's corporation and advisory. They are an important partner for GE due to their extensive expertise and knowhow on farming and the agricultural sector in the region e.g. in relation to nutrient needs in the region. Machinenring might also provide insights on specialised and precise machinery, such as high-accuracy compost spreaders. Additionally, in their role as nutrient broker, the Machinenring

possess knowledge on potential nutrient input streams, and areas in which the Machinenring is active, where there are existing demands for nutrients.

Deutsches Institute für Normung

- Owns an important evaluation channel to enable customers of KIT to evaluate its properties. Through specific standards, the compost is tested for various attributes, including smell and appearance. Each batch of compost must be tested before being listed in the web shop, ensuring the safe use of KIT.

8.4.4 Channels

The key channels of the German business model are divided into the following channel categories:

- Channels that are vital to *raise awareness* about sanitation camps, nutrient rich compost and consultancy
- Channels that are vital to enable customers to *evaluate* the products functionality.
- Channels that are vital to *distribute* GE products and allow customers to *purchase* GE's products and services.
- Channels that are vital for *after sales support*

Raising awareness

The business model relies on different awareness channels when promoting the concept of nutrient recycling. GE uses both internally and externally owned awareness channels that work together in a mutually beneficial way to boost awareness. They aim to be transparent throughout all stages of its production processes to explain why KIT is needed as an alternative to artificial fertilisers, and how conventional sewer-based sanitation systems can be substituted.

Festivals and events own important channels for communicating about sanitation. They provide a platform from where GE is enabled to use photos and videos from the composting facility and raise awareness about its purpose to increase sales. When setting up and operating sanitation camps, GE sell the idea that human excreta can be used for food production. GE builds on the concept that one can use the toilet and, six months later, purchase the resulting compost, which is facilitated by hand-out QR codes, where customers can gain insights into the journey from toilet to compost and where to buy their excreta some months later. Dry-toilets are also used as a showcase to raise awareness about the concept by exhibiting plants growing from the toilet at the front-desk of the camp, symbolising the potential of recycled excreta. Meanwhile, potential visitors of GE's web shop are exposed to the GE brand, which increase its recognisability at festivals and potentially benefit from referral and the power of word-of-mouth marketing. Thus, in its role as a customer experience center, Goldeimer owns a

channel which can be used to demonstrate other complementary products and potentially partner products (Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation 2019). Insights from developing countries have similarly shown, that inclusion of partner shops into a toilet complex provided tangible revenue potential (Otoo et al. 2018). Hence, Goldeimer owns an awareness channel at festivals, which can be utilised for a variety of complementary purposes.

On the other hand, the actual web-shop of GE represents an internally owned key raising awareness channel. Circularity and the purpose of GE is communicated in different stories about the cooperatives, which help bring valuable awareness to the business model among customers entering the website.

It must also be noted that partnerships are a key component to raise awareness and support the story of closing the loop from fork to farm. In this relation, entering partnerships with farmers will help bring symbolic value and support the narrative of using human excreta for agricultural purposes.

In relation to GE's consulting services, the relevant channels have not been identified. However, partners such as the Machinenring poses an opportunity to engage potential customers and promote GE's knowhow related to composting. Alternatively, a direct sales force could be relevant to promote consulting services in the future.

Enabling evaluation

Deutsches Institute für Normung owns an important evaluation channel to enable customers of KIT to evaluate its properties. Through specifications the compost is tested on different attributes such as smell, looks, etc. Every batch of compost must be tested before it reaches the web shop, which play an important role to support the safety of using KIT.

Purchase and distribution channels

The main purchase channel is the web shop managed and owned by GE. It serves both as the primary point of sale and a key promotional tool for their brand, mission, and project initiatives. GE already has extensive experience in online sales, as they successfully sell sanitary products through this platform.

When customers have ordered the products from GE, shipping partners own the distribution channels, meaning they are responsible to ensure quality packaging, and on-time delivery for customers.

One alternative distribution channel for future development is the point of sales owned by garden shops, boutique retailers, hardware stores, and large retail chains. However, entering major retail chains requires a reliable and scalable production capacity, as failure to meet demand could lead to removal from store listings. This level of supply currently poses a challenge due to the difficulty of maintaining a continuous supply of

dry toilet matter for the compost production. However, with a significant increase in production this might prove to become a viable option in the future.

After sales support

After sales support will depend on the specific agreements made with customers of the consulting services. One opportunity is to rely on maintenance contracts where technical personnel of GE continuously support the customer with advise on the technologies of the composting plant.

8.5 Value capture

8.5.1 Revenue streams

The circular business model of the GE part of the North German Plain will capture value through different possible revenue streams, as shown in **Table 30**. Although the revenue streams are multiple, they are all driven by GE.

What distinguishes GE from other pilot partners is its unique organisational structure, which intentionally combines profit and non-profit entities. The online shop functions as the for-profit part of Goldeimer Services GmbH, focusing on e-commerce and the sale of toilets and related products to finance the non-profit activities. GmbH is GWÖ-certified, ensuring that all profits are transferred to charitable purposes rather than being distributed to shareholders. The profits generated from the for-profit GmbH are then transferred to the non-profit part (GmbH) as a donation. Prior to this project, profits were redirected to support R&D purposes for the compost. This hybrid model secures financial stability for the non-profit segment, enabling it to sustain and expand its mission-driven activities more effectively.

Moreover, the revenue model is based on cross-subsidisation, where profits from e-commerce activities are transferred to support the non-profit activities.

Table 30: Revenue streams, GE part of the North German Plain

Revenue stream	Description
Pay-per-use-fees (Festival attendees to GE)	Pay-per-use fees generates revenue from provision of dry-toilets at sanitation camps. By charging toilet-using festival attendees a variable use-rate of €2, or a flat use-rate of €20-€25 per day.
Compost transactional sales (Hobby gardeners to GE)	Selling nutrient-rich compost (once legislation permits). Revenue will be generated through transactional fees primarily aimed at urban or hobby gardeners. If the scales allow it, some revenue might also be generated from farmers. The premium compost is expected to be sold at €990/t.

<p>E-commerce revenue from GE product sales (Sanitation customers to GE)</p>	<p>A key revenue stream to drive profits and thereby support the cross-subsidising structure of GE’s business model is related to transactional sales of dry-toilets, bathroom supplies, and other sanitation-related equipment in GE’s web-shop. This cross-subsidisation involves transferring profits to the non-profit side of GE as a donation.</p>
<p>Consultancy payments (consultancy clients to GE)</p>	<p>Finally, GE generates revenue from consultancy services on planning, permitting, operating, quality testing, and advise on sourcing of raw material – all related to composting. Customers would pay based on hours spent, as a set budget per project or through a subscription-based agreement where GE are hired to continuously support the processes and maintain the recycling plant.</p>

In addition to the primary revenue streams, the following complementary revenue streams are under consideration to further strengthen the company’s financial sustainability and operational resilience:

Table 31: Additional revenue streams, GE part of the North German Plain

<p>Additional revenue stream</p>	<p>Description</p>
<p>Festival compensations (Festivals to GE)</p>	<p>While GE do not charge festivals for their sanitation services, they receive non-financial compensations that contribute to capture value generated in their sanitation camps. Instead of paying for the allocated area for the camp, fences, electricity, and festival tickets (used for volunteers), GE are offered these without charge at some festivals in Germany. This type of compensation act to capture value by reducing costs of operating a sanitation camp.</p>
<p>Disposal fees (Sanitation service providers to GE)</p>	<p>Charge disposal fees from sanitation providers who deliver raw dry toilet matter at the compost facility, similar to fees of traditional disposals at WWTPs. Early engagements initiated last autumn indicate that several stakeholders are interested in delivering their dry toilet waste to the GE compost facility. Structured as amount-based fees, they could provide a steady, but marginal source of revenue, as the disposal fees are set at €0.095/litre.</p> <p>The compost facility has already received smaller amounts of dry toilet matters from sanitation providers charging a recycling fee of €50 per bin.</p>

Commission-based payments (Compost Systems to GE)	A crucial element of GE's consultancy is to advise specifically on the technology provided by Compost System. Thus, GE may undertake promotional activities for compost systems. Such revenue streams will rely on specific agreements made with Compost Systems, and they could take various forms, e.g., commission-based payments, meaning that GE would receive a cut from the sales that their consulting generates.
Government subsidies (public entities to GE)	Securing government subsidies represent another possible revenue stream. The argument behind subsidies as value capturing lies in the rationale that GE creates both environmental and financial value for public entities such as water authorities. Thus, financial support or subsidies would be based on pollution prevention and avoided costs. Cases from developing countries have shown how the government could provide price subsidies for compost (Rao et al. 2016).

8.5.2 Financial value creation flows

Within the GE part of the German pilot, the financial value flows are relatively straight forward as GE is the sole partner, collaborating with VH, who rents out land and conducts field trials. Additionally, since the project integrates both for-profit and non-profit components within GE, internal financial flows play a crucial role.

Operationalising financial value creation flows between partners

From GE to VH: Rent payments

GE pays rent to VH for hosting the compost treatment facility and supplying machinery assistance on their premises.

From the 'for profit' to the 'non-profit' part of GE: Internal reinvestment

A portion of the profits generated by the for-profit segment of GE is redirected as donations to its non-profit part. This internal transfer ensures that surplus revenues are reinvested into mission-driven initiatives.

8.5.3 Cost structure

For the German GE pilot region, the cost structure is divided into two primary categories: CAPEX and OPEX and two scenarios, respectively one scenario based on the ideal case where GE receive the maximum amount of toilet matter possible. The other scenario assumes a production of 11,74 t DM of compost per year in the start-up phase.

CAPEX includes the one-time investments needed to set up the production facility, while OPEX covers the recurring costs associated with operating the composting facility

and delivering the compost products. The majority of the OPEX expenditures are variable to the ton of dry toilet contents processed

Table 32 below showcases OPEX and CAPEX of the initial startup phase. These estimates are based on preliminary assumptions and the values provided on the compost initially produced. As legislation prevents commercialisation, these amounts are naturally limited. As more validated expenditures becomes available with an establishment of the business model, the percentages and absolute cost figures may be further refined.

Table 32: Cost structure of CAPEX and OPEX of the startup phase, GE part of the North German Plain

Initial startup phase (based on 11,74t/compost/yr expected to be produced in 1 year)	Estimated amount (EUR)	Percentage (%)
Total CAPEX	596,413	80%
Total OPEX (1 year)	144,942	20 %
Total costs	741,355	100 %

Given these estimates, the CAPEX accounts for approximately 80 percent of total costs during the startup phase, adding up to around €600,000 needed to support the value proposition of the GE business model – mainly related to the production of compost. OPEX are expected to make up the remaining 20 percent with expenses of around 140.000 Euro. High capital expenditures are common in infrastructure-heavy sectors, where significant upfront investments are required to implement the value proposition, while the ongoing costs are primarily driven by variable and recurring expenditures related to the amount of dry toilet content processed.

For GE CAPEX and OPEX includes different cost items elaborated in **Table 33** below. Due to confidentiality of the specific cost elements, these are not elaborated in monetary amounts.

Table 33: Cost items for CAPEX and OPEX, GE part of the North German Plain

Cost category	Key items
Capital expenditures (CAPEX)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Treatment Area development (e.g. lifting platform, bin washing facility, electricians, earthworks/crane, building related consultancy etc.) • Sanitisation composter • Earthflow composter • Screening equipment • Festival toilets (80 pcs)
Operating expenditures - Fixed (1 year)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facility rental • Maintenance • Human resources (1.5 FTE)
Operating expenditures – Variable (1 year)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Composting facility operations (dependent on amount of dry toilet content) • Transport (processing & commercialisation)- • Packaging & marketing expenses • Consumables (straw, biochar, bentonite, shredded green waste) • Marketing (around 10 % of net turnover assumed)

As the business model matures and reaches full capacity, assuming maximum input of dry toilet matter, variable OPEX will increase as they depend on the volume of material processed, such as input materials and related handling costs. However, higher volumes are expected to create cost advantages through economies of scale, ultimately improving the financial sustainability of the business model. The estimated expenditures and percentages of CAPEX / OPEX in a scenario where GE receives the maximum of input are presented in **Table 34** below.

Table 34: Cost structure of CAPEX and OPEX of the ideal case - GE part of the North German Plain

Ideal case (based on maximum input material 120 t/compost /yr)	Estimated amount (EUR)	Percentage (%)
Total CAPEX	596,413	42 %
Total OPEX (1 year)	812,110	58 %
Total costs	1,408,523	100%

While CAPEX is static in both start-up and ideal case scenarios, the fixed and variable OPEX costs are estimated to account for around €800,000 per year in a best-case scenario, where GE receives the maximum input of material. This accounts for the majority of the total expenditures.

The activities which drive the largest OPEX expenditures is related to running the composting facility, which constitutes around 80 % of the OPEX alone in both the start-up and ideal case scenario. GE expects to spend between 5 % to 15 % of the net turnover of the sold product on marketing expenses. For the transportation of big bags of KIT when legislation allows for marketing, the shipping cost varies based on weight and distance. In Germany, transporting a 1m³ Big Bag ranges from €80 to €300, regardless of distance. For a full truckload over 600 km, the cost is approximately €1,000. Alternatively, compost can be packed in 20L bags, with four bags shipped via DHL for €10, including packaging, fulfilment, and freight.

While the value proposition of compost is a key activity for the GE pilot, the increased expenses related to the volumes of compost produced put high demands on the pilot's ability to capture this value efficiently through all its revenue streams.

8.6 Conclusion

This part of Metropolitan Region of North German Plain focuses on recycling faecal matter from dry festivals toilets to nutrient rich compost (KIT), addressing nutrient losses, water scarcity and reducing reliance on limited phosphorus.

GE's circular business model is unique due to GE being the sole operator of the core activities in the circular value chain, ranging from sanitation services at festivals to production and marketing of nutrient-rich compost. Additionally, experience gained in relation to the establishment of an in-house owned composting facility has created a parallel consultancy opportunity to support other businesses on the path of sanitary transformation. Similarly to VN, GE is subject to current legislation that prohibits commercialisation of compost based on human excreta.

Another distinctive characteristic of this circular business model is its aim to establish an economically viable approach to operating a purpose-driven organisation. GE balances non-profit activities with revenue generated from for-profit operations with an

organisational structure developed to support purpose-driven efforts which are often costly to operate. This reflects an innovative approach to the business model that goes beyond profit maximisation, but rather actively contributes to value creation in both sanitation and agricultural contexts. By channelling profits as donations, GE supports the financial resilience of its purpose-driven activities, which allows the company to pursue its mission-oriented goals. This model is designed to facilitate a greater adoption of circular sanitation solutions and to spread knowledge about the need for an alternative to mineral fertilisers. Thus, success for GE is measured not solely by financial sustainability, but by the widespread implementation of sustainable sanitation practices that align with GE's mission-oriented purpose.

As a well-established brand, GE has already proven its concept of entertaining and educational sanitation services, which are up and running. Festivalgoers have proven willing to pay a premium for these services, and early market validation is evident from strong festival demand. Additionally, the recently granted permits to operate the GE-owned composting facility has created an alternative local option for other portable toilet service providers to dispose of their dry-toilet matter, with a few partners already showing willingness to pay disposal fees. Currently, GE is facing a higher demand for its sanitary services than it can accommodate from a logistical, human resource, and environmental perspective (Schremmer, 2022). This suggests not only a strong demand for their services but also a growing need for additional providers offering similar solutions, who will likely require consultancy support. Being able to drive similar solutions forward would be a success criterium for GE.

Still in its early development stages, GE may benefit from research and innovation grants offered by both EU and German institutions, especially in fields related to innovation and the circular economy. These possibilities are elaborated further under the section Funding requirements for the North German Plain .

Strengths

By utilising assets already at disposal: a fleet of dry toilets, relationships with festivals and volunteers, the on-site composting plant at VH, and an experienced online sales channel, the business model is well placed to succeed in marketing both compost and consultancy services once legislation permits full commercialisation. The strategic use of GE's established e-commerce channel and strong brand recognition will support market penetration. Additionally, an established brand and strong reputation further enhances collaboration across the value chain with farmers, cooperatives, and local authorities which is a great strength of the GE business model.

The integrated approach of combining sanitation services, compost production, and consultancy creates numerous revenue opportunities. By relying on a combination of user payments, disposal fees, and consultancy-related revenue, GE complements the income generated from the mere sales of compost to increase the economic viability of the business model.

Furthermore, a clear narrative of the environmental and economic benefits created by the business activities is critical to drive acceptance. GE has implemented storytelling as a critical part of their communication efforts related to the circular nutrient loop to highlight the benefits of transitioning from linear systems to more sustainable practices. Along with transparency of their operations, these elements are key to build consumer trust among festivalgoers, hobby gardeners, municipalities, farmers, sanitation service providers, and other potential clients.

Challenges

While GE has successfully established itself in the sectors of sanitation services and e-commerce, several challenges must be overcome to unlock the composting business model. The main hurdle is the current regulatory framework both related to the operation of a composting facility, but also to allow the sales of compost based on human excreta.

Regulatory changes would improve the conditions of potential clients considering investing in a composting facility, where obtaining the right permits to plan and operate a production plant is necessary. Today, this process involves interactions with a variety of different authorities, including building and fertiliser authorities, often with long response times which complicates the matter further. Similarly, prohibited sales and use of compost made from dry-toilet matter hinders the commercialisation of the business model, and limits interest from potential clients demanding consultancy services.

A market challenge is competition on different levels. On one hand, the regions of Lower Saxony which is characterised by nutrient surpluses due to intensive pig farming industry. On the other hand, while the compost is soil improving, the composting methods are not yet as productive as conventional, low-priced fertilisers. Further, the scale of compost production does not meet broader agricultural demands. These issues have led GE to shift its focus from large-scale farming to offering a premium product for hobby gardeners, and broaden their practices to involve consultancy thereby being an indirect force to broaden adoption of alternative human excreta treatment.

At the same time, recognising and internalising the environmental and social costs associated with conventional fertilisers, such as nutrient runoff, water contamination, and greenhouse gas emissions, can shift the economic balance. These external costs are often excluded from market prices but are nonetheless real burdens on society. By accounting for these externalities, the solutions proposed in the pilot region may emerge as competitive alternatives.

9 Environmental and organisation value creation flows across the North German Plain

The following section will explore the environmental and organisational value creation flows in the North German Plain region across both business models. While the business models differ by having two circular solutions, the environmental and organisational value creation flows will be discussed together, as they share several common elements.

While the environmental impacts and benefits in this section have been identified through interviews and desktop research, a life cycle assessment is being conducted as part of the P2Green project. This assessment will provide a more comprehensive study of the environmental impact and is being carried out in WP2 and elaborated in T 2.3.

9.1 Environmental value creation flows

VN and GE, as the technology and fertiliser providers, enable a flow of environmental value creation across partners, including value creation for internal partners such as KWB and VH as well as external partners such as Finizio, farmers, festivals, Barnim County and North German Plain region. Each partner plays a role in the circular value chain and thereby in reducing environmental impacts through their interconnected activities. The circular business models create environmental value by addressing multiple ecological challenges.

From GE and VN to VH

The production of fertiliser and compost are expected to reduce the environmental footprint of farmers by minimising reliance on energy-intensive mineral fertilisers emitting greenhouse gases. An analysis of the environmental benefits of Aurin as a fertiliser showed a CO₂e reduction of 549 grams per kilogram of grain produced. The reclaimed nutrients help avoid the greenhouse gas emissions typically associated with conventional fertiliser production, reducing the carbon footprint of agricultural practices. Thus, compared to conventional fertiliser, VN and GE offer a less energy-intensive substitute.

From the opposite perspective, VH provide industrial waste heat for GE's composting facility. This reduces the need for alternative energy sources, thus lowering the overall use of energy when producing compost fertiliser.

From VN to KWB

The environmental value creation flow identified between VN and KWB is exemplified by a dotted line, representing the situation in which KWB simulates a building owner. This is due to urine recycling currently being an area of R&D for KWB, thus having no direct environmental benefit from participating in the circular value chain. However, in

the role of a building owner, they will gain benefits related to reduced carbon emissions by avoiding discharges of urine into WWTPs.

Environmental value from the pilot region to the County of Barnim and the North German Plain

There are multiple environmental benefits flowing from VN and GE, to the County of Barnim. These include a reduction in aquatic nutrient pollution due to the avoidance of nutrient disposal via local utilities and reduced GHG emissions from the nitrogen removal process (nitrification-denitrification) and the anaerobic digestion of organic matter in sludge treatment processes.

By diverting urine and faeces from WWTP's converting it into fertilisers and compost help reduce nitrogen and phosphorus pollution, which are major contributors to water body eutrophication in the North German Plain (P2Green, 2023b; German Environmental Agency, 2017).

German regions are increasingly experiencing issues related to the availability of fresh water, which led to several German municipalities to declare water crises due to dry periods during the summer. Whereas traditional chemical toilets use large amounts of drinking water with every use the dry toilet system provided by GE, in contrast save approximately six litres per flush. Since the introduction of their services in 2013, over 8.5 million litres of drinking water have been conserved (Goldeimer, 2025).

The increased population density of urban areas in Europe further increases the pressure on the local WWTPs with an emerging need for cities to consider alternatives to traditional wastewater treatment. In this context, the nutrient recycling system also represents an alternative to either building new WWTPs or extending the already established plants. The ability to stand as a supplement to the WWTPs that are expected to manage quantities that are beyond their capacities in the future to come, is further perceived as valuable to the regional WWTPs.

The nutrient rich compost product from GE improves soil quality by adding organic matter and increasing humus levels. This is particularly beneficial in regions like eastern Germany that has sandy soils, where soil degradation and poor water retention are common challenges. By enhancing soil structure and fertility, this compost solution not only supports plant growth but also contributes to long-term soil health and resilience in the region.

Recycling human excreta into compost reduces reliance on the resource phosphorus, while Aurin reduced reliance on nitrogen extraction. Phosphorus is extracted through mining, contributing to environmental degradation (Reijnders, 2014), while nitrogen is extracted through the GHG emitting process of Haber-Bosch (Beneker et al. 2023, based on Menegat et al., 2022; Steffen et al., 2015). The business models of VN and

GE are therefore reducing pressure on exceeded planetary boundaries, including freshwater use, novel entities, and biogeochemical nitrogen and phosphorus flows (Beneker et al., 2023, based on Richardson et al., 2023).

While the collaboration in the value chain offers nutrient recycling with great benefits, potential environmental drawbacks require further investigation.

The pilot projects will require energy input and materials to build the technologies, containers, separating toilets, and the infrastructure needed. Further the transportation of toilet matter input will be an environmental negative through GHG emissions. This is addressed by GE, who considers both environmental and cost factors when reviewing requests as it does not make sense to set up three toilets for an event hundreds of kilometres away from the treatment facility, in line with GE's local and circular approach.

Additionally, using too much nutrient rich compost, or Aurin fertiliser, can cause similar environmental problems as mineral fertilisers. Therefore, only the necessary amount should be applied to the soil.

It is important to note, that the environmental positive and negative impacts for the pilot will be assessed in depths in WP2, task 2.3, through a lifecycle assessment of environmental impacts.

9.2 Organisational value creation flow between the North German Plain partners

The value creation flows refer to the streams of value stemming from the business models and are generated based on the activities of all the participating project partners. The organisational value creation flows from the two business models: VN and GE will be addressed jointly as there are several overlaps.

Organisational value creation flows include parameters such as knowledge exchanged between partners, capacity building, brand spill over or know how created in favour of the regional society. There is multiple value creation flows between the four partners in the pilot. These will in the following be further elaborated.

Collaboration

Collaboration is the overarching key organisational value that is determining for the success of the circular solution. However, collaboration also requires an extra effort from the partners to be able to succeed with the circular solution. Collaboration is operationalised through the following value creation flows among the partners:

Synergy effects

According to the participants, the ability to leverage each other's competencies contributes to building a more robust and well-founded business case. This is largely driven by knowledge-sharing and the opportunity to draw upon one another's experiences and expertise. As a result, the partnership provides a stronger foundation and has proven valuable in addressing challenges as they arise. The presence of other

partners brings visibility and credibility that the other partners can benefit from. The credible and well-known brands of GE and VN, along with the good reputation of KWB among local politicians, has built up goodwill that the other partners benefit from in the collaboration and thereby stand as more established than they would have, operating alone. This creates an image-spill-over effect among the other participants and the value chain.

Gatekeeping

The participation of KWB is vital for sourcing of input material for the production processes of the German pilot region. Through their established relationship with sanitation service provider, Finizio, they enable urine to enter the VN's production of fertiliser. Additionally, since KWB is publicly owned along with their strong reputation among politicians is assessed as a potential enabler of initiating talks about public support.

Willingness to engage

Currently, VH neither pays for nor receives payment for the fertiliser used for conducting field trials of Auring fertiliser and KIT compost at their farm. Nevertheless, this partnership highlights something beyond financial transactions, through the willingness to share risks, specifically by allocating 6 hectares of land dedicated for field trials. By taking part in this collaboration, the parties involved demonstrate a commitment to cooperation and mutual benefit rather than focusing solely on economic gain. Their collaboration underscores the importance of trust and shared responsibility in developing sustainable agricultural practices.

The Aurin fertiliser is produced from urine, representing only one waste stream from the collection of resources from toilets. VN is interested in testing mixing their fertiliser with other waste products to be able to supplement organic matters to increase the quality of their product. Through the collaboration with GE, that can collect both urine and faces, VN has the potential to develop their product further to heighten the quality of their product. The fertiliser and compost market are complex and dynamic but the collaboration between GE and VN makes it possible for them to continuously develop and test new product innovation. This may essentially result in more fertiliser options for users, as they can adapt their fertilising practices based on the needs of their plants.

Knowledge sharing and capacity building

The partners are learning from each other. GE offers valuable expertise not only in product development but also in logistics and e-commerce, which is especially beneficial to VN. This exchange of knowledge enables the partners to derive valuable lessons from their collaboration and internal discussions. Even across pilot regions, S360 from the Swedish pilot and VN continue to share knowledge and expertise, despite being competitors.

Related to capacity building, the integration of VN's Aurin treatment system allow KWB to add an additional service to their portfolio of recycling services, thereby improving their offering towards Barnim County.

The capacity-building effects and knowledge sharing extend beyond internal organisational value creation within the pilot. By demonstrating the feasibility of nutrient reclamation flows, the pilot project will help raise awareness of how these solutions can be integrated and what is required to support them. This will not only benefit the Barnim County district through the environmental benefits of the nutrient recycling solution, but also contribute to the broader political landscape, fostering a deeper understanding of the potential for such solutions at both the local and regional levels.

10 Funding requirements for the North German Plain

In this chapter we provide an overview of the financing requirements of the key partners involved in the North German Plain.

Implementing the two envisaged circular business models require financial investments in:

Table 35: Business models financing requirements - North German Plain

Business Model 1: VN & KWB (urine)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Initial investment in technology• Infrastructure for collection and transportation (urine separation toilets, logistics fleet)• Processing facilities (Aurin treatment system, storage units, quality control mechanisms)• Research and compliance with agricultural standards• Market development and farmer outreach programs• Operational costs, and scaling efforts to establish a viable market for bio-based fertilisers.
Business Model 2: GE (faeces)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Establishing composting facilities• Scaling collection logistics• Navigating legal restrictions• Investing in marketing to promote the benefits of compost fertilisation• Financial support for expanding GE's consulting services to municipalities, sanitation service providers, and farmers.

Given the current legal restrictions on the commercial sale of fertilisers derived from human excreta in Germany, funding needs are also directed toward regulatory efforts to enable market entry.

Funding requirements will change and evolve throughout the different stages of the circular business model. The following **Table 36** provides an overview of the identified funding requirements for each of the three development stages of the business model, as well as funding options suited to different stages of development.

Table 36: Funding requirements - North German Plain

Stages of development			
Stage	Proof of concept & design development	Testing & pilot implementation	Scaling & optimisation
Corresponding TRL	1-4	5-7	8-9
Stage Objective	Validate the feasibility of the business model concept and develop initial technological designs.	Pilot the integrated circular business model under real-world conditions.	Expand the business model across the region and optimise operational performance.
Investment in	Research, lab testing, feasibility studies, and initial system design. Pilot facilities, small-scale testing, market research, and advocacy for regulatory changes.	Pilot infrastructure setup, field trials, performance evaluation, stakeholder training, and data analysis. Construction of operational facilities, expansion of collection networks, and legal compliance efforts.	Expansion of infrastructure, optimisation for scalability, commercialisation efforts, and policy integration. Large-scale production capacity, commercialisation efforts, consulting services expansion, and international market entry.
Funds required (VN & KWB)	€200,000 - €400,000	€800,000 - €1,200,000	€1,500,000 - €2,500,000
Funds required (GE)	€ 100,000 – €300,000	€ 500,000 – €1,000,000	€1,000,000 – €2,000,000
Types of funding	Public & Private Grants, Angel Investors, Venture Capital	Grants, Equity, Crowdfunding, subordinated loans	Equity and debt financing, Blended-finance

Requirements of financing partners	Strong founding Team, Large (growing) Market, Differentiated Product/Technology	Proven revenue model, clear path and timeline to profitability	Stable, profitable business with recurring Cash-flows
Position of Key Technology/ Partner at Start of P2Green		Faecal composting, GE (TRL 5) Aurin®, VN (TRL 6)	
Target Position of Key Technology/ Partner		Faecal composting, GE (TRL 7)	Aurin®, VN (TRL 8)

The active participation and collaboration of key partners are crucial for the success of the project. Each partner plays a unique role in the value chain, contributing to resource recovery, product development, and agricultural application. The following outlines the specific funding needs for these partners:

KWB

Serving as a platform for the Aurin treatment system, KWB needs funding for infrastructure setup, logistics coordination, and maintaining collaborations with partners like Finizio. Additionally, KWB requires resources to manage urine collection and disposal logistics, ensuring efficient nutrient recycling.

Finizio

The service provider responsible for collecting and transporting urine requires investment for transportation logistics, collection equipment, and potential expansion to serve larger events and urban areas.

VN (Technology Provider)

As the technology provider for the Aurin treatment system, VN requires funding for the production and scaling of the Aurin system, including reactor development, material costs, and operational expenses. VN's funding needs also cover research for optimizing the Aurin production process, market expansion efforts, and addressing legal barriers.

VH

Funding is needed for the infrastructure to host composting facilities, field trials to evaluate the performance of the compost, and adherence to agricultural regulations.

As the agricultural partner utilising the produced fertiliser, VH also needs support to adapt its agricultural practices and monitor the efficiency of the bio-fertiliser.

GE

As the main operator, GE requires funding for establishing and maintaining composting infrastructure, developing marketing strategies, and expanding its consultancy services. Additional investment is necessary for regulatory advocacy to legalise the sale of faecal compost.

The total estimated investment for the VN & KWB business model across the three development stages is between €2.5 million and €4.1 million. These investments are crucial for overcoming current legal challenges, achieving technological optimisation, and expanding market reach to establish a sustainable, circular business model for bio-based fertilisers.

For the GE business model, the total estimated investment across the three development stages is between €1.6 million and €2.6 million. These investments are essential for overcoming legal and logistical barriers, optimising compost production processes, and expanding market reach for compost products and consulting services.

10.1 Barriers to entry and key readiness factors

Barriers to entry

The two circular business models in the North German Plain respectively, VN & KWB and GE, face several barriers to entry for potential investors. Here are the key barriers based on the envisaged business models:

Regulatory barriers

The primary and most significant barrier is the legal prohibition against the commercialisation of bio-based fertilisers derived from urine and faeces in Germany. Although Aurin is approved in Austria, Switzerland, Lichtenstein, and France, marketing it in Germany remains illegal. This lack of regulatory approval severely limits scaling, revenue generation, and investor confidence.

Market acceptance and demand

While there is interest in sustainable, circular solutions, convincing farmers and larger agricultural cooperatives of the value of bio-based fertilisers remains a challenge. Many are accustomed to large-scale, mineral fertilisers that are cheaper and easier to access. The niche appeal of the products limits market penetration and scalability.

Economic and financial barriers

The cost of producing fertilisers like Aurin is currently significantly higher than mineral alternatives. The high initial capital expenditure (CAPEX) and operational expenditure

(OPEX) for setting up collection and treatment infrastructure, combined with a lengthy return on investment, create financial risks.

Technical and logistical challenges

Both business models rely on relatively new, decentralised technologies that require significant investment and adaptation. Additionally, logistics for urine and faeces collection, particularly at large scales, are complex and costly. Ensuring efficient and consistent collection from festivals, events, and public areas poses operational challenges.

Infrastructure dependencies

The dependency on partners like Finizio for urine collection and KWB for site premises means that disruptions in these partnerships could jeopardise the business model. Moreover, public water authorities control wastewater, and conflicts of interest could arise if traditional wastewater treatment plants face reduced revenue due to decentralised solutions.

Scaling and replication challenges

While the VN model has proven successful in Switzerland, replicating this success in the German market requires navigating stricter regulations, securing financing, and expanding partnerships to build a robust value chain.

Key funding readiness factors

For the long-term success of the two German business models securing financing for the final development stage (Scaling & optimisation) is vital.

This section identifies the key funding readiness factors for the involved partners.

Proven technology and operational effectiveness

- Technical validation: The Aurin treatment system and GE's composting process must demonstrate proven efficiency in nutrient recycling, safety compliance, and cost-effectiveness through field trials and pilot implementations.
- Operational efficiency: Both business models should exhibit streamlined logistics, cost-effective production processes, and optimised distribution networks.

Market validation and demand assessment

- Market traction: Evidence of demand for bio-based fertilisers among farmers, municipalities, and hobby gardeners through pre-orders, pilot customers, or letters of intent.

- Market research: Comprehensive data validating the competitive advantage of circular fertilisers over conventional options, highlighting environmental benefits and cost competitiveness.

Regulatory compliance and legal pathway

- Compliance readiness: Clear pathways for legal compliance in Germany and strategies for market entry amid current regulatory constraints.
- Advocacy and lobbying: Active engagement with regulatory bodies to influence favourable policy changes and gain market access.

Financial viability and scalability

- Cost structure and pricing strategy: Transparent cost structures with demonstrated strategies for achieving economies of scale, reducing production costs, and increasing profitability.
- Revenue streams: Multiple and diversified revenue streams, including system sales, fertiliser sales, consultancy services, and potential utility partnerships.
- Investment case: A strong business case showcasing ROI within 10-15 years, supported by data from the scaled-up operations in Switzerland (VN) and projected scenarios for GE.

Strategic partnerships and stakeholder engagement

- Collaborative networks: strong partnerships with waste management entities (KWB), event organisers, agricultural stakeholders, and public authorities.
- Public-private synergies: Potential collaborations with public utilities and local governments for infrastructure support, policy influence, and co-financing.

Environmental and social impact

- Impact metrics: Quantifiable data on environmental benefits, including reduced nitrogen and phosphorus runoff, lower CO₂ emissions, and water savings.
- Alignment with SDGs: Strong alignment with SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation), SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), and SDG 13 (Climate Action).

10.2 Funding options and funding sources

Considering the funding requirements of the key partners as described in the previous chapter, this chapter explores various funding options and identifies suitable potential financing partners for each key partner in the German pilot.

Table 37: Funding options and funding sources - North German Plain

Key partner	Funding type	Funding partner	Description / Access requirements
VN, KWB, GE	Grants	<p>Bundesministerium für Umwelt, Naturschutz, nukleare Sicherheit und Verbraucherschutz - Umweltinnovationsprogramm (BMUV - UIP) (German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection)</p> <p>Note for VN: Applies to domestic and foreign commercial enterprises with a permanent establishment ("Betriebsstätte") in Germany.</p>	<p>The Environmental Innovation Programme funds large-scale demonstration projects in Germany that show for the first time how advanced processes can be used and combined to avoid or reduce environmental pollution after research and development has been completed.</p> <p>Commercial enterprises and legal entities under public and private law are eligible to apply. Funding prioritises small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Amount max. €7.5m</p>
		Horizon Europe - EU	<p>Is the EU's key funding programme for research and innovation. It tackles climate change, helps to achieve the UN's Sustainable Development Goals and boosts the EU's competitiveness and growth.</p>
KWB	Grants	<p>European Investment Bank (EIB)</p> <p>"Circular City Centre (C3)"</p>	<p>The EIB supports projects in Europe in the field of circular economy and sustainable infrastructure. In the area of the sanitation transition, investments in wastewater treatment systems or innovative water management solutions could be supported.</p> <p>Circular City Centre (C3) Financing expertise by:</p>

			<p>leveraging horizontal (market) studies to further define funding gaps,</p> <p>recommending internal EIB-managed instruments and/or Investment Platforms (IP),</p> <p>structuring/implementing Investment Platforms that mobilise public/private investors.</p>
VN, KWB, GE	Grants, loans	<p>Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau (KfW) (German state-owned investment and development bank)</p> <p>“Nr. 230 Umweltinnovationsprogramm”</p> <p>“Nr 240/241 KfW-Umweltprogramm”</p> <p>“Nr. 291 KfW-Konsortialkredit Nachhaltige Transformation - > Modul D”</p> <p>“Nr. 293 Klimaschutzoffensive für Unternehmen -> Modul D”</p> <p>Note for VN: Nr. 230, Applies to domestic and foreign commercial enterprises with a permanent establishment ("Betriebsstätte") in Germany. Nr. 240/241, Nr. 291 & Nr. 293</p>	<p>The KfW offers various funding programmes in Germany for environmentally friendly and sustainable projects that also affect the sanitation transition. These programmes support the development of innovative technologies in the areas of wastewater and water management.</p> <p>“Nr. 230 Umweltinnovationsprogramm”</p> <p>With the Environmental Innovation Programme, KfW promotes innovative large-scale pilot projects that sustainably relieve the burden on our environment – projects that have not yet been implemented on the market and serve as role models. Funding available for construction measures, machinery and expenses for commissioning as well as, where applicable, for measurements to monitor the success of these measures – particularly in the areas of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • wastewater treatment

		<p>The following are eligible to apply for projects in Germany:</p> <p>Natural persons, legal entities and partnerships with legal capacity with a majority of private-law participation, each acting in the exercise or for the purpose of taking up a commercial or freelance activity – with a registered office in Germany or with a registered office abroad.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• waste prevention, recycling and disposal• circular economy• soil protection <p>Investment projects that serve as models and are aimed at achieving adaptation to climate change can also be funded, provided that environmental pollution is directly avoided or reduced as a result.</p> <p>“Nr 240/241 KfW-Umweltprogramm”</p> <p>The KfW environmental programme promotes investments that improve the environmental situation and climate protection, conserve resources, strengthen biodiversity and natural habitats, or serve to adapt to the consequences of climate change.</p> <p>The eligible measures include, in particular measures for the efficient and circular use of resources (‘Circular Economy’)</p> <p>“Nr. 291 KfW-Konsortialkredit Nachhaltige Transformation – Modul D”</p> <p>Funding will be provided to companies that align their business model with the environmental objectives defined in the EU taxonomy, as well as to investments in the construction and acquisition of eligible plants and the modernisation of existing plants. These include:</p>
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			<p>Module D: Drinking water, waste water and solid waste.</p> <p>“Nr. 293 Klimaschutzoffensive für Unternehmen - Modul D”</p> <p>KfW is promoting investments in measures to reduce, avoid and reduce greenhouse gas emissions with a low-interest loan including</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measures for the provision of drinking water and wastewater treatment, including facilities for collection and distribution. • Construction of new plants for the collection and recycling of waste.
<p>VN, KWB, GE</p>	<p>Grants</p>	<p>Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung (BMBF) (German Federal Ministry of Education and Research) and its platform FONA (Research for Sustainability)</p>	<p>The BMBF provides funding for research projects in the field of sustainability and the circular economy. This includes projects dealing with sustainable sanitation and water treatment.</p> <p>FONA supports projects that develop solutions for sustainable development, including the promotion of circular business models.</p>
		<p>Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz (BMWK) (German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action) and its programs Zentrales Innovationsprogramm (ZIM) and INVEST</p> <p>Note for VN: Applies to domestic and foreign commercial</p>	<p>ZIM supports research and development projects by small and medium-sized enterprises, including those focusing on circular economy.</p> <p>INVEST supports investments by business angels in innovative start-ups, including those in the circular economy. Amount max. €100k</p>

		enterprises with a permanent establishment ("Betriebsstätte") in Germany.	
	Grants & loans	Investitionsbank Berlin (Pro FIT) Note: With a registered office in Berlin or at least one organisationally independent place of business in Berlin.	Supports research, innovation and technology projects by companies based in Berlin, including those focusing on circular economy. Amount: Loans max. €1m, Grants max. €400k.
VN	Grants & loans	Innosuisse Schweizerische Agentur für Innovationsförderung "Eurostars" "EUREKA" "IraSME"	The Eurostars initiative is particularly aimed at innovative SMEs. Eureka is an independent initiative of 50 countries, separate from the European Commission's framework programmes, to promote cross-border collaborative projects in market-oriented research and development. Innosuisse and the ZIM programme of the German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Protection support bilateral (and multilateral) cooperation between companies from Switzerland and Germany in the IraSME network. Cooperative innovation projects between Switzerland and Germany are funded through IraSME calls for proposals.

VN

As VN requires funding for both scaling up and research, it may benefit from grants offered by various EU programs and – as the pilot project itself is in Germany – by German ministries, including the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate

Action. Additionally, VN could leverage traditional financing sources, such as loans from the European Investment Bank (EIB), KfW, or conventional project finance loans from established financial institutions. The company may also explore opportunities for research and development (R&D) partnerships to further support its growth and innovation efforts.

KWB

As a research-focused organisation within P2Green, KWB currently benefits from EU funding and may explore additional grant opportunities from the European Investment Bank (particularly through the Circular City Centre), as well as from several German ministries (e.g. the UIP program of the Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation).

GE

GE's business model within P2Green is currently in the early stages of the second phase of development (Testing & Pilot Implementation) and remains in the research phase as a non-profit entity. Given this status, GE may benefit from a wide range of research and innovation grants at both the EU and local levels in Germany. In particular, the Federal Ministry for the Environment and Nature Conservation, the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action, and the Federal Ministry of Education and Research provide support for projects focused on innovation sanitation and the circular economy.

In conclusion, VN, KWB, and GE can leverage various funding opportunities to support their respective growth and research initiatives. VN may benefit from EU and German ministry grants while also exploring traditional financing options and R&D partnerships. KWB, as a research-focused organisation, can seek additional grants from the European Investment Bank and German ministries. GE, still in the early stages of development, can take advantage of research and innovation grants from both EU and German institutions, particularly in areas related to innovation and the circular economy. These strategic funding approaches will enhance their contributions to sustainable development.

11 Circular Business Model: The Axarquía pilot region

11.1 The potential of the Axarquía pilot region

Axarquía is a region located in the province of Malaga on the southern coast of Spain. Malaga ranks as the fourth most economically active province in Spain, with key sectors including tourism, construction, and agriculture (Internet Archive, 2011; Euro Weekly News, 2024). Notably, the province is the leading producer of tropical and subtropical crops in Europe. Malaga, alongside the Granada region, is responsible for producing about one-third of the avocados consumed within the European Union. Additionally, the cultivation of mangos in Axarquía has heavily increased the previous years and in 2024 the region supplied 90 % of the mangos cultivated within the European Union (Cabezas, 2024b; Departamento de Fruticultura Tropica, 2005).

The agricultural sector in Malaga is facing critical challenges, primarily stemming from water stress in the region which refers to the lack of sufficient freshwater resources to meet standard water demands. The province experiences persistent water scarcity, overexploitation of groundwater, and a significant risk of desertification. This is compounded by nutrient pollution, which affects the water ways (Stuber, 2023). Malaga's Mediterranean climate, coupled with high agricultural demands, limited natural water resources, and a growing population driven by tourism, intensifies the region's water-related challenges (Rodríguez-Villanueva & Sauri, 2021). The increasing demand for avocados and mangoes has further exacerbated these issues (Okendo, 2024).

As a result, many farmers rely on illegal water use, including illegal wells and unregulated irrigation systems. In 2017, it was reported that 30–40% of the irrigated land in Malaga's Axarquía region was illegally irrigated, and the irrigated area has since continued to grow despite severe droughts (Cabezas, 2024). This unsustainable practice not only depletes water resources, but also contributes to soil erosion, biodiversity loss, and the destruction of river ecosystems.

Water scarcity has severe economic implications for farmers, who face increasing water costs that make cultivating water-intensive crops like mangos and avocados increasingly difficult. In the Axarquía region, the 2023/2024 water shortage devastated mango production, resulting in an 80 % reduction in yield compared to an average year (Euro Weekly News, 2023; Cabezas, 2024b). Avocado harvests were similarly affected, with yields falling by approximately 50 % (Cabezas, 2022). This drought profoundly impacted the agricultural sector, creating economic strain for local farmers, underscoring the need for a steady availability of water supply suitable for agricultural uses.

The farmers also face external challenges. The limited natural resources of phosphorous puts current food systems at risk. Therefore, the mission of the Spanish pilot is to reduce the dependence on water resources and phosphate by utilising nutrient-rich reclaimed water to create an alternative irrigating and fertilising solution. By utilising the wastewater from households in the region, the reclaimed water with its

nutrients can be channelled to the regional farmers providing them with fertigation. Besides saving freshwater, the nutrient-rich reclaimed water allows the farmers to reduce their use of mineral fertilisers.

Moreover, the solution proposed in the Spanish pilot region provides sanitation options and waste management practices that reduce the release of pollutants through WWTP to the coastal areas of Malaga.

11.2 Introduction to the pilot region

The Spanish pilot consists of a collaboration between five partners. The partners are Bioazul (BioA), a company that operates a tertiary treatment plant (TTP) and provides the technology to produce the nutrient rich reclaimed water. Axaragua (AXA) - a public operator of the municipal WWTP, AGL, a software company developing the Smart Fertigation Tool (SFT) that provides insights into nutrients levels in soil, TROPS, a cooperative representing the farmers and a technical advisor within fertigation and finally, CETAQUA (CET) a water research centre responsible for data analysis of the reclaimed water.

BioA serves as the connector between pilot partners. The wastewater treatment process is well-established and has been providing reclaimed water in the p2green scope since February 2023. The reclaimed has demonstrated a high agronomic value as a fertiliser supported by promising preliminary NPK values (Beneker et al., 2023). Together, the partners produce reclaimed water used as both irrigation and fertiliser (also referred to as fertigation). AXA receives the wastewater through the WWTP and after primary and secondary filtration the water is redirected to the TTP operated by BioA. At the TTP BioA produces reclaimed water as a nutrient rich effluent for fertigation, with the analysis of the reclaimed water being delivered by CET. AGL has a nutrient control sensor that can register the nutrients level in the water, and they deliver a decision support system for the farmers to monitor the nutrients needed by the crops. The reclaimed water is distributed to farmers, which is currently facilitated by TROPS. Development of the SFT is currently on its way. However, while the technology for collecting field data is mature, the algorithm designed to measure NPK concentrations in water for optimal nutrient adjustment is currently in development. The pilot aims to develop an integrated irrigation fertigation system, targeting TRL 8 by the conclusion of P2Green.

Figure 6 illustrates the circular supply chain, showing the transformation of wastewater from a wasted resource into fertigation leading to crops production and consumption, thereby closing the loop from farm to fork.

Figure 6: Circular value chain – Axarquía pilot region

In the following the assumptions and decisions made when developing the business model is described. Following this, the CBMC is described through its building blocks: *value proposition*, *value creation & delivery*, and *value capture*. The full circular business model canvas is illustrated in Appendix IV: Circular Business Model Canvas: Axarquía pilot region. Additionally, the organisational, financial, and environmental value creation flows are explored and integrated throughout the business model. These value creation flow parameters are illustrated below, again with the monetary flow representing hypothetical internal financial flows as a part of the possible revenue streams which are elaborated in the following sections:

Figure 7: Value creation flow parameters between partners in the Spanish pilot region

11.3 Assumptions and decisions

The following decisions and assumptions have been made for the development of the CBMC:

- The circular business model is developed with its main focus on BioA and AGL, as they are the main providers of the circular solution. BioA and AGL’s solution is the link connecting partners, that already exist in the marketplace, and BioA and AGL are critical to the success of the circular business model.
- Although the value proposition and offerings are clearly defined, the detailed structure such as cost distribution, revenue streams, and overall financial setup is still in an initial phase and not yet fully matured. The presented CBMC and value creation flows therefore illustrate an envisioned business model and the supporting building blocks, highlighting various pathways toward developing a viable circular business approach.
- Throughout revenue streams and cost structures, certain costs and revenues have been estimated and presented as percentages due to the confidentiality of the underlying data. As a result, the cost structures are based on both actual and projected costs provided by pilot partners.
- Throughout the business model, when environmental claims are made these may not be used for communication purposes unless these are documented, for example

through a life-cycle analysis or similar documentation. Focus of this deliverable is the business models of the pilots, whereas work package 2 documents the environmental impact of the pilot regions.

11.4 Value proposition

The value proposition consists of four distinct value propositions that serve different customer segments both upstream and downstream provided by the pilot region value chain partners BioA, AGL and TROPS.

It should be noted that a lifecycle analysis (LCA) must be done to document the impact of the value propositions described below before marketing either of the value propositions as sustainable, sustainably grown, environmentally friendly or similar. An LCA study will be performed in P2Green under work package 2 (D 2.3).

Table 38: Value Proposition - Axarquía pilot region

	Value proposition	Value created for customer segment
Upstream	Water reclamation plant (WRP)	<p>For public water authorities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transforms wastewater into a revenue source by producing reclaimed water for irrigation. Customisable tertiary treatment system that integrates into existing WWTPs or operates as a decentralised solution. Reduces well water consumption, addressing regional water scarcity. Minimises discharge into the sea, avoiding environmental taxes. Ensures compliance with upcoming EU regulations (Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive). <p>For irrigation communities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reliable water source during droughts, increasing regional self-sufficiency. Customisable water quality to meet different crop and irrigation system needs. Alternative to costly mineral fertilisers, reducing dependency on global price fluctuations.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decentralised installation option for larger cooperatives capable of managing the system.
Upstream	Smart Fertigation Tool (SFT)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Optimises crop fertilisation by measuring and managing NPK concentrations in soil and reclaimed water. Through the precise management and optimisation of mineral fertiliser application, the approach mitigates adverse environmental impacts, particularly the contamination of surface and groundwater resources by excessive nitrate levels. Prevents over-fertilisation, ensuring compliance with regulations like Royal Decree 1085/2024 Reduces dependency on well water and mineral fertilisers, lowering costs. Enhances crop health and yield, improving farm profitability. Provides automated decision support, integrating real-time data from soil and water sensors. Strengthens buyer-seller relationships by supplying data on water use and carbon emissions.
Production	Water reclamation and joint fertigation services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complete fertigation management, combining wastewater treatment and nutrient monitoring. Ensures compliance with EU Regulation 2020/741, reducing risks of eutrophication and health hazards. Optimises water and mineral fertiliser use, lowering costs for irrigation communities. Enhances crop yields and soil health, improving agricultural productivity. Strengthens resource security, mitigating drought and fertiliser price volatility.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ideal for farming cooperatives, offering a large-scale irrigation solution. • Potential licensing or contracting models, enabling strategic partnerships between BioA and AGL.
Downstream	Avocados and mangos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-quality avocados and mangos, cultivated with reclaimed water. • Support retailers in reducing Scope 3 emissions. • Meets growing consumer demand for eco-friendly and responsibly sourced produce. • Potential for eco-certification, increasing transparency and market appeal. • Strengthens brand differentiation and communication of sustainable initiatives for retailers.

Water reclamation plant (WRP), upstream

BioA provides customised water reclamation solutions transforming wastewater into a valuable resource for agricultural fertigation. By integrating tertiary treatment (TT) into existing WWTPs or installing decentralised systems, BioA enables the production of nutrient-rich reclaimed water, reducing reliance on scarce natural water reservoirs and offering an alternative for irrigation. The tertiary filtration treatment is designed to decrease suspended solids and organic matter, ensuring the removal of harmful microorganisms and preparing the water for subsequent disinfection. BioA’s solution can recover 72% of nitrogen and 63% of phosphorus from the reclaimed water (Beneker et al., 2023).

Public water authorities

Due to its highly customisable nature, the WRP can be installed at any WWTP. Thereby, the WWTP is enabled to produce reclaimed water on demand and customise the nutritional contents to meet the demands of the irrigation users. WWTPs can thereby turn wastewater, currently accounting for expenses, into a new source of income.

A related effect from the value proposition is the reduction in the amounts of well water being used for irrigation in the region, which is currently subject to scarcity issues. Additionally, by utilising wastewater for irrigation purposes, WWTPs avoid the discharge of secondary treated water into the sea, making it an economically beneficial alternative.

BioA's WRP enables water authorities to reach future legislative compliance. Currently, there are no legal requirements related to TT, however, with the new Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive issued by the European Commission, tertiary treatment will be a requirement for larger plants from 2035 and from 2045 further applied for smaller plants. Therefore, the regional government of Andalusia has initiated a push related to installation TT at the regional WWTPs.

Irrigation communities

The WRP can also be installed as a decentralised system. While WWTPs typically handle reclaimed water production, larger irrigation communities and cooperatives like TROPS may operate their own systems where municipal WWTPs lack TT. These communities can treat secondary effluent from existing WWTPs, producing reclaimed water independently.

This flexible solution ensures water quality meets specific irrigation needs, such as stricter filtration for sprinkler systems. It also enhances water access in drought-prone regions, reducing reliance on well water and increasing resilience. Additionally, farmers benefit from stable fertiliser costs due to the nutrient-rich reclaimed water.

Smart Fertigation Tool (SFT), upstream

AGL helps farmers optimise crop cultivation through the SFT, designed for those using reclaimed water. The system includes two sensors - one in the soil and one in the reclaimed water tank, along with a cloud-based software application that provides automated decision support.

Without monitoring, farmers risk over-fertilisation, especially in Nitrate Vulnerable Zones (NVZ). With the SFT, farmers benefit from reduced reliance on mineral fertilisers and well water, expectingly leading to cost savings and improved crop yields. Additionally, the data collected enhances farming practices and may support sustainability reporting by providing transparency on carbon and water footprints, potentially strengthening relationships with buyers like TROPS.

Water reclamation and joint fertigation services, production

The synergy between the WRP and the SFT enables a third value proposition: an integrated solution managing the entire fertigation process. By combining tertiary wastewater treatment with real-time NPK monitoring, this approach ensures precise nutrient delivery to crops, contingent on the SFT reaching sufficient maturity. To comply with Regulation (EU) 2020/741, treated wastewater must meet strict nutrient and health safety criteria. This solution addresses these requirements through ozone disinfection to eliminate pathogens and SFT monitoring to prevent over-fertilisation. The benefits include reduced water and fertiliser costs, optimised nutrient application, and higher agricultural yields, supporting both WWTPs and irrigation communities. Farming cooperatives are the primary customer segment, as the investment required is

substantial. A combined offering would allow BioA to deliver a full irrigation system, requiring a formal agreement with AGL. This could take the form of a license agreement, where BioA pays royalties for using SFT technology, or a contracting model, with AGL providing installation and services under BioA’s umbrella.

By utilising the nutrients in reclaimed water, farmers can reduce their spending on fresh water and mineral fertilisers while also minimising soil contamination and the associated costs. Additionally, lowering water and fertiliser use is likely to promote healthier plants, ultimately enhancing crop productivity.

Avocados and mangos, downstream

TROPS’ value proposition offers consumers sustainably grown, high-quality avocados and mangos, catering to retailers seeking environmentally friendly fruit options. This proposition enhances the customer experience by improving fruit quality while helping retailers reduce scope 3 emissions. However, to maximise value, official certification is important to highlight the reduced use of water and mineral fertilisers in these fruits, setting them apart. While retailers already sell produce grown with reclaimed water, a certification or eco-label would create awareness and attract conscious consumers.

11.4.1 Customer segments

The business model offers four value propositions which provide value for different customer segments, as described in the **Table 39** below.

Table 39: Customer segments - Axarquía pilot region

Customer segments	
Water reclamation plant (WRP) catering to public water authorities, municipalities, gardening/landscape/golf organisations and large irrigator communities	<p>Public water authorities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Require cost-effective solutions for converting wastewater into reclaimed water. • Face discharge taxes for untreated wastewater. • Need TT to comply with new regulatory requirements (Urban Wastewater Directive). <p>Municipalities, gardening/landscape organisations, golf Courses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need alternative water sources for irrigation, especially during dry periods. • Require cost-efficient water solutions for maintaining green spaces. • Struggle with high water costs and risk of water scarcity affecting green areas.

	<p>Large irrigator communities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Need reliable water sources, particularly during droughts.• Seek nutrient-rich reclaimed water to reduce fertiliser costs.• Need to invest in water reclamation systems for self-sufficiency.
<p>Smart Fertigation Tool (SFT) catering to individual farmers and farming cooperatives.</p>	<p>Individual farmers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Need tools to optimise water and nutrient use for improved crop yield.• Require cost-effective solutions for water and fertilisers.• Seek ways to reduce dependency on mineral fertilisers and well water.• Interested in technologies that help improve farm productivity and sustainability. <p>Farming Cooperatives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Need solutions to optimise resource use and improve efficiency across multiple farms.• Seek ways to reduce overall farming costs, especially related to water and fertiliser.• Look for tools that can enhance collective profitability and sustainability.• Require investments that benefit all cooperative members, reducing individual financial risks.
<p>Water reclamation and joint fertigation services catering to irrigation communities, and farming cooperatives</p>	<p>Irrigation Communities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Need tailored irrigation systems that optimise water use and nutrient management for multiple members.• Seek cost-effective, collective solutions that benefit all members of the community.• Require flexibility in system design to meet diverse agricultural needs (e.g., crops, irrigation systems).• Interested in reducing the financial risk by sharing resources and investments among community members. <p>Farming Cooperatives</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Need systems that can improve resource efficiency and increase farm productivity across their entire cooperative.• Focus on cost savings, particularly related to fertiliser use and water consumption.• Interested in tools that improve sustainability and profitability for all cooperative members.• Look for collective investments that can drive long-term benefits and improve operational efficiency.
Mangos and avocados catering to food retailers and supermarkets	Food Retailers and Supermarkets <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Need products to meet consumers who demand environmentally better produce.• Seek to differentiate their offerings with high-quality fruits that have a reduced environmental impact.• Interested in certifications that prove the sustainability of their products, helping to attract environmentally conscious consumers.• Want access to environmental data to support sustainability claims and enhance their image with consumers and stakeholders.• Looking for suppliers that can provide consistent quality and sustainability, which aligns with their marketing and corporate values.

Water reclamation plant (WRP) catering to public water authorities, municipalities, gardening/landscape/golf organisations and large irrigator communities

Public water authorities

The primary customer segment for the WRP is public water authorities with no existing TT solution, who are willing to upgrade existing municipal WWTPs with TT to produce reclaimed water. This includes WWTP who has secondary treatment but lacks a TT, and WWTPs without any wastewater treatment in small settlements.

Water authorities are responsible for providing clean water, facilitate the use of well-water for irrigation, and treat effluent from urban areas, and either dispose of it, or use it for production of reclaimed water for agricultural purposes.

Public water authorities will have different needs and preferences related to TT. Some will manage an established WWTP already providing primary and secondary treatment,

while other authorities will completely lack wastewater treatment solutions (e.g., for a small settlement).

Public water authorities are bound to comply with regulation and through the Urban Wastewater Directive, public authorities must conduct TT, which ultimately expands the potential customer segment.

Municipalities, gardening/landscape organisations, golf courses, etc.

Municipalities and organisations managing green spaces, like parks and golf courses, need alternative water sources, especially during droughts. The WRP can supply reclaimed water for irrigation, keeping green areas hydrated even in water-scarce periods. However, the high upfront investment required may limit the ability of smaller municipalities to adopt this solution.

Large irrigator communities

Finally, a target group for the WRP is large irrigator communities willing to acquire a WRP to treat secondary treated effluent from an existing WWTP and produce reclaimed water themselves.

Individual farmers often belong to larger groups known as irrigation communities (Hoogesteger et al. 2023), making these communities another important target user. Since smaller irrigation communities will most likely not be able to invest in a decentralised WRP, the most beneficial and efficient option for such a community will be for the plant to be installed at a centralised treatment facility. However, larger communities might have the capacity for such an investment to be profitable for members of the community. With a decentralised plant, the communities will be able to acquire secondary treated wastewater from their local WWTP and treat it into reclaimed water themselves. In this way, they will obtain both an alternative source of water (especially valuable in areas prone to droughts), and a source of nutrients to substitute mineral fertilisers.

It must be mentioned that there are different ways of structuring such an investment. E.g., one local irrigation community have purchased their own tertiary treatment system and have reached an agreement with AXA to provide them with secondary treated wastewater at no cost, because they avoid discharging it to the environment. Similar models have been introduced outside the Spanish region, where treated wastewater is distributed to agricultural organisations for free (Otoo et al. 2018). Hence, such a model could be viable to finance the WRP in decentralised locations, but it will depend on the specific context.

Smart Fertigation Tool (SFT) catering to individual farmers and farming cooperatives

Individual farmers and farming cooperatives

The SFT is targeted at farmers at both individual and cooperative levels. Farmers cultivate their agricultural land by managing their plants and soil to meet the right agronomic conditions for them to grow and produce yield in the form of crops. The SFT allow the farmer to apply the optimal amount of water and nutrients, by measuring the conditions of the plants and soil. The technology can be applied in farms receiving reclaimed water, making it an option for both conventional and organic individual farmers.

TROPS, as a leading cooperative in the production and commercialisation of avocados and mangoes, can play a key role in promoting the use of the SFT once its effectiveness is validated. In this scenario, individual farmers would assume the investment cost, either independently or with support from TROPS. This support could include assistance in identifying financing mechanisms or managing access to national or international subsidies (e.g. digitalisation aid, FEDER funds⁶, etc.).

Alternatively, TROPS may consider covering the investment directly on behalf of its members. However, this approach would require a deeper analysis supported by more definitive data on the expected costs and benefits of the system.

It is worth noting that some farmers are reluctant to use reclaimed water due to concerns about salinity, particularly for sensitive crops like avocados and mangoes. High salinity can accumulate in the soil over time, leading to long-term negative effects on crop health. Therefore, for these farmers to be considered a viable customer segment, reclaimed water must be compatible with well water. This requires the installation of a mixing unit⁷, which has already been implemented in the pilot region.

Water reclamation and joint fertigation services catering to irrigation communities, and farming cooperatives

Irrigation communities and farming cooperatives

The target customers for the Water reclamation and joint fertigation services include regional farmers in Axarquía, as well as other stakeholders in the irrigation community, such as golf courses, parks, and garden management organisations.

The key characteristic of this customer segment is their size, as these groups must have the capacity to make the investment worthwhile. Local irrigation communities are

⁶ In a Spanish context, the European Regional Development Funds (FEDER) has been included in the ERDF Spain Multi-Regional Operational Programme (SMOP) contributing to improve competitiveness and promote more intelligent growth supported by research and innovation, with particular attention to the needs and potential of SMEs (Ministerio de Ciencia n.d.)

⁷ The mixing unit consists of tanks storing reclaimed- and well-water, tanks for blending purposes, irrigation pumps, electronic devices, water probes, etc. The unit was installed to accommodate the various treatment options at the test site, where either trials using well water, reclaimed water, smart addition of mineral fertilisers, in different combinations are conducted

often composed of farmers who can benefit from shared resources and investments. Farming cooperatives like TROPS, which may already have the resources to invest in such systems, can also be targeted directly. For cooperatives, the main benefit lies in improved resource efficiency, reduced fertiliser costs, water resilience during droughts and enhanced productivity. While individual farmers benefit directly from the solution, cooperatives like TROPS gain from the overall increase in their members' success and profitability.

Additionally, a model where irrigation communities work with local water authorities to finance the system could also apply to this combined offering, making it more feasible for larger groups.

Mangos and avocados catering to food retailers and supermarkets

Food retailers and supermarkets

TROPS already sell avocados and mangos to food retailers and supermarkets both nationally, and internationally. While mainstream retailers and supermarkets represent the primary target group, sustainability-oriented chains serve as an especially interesting segment, as the SFT enables them to offer end-consumers high-quality fruit grown with reduced water usage and lower chemical fertiliser input compared to crops without precision irrigation tools. However, adoption by such buyers would likely require third-party certifications and proof of traceable environmental benefit, which are not yet in place. It must also be acknowledged that sustainability requirements from international buyers vary significantly, and that reclaimed water use is not universally seen as a competitive advantage.

Nevertheless, the data obtained through the SFT contains a potential to strengthen the buyer-seller relationship between TROPS and its clients by providing key environmental data, increasingly requested by some supermarkets. To fully capitalise on any sustainability claims made using SFT-generated data, an employed third-party certification must be aligned with private certification schemes such as GLOBALG.A.P.⁸, LEAF Marque⁹, or organic labels.

⁸ GLOBALG.A.P. standards are designed to foster the global adoption of more responsible farming practices. Audits are conducted using methods such as reviewing documentation, conducting interviews, and performing on-site observations. When the criteria are fulfilled, the producer or producer group is awarded certification (GlobalG.A.P. n.d.)

⁹ LEAF Marque certification builds on the principles of Integrated Farm Management (IFM) – a whole farm approach utilizing modern technology and traditional methods to deliver prosperous farming enriching the environment and engaging the local communities (LEAF n.d.)

11.4.2 Customer relationships

The following section explores the customer relationships with each of the above-mentioned customer segments that must be established for the success of the business model building on insights related to existing customer relationships of the partners.

Water reclamation plant (WRP)

The relationship between BioA and its customers are mainly based on personal assistance relationship while it also contains co-creation characteristics. Installing a WRP requires collaboration with the client from the beginning of the relationship for the system to be customised to the needs of the client based on the existing condition of the WWTP. This co-creation will allow the solutions to be adapted to the quality demanded for treatment, the volumes to be treated, etc.

Having installed a WRP, the relationship will often be based on subcontracting where technical staff from BioA performs maintenance and different water engineering services, showcasing an automate service relationship. In other cases, BioA will also be able to educate the client about how to operate and maintain such a facility enabling them to support themselves.

Smart Fertigation Tool (SFT)

Generally, the services offered in relation to the SFT operate in an almost fully automated manner, requiring little to no direct interaction with the client. However, depending on the service offered, AGL provides personal assistance and maintenance in case either the hardware or software component fails. Thus, the direct interaction with the customer is minimal following installation. This creates a seamless experience that provide customers with necessary means to use the system without much support.

Water reclamation and joint fertigation services

The customer relationships that must be built for the combined offering to succeed will contain elements from both BioA's and AGL approaches to manage clients. Co-creation between BioA and the customer is needed to customise the solution depending on the quality and volumes demanded by the client. Likewise, personal assistance from the technical staff of BioA will be required to maintain the plant. Combined with the automated relationship between AGL and the client, the combined offering will build on a mix of dedicated personal assistance with BioA employees, and once up and running, a seamless automated experience created by AGL.

Avocados and mangos

The relationship between TROPS and their food retail clients are highly dependent on trust and quality products. Some retailers are increasingly focused on the sustainability of their value chain, meaning that showcasing positive environmental practices may become an important part of building a strong relationship with these food retailers.

Thus, the future data on reduced water footprints and environmental impact can enhance loyalty and collaboration with clients. Additionally, the resources spent on building a brand associated with high quality products contain the possibility that end-consumers create a pull-effect of TROPS' products, thereby possibly enhancing the relationship with retail clients. A third-party certification could support this effect.

11.4.3 Environmental value creation flows

BioA and AGL, as the technology and fertiliser providers, enable a flow of environmental value creation across partners, including value creation for internal partners such as AGL, TROPS and AXA as well as external partners such as farmers, WWTPs, communities and the region. Each partner plays a role in the circular value chain and thereby in reducing environmental impacts through their interconnected activities.

A detailed quantification of the agroecological and environmental impacts including analyses of local water, reclaimed water, soil, etc, will be carried out by CET, a water research centre, in collaboration with partners from Work Package 2 (task 2.3).

From BioA/AGL to TROPS and farmers

Some farmers in Spain are already using reclaimed water, but there is an existing issue where such farmers apply mineral fertilisers on top of the reclaimed water. This leads to overuse of fertilisers, and contamination of the soil which subsequently has negative impacts on the quality of the soil and the health of the plants. By gaining information on the activity of the roots, the farmers will obtain valuable knowledge on how much nutrients to apply to their fields and thereby reduce the nutrient pollution of the soil and increase the yield of their crops.

By employing the SFT, over-application of nitrogen and other nutrients are prevented which can contaminate the soil and groundwater. Agricultural areas that apply more fertiliser than necessary often experience increased levels of nitrates and phosphates, which degrade groundwater quality and posing risks to local ecosystems and drinking water supplies.

From BioA/AGL to AXA

Nutrients from secondary treated wastewater are currently discharged to the sea, negatively impacting the aquatic environment. This issue is eliminated by producing reclaimed water through TT. This value creation flow arises directly from the WRP provided by BioA and is also facilitated by the AGL who contribute to increased adoption of reclaimed water through their SFT.

From BioA/AGL/TROPS to the region of Andalusia

Facilitating the use of reclaimed water for irrigation will have beneficial side effects, including increased water flow in regional rivers, improved groundwater levels, and

enhanced conditions of nearby wetlands and natural habitats. Additionally, monitoring the nutrients released into the soil may help detect potential leaching into the groundwater.

The TTP provided by BioA mitigates outflows of secondary treated water and therefore reduces the nutrients and nitrogen released to the Mediterranean Sea. By reclaiming nutrients, the loop from fork to farm is closed, reducing both the extraction of phosphorus and the production of energy intensive nitrogen fertilisers, thereby providing a positive environmental impact. The pilot anticipates a great reduction in the use of mineral fertilisers with the use of reclaimed water of the SFT.

Potential environmental negative impacts of the business model are expected to stem primarily from the energy required to build and establish the system. More specifically, these impacts are associated with constructing the WRP, building the pipe infrastructure, and operating the plant. Efforts by BioA are underway to explore the use of renewable energy to counteract this.

Furthermore, high salinity levels in the fertigation water may accumulate in soils, disrupting beneficial soil microorganisms that are critical for nutrient cycling and soil fertility. This may impair plant growth, which is why managing salinity levels in the irrigation water is essential to safeguard soil health and maintain sustainable agricultural practices which is a key focus for the pilot. Salt intrusion occurs when saltwater enters the pipes delivering reclaimed water. This phenomenon is highly context dependent. For instance, farmers located in areas like the P2Green test site (close to coastline and seawater intrusion issues due to poor quality of sewer and collection infrastructure) will be more prone to salinity problems, while it might not be an issue in a different location. While inefficient management of salinity levels poses a potential environmental and agricultural threat, introducing a mixing unit provides a solution to this issue. However, for the future scaling of the business model, the implementation of an alternative desalination method, whether a mixing unit or another desalination system, will only be considered, if necessary, based on local conditions, as such it is not a default requirement.

Moreover, without using the SFT, farmers risk over application of nutrients, leading to negative impacts similar to those observed with conventional fertilisation. Overuse of nutrients beyond plant needs result in excess nutrients flowing into the environment, negatively affecting soil and water ways. By using SFT and controlling nutrients, the amounts supplied in excess can be reduced. Failing to control and monitor nutrients in reclaimed water is estimated¹⁰ to result in an excess of:

¹⁰ Estimations are based on calculations conducted by BioA.

- **Avocado crops:**

- 50 kg N/ha*year
- 30 kg P₂O₅/ha*year
- 78 kg K₂O/ha*year
- 225 kg CaO/ha*year.

- **Mango crops:**

- 110.12 kg N/ha*year
- 57.96 kg P₂O₅/ha*year
- 168.08 kg K₂O /ha*year
- 478.17 kg CaO/ha*year

11.5 Value creation and delivery

11.5.1 Key activities

The value chain includes recovery of wastewater, production of reclaimed water, fertigation control, and sales of fruits. The key activities are separated into upstream, production and downstream activities, with the reclamation of wastewater and operation of the SFT as the core focus.

Upstream

The upstream activities are mainly performed by AXA who undertakes operations related to collection of sewage and the first rounds of treatment that initiates the stream of nutrients that circulates in the value chain.

Production

Key production activities are those required to produce reclaimed water and prepare it for fertigation. This involves treatment of secondary treated effluent, and the operation of the SFT. This is performed in conjunction between BioA and AGL.

Besides the irrigation tank where reclaimed water, mineral fertilisers or well water can be added depending on the needs of crops, the mixing unit installed at the test site has shown to be valuable in reducing occasional issues with high salinity levels of the reclaimed water. As described earlier, scaling in areas without salinity problems may not require the operation of a mixing unit.

The operation of the SFT is similarly considered a key activity within the production due to its essential role in facilitating the optimised use of water and nutrients for irrigation. When installed, these processes will function automatically, apart from the calibration of the system where actions from AGL is needed.

Downstream

When the reclaimed water is released from the tank, key downstream activities involve fertigation and measuring nutrient levels using the SFT. After crop cultivation, subsequent stages rely on TROPS' established distribution network, where fruits are sold to retail customers and then distributed to end consumers of avocados and mangos. A key activity in this respect is the marketing efforts conducted by TROPS, such as advertising, which create a pull effect among end consumers that resonates with TROPS' brand.

Table 40 below, shows the key activities provided upstream, in production and downstream.

Table 40: Key activities - Axarquía pilot region

Key activities	Description of key activities
Key upstream activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Collection of sewage from the municipality of Algarrobo and nearby municipalities (AXA) 2. Primary and secondary treatment of raw wastewater (AXA) 3. Transportation of secondary treated effluent through a pump via pipelines into the WRP (AXA)
Key production activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Design of customised solutions for the WRP (BioA) 5. TT of secondary treated effluent (BioA) 6. Maintenance of water reclamation plant (BioA) 7. Transportation of reclaimed water through a pump via pipelines into tanks of irrigation users (BioA) 8. Measurements of the nutrient content of the reclaimed water by sensors installed in the irrigation tank (AGL) 9. Measurement of the nutrient levels at the roots of the plants by sensors installed in the soil (AGL) 10. Customised and automatic remote-controlled dilution or added dosage of mineral fertiliser to the irrigation tank based on the Decision-Support System (DSS) (AGL) 11. Regular calibration of the DSS (AGL)

Key downstream activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 12. Fertigation of mangos and avocados (TROPS) 13. Cultivation and management of crops (TROPS) 14. Harvest and distribution of mangos and avocados for retail customers (TROPS) 15. Counselling of farmers on crop management (TROPS) 16. After sales technical service advise of WRPs (BioA) 17. Marketing and advertising practices related to sustainable agriculture (TROPS)
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11.5.2 Key resources

The key resources are listed in **Table 41** and elaborated below.

Table 41: Key resources - Axarquía pilot region

Key resources	Description of resources	Status
Physical resources	Production facility	Available through BioA / AGL
	Piping infrastructure	Available at testing side - availability are site specific
	Existing WWTP	Availability depends on geographic location
	Irrigation tank	Available through BioA
	Mixing unit	Available through BioA
Human resources	Water engineering and technical experts	Available through BioA and AXA
	Commercial personnel	Available BioA + AGL
	Developers and software engineers	Available through AGL

	Farming advisors	Available through TROPS
	Communication specialists	Short-term available through CET
	Water scientists	Short-term available through CET
Intellectual resources	Proprietary knowledge of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water treatment, design, installation, operation, etc. Software- and algorithm development Effective farming practices Data to improve farming practices. 	Available through BioA Available through AGL Available through TROPS Future availability
	Partnerships <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Farming cooperative structure Subcontractors for plumbing and electricity Formalised partnership agreements 	Available through TROPS Available -third party Future availability
	Brand equity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> TROPS BioA 	Available
	Customer databases <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Client database of AGL Distribution network for retail clients 	Available Future availability
	Intellectual property aspects for the SFT	Not yet defined
	Financial resources	EU-funds (i.e., P2Green project)

	Regional funds from Provincial Government of Malaga (i.e., Diputación de Málaga)	Available
	Funds from the established businesses in the pilot region	Available

Physical resources

The most essential physical resources to produce reclaimed water for fertigation is the technologies of the WRP possessed by BioA and the SFT that refers to the IoT connection of electronic sensors installed in water irrigation tanks and the agricultural soil to support the Decision Support System software belonging to AGL. While these physical resources can potentially be located at different geographical locations, they are considered to jointly represent the production facility of the reclaimed water.

Another essential physical resource required to distribute reclaimed water from the WRP onto the agricultural fields is the piping infrastructure. This infrastructure is owned by the regional government, and new pipelines must be built to distribute reclaimed water to locations without current access to this as an irrigation resource.

Naturally, the existing WWTPs owned by water authorities like AXA, and the piping infrastructure that connects it with urban areas, represent key physical resources to conduct the first rounds of wastewater treatment. Additional key physical resources are the drrigation tank provided by BioA for storage and customisation of reclaimed water, and currently also the mixing unit (in this project installed in collaboration between BioA, TROPS and AGL) needed to decrease the salination levels of the reclaimed water as mentioned in key activities' section.

Human resources

BioA provides engineers and technical experts who are essential for designing, planning and operating the WRP. BioA's commercial personnel are essential when reaching out to potential customers and participating in regional, national and European networks and associations to promote the solutions. Additionally, developers and software engineers from AGL are important to facilitate the efficient use of the SFT, while TROPS expert employees are key to advise farmers in relation to improve existing farming practices, thereby supporting the adoption of reclaimed water and measurements at the individual farm level.

In the project period of P2Green, CETAQUA (CET) also provide key human resources but only for a limited period. However, it cannot be neglected that these personnel, including scientists and communication specialists, are key in analysing data from the project to improve the technologies, and facilitate workshops to communicate about the solutions.

Intellectual resources

While neither BioA nor AGL possess patents for their technologies, other intellectual resources are essential for the business model. Proprietary knowledge and experience with designing, installing and maintaining water treatment solutions and conduct technical-economic feasibility studies to select the most appropriate solutions for the customer are important components of the value propositions. The same goes for the knowledge required to develop and operate algorithms for fertigation. TROPS also possess years of experience within effective farming practices and with an operative business model, they will gain access to valuable agricultural data which can be further used to improve their practices and enhance the efficient delivery of fruits.

Another vital intellectual resource is the brand equity of TROPS. In the latest years, TROPS have invested heavily in communication and advertising to increase the likelihood that consumers will associate the brand with products of high quality and sustainable farming practices. This help bring legitimacy to all partners in the business model.

Lastly, TROPS possess an established customer database consisting of retail clients already offering fruits grown by their farmers which can be essential to utilise when scaling the production of fruits grown with reclaimed water. In the same vein, AGL are already operating in Almeria with a similar technology thereby owning an established customer database which could be essential when acquiring future customers while BioA can provide operational guarantees based on a track record of more than 20 years and with more than 80 international cooperation projects to date.

Financial resources

The partners are supported by various financial resources, including EU funds, such as the P2Green project. Additionally, regional funds from the Provincial Government of Malaga (i.e., Diputación de Málaga) contribute to the partnership. These funds cover a range of expenses, including personnel costs and the design and development of the treatment solution. They are also used for the installation, operation, and maintenance of the technologies involved. Furthermore, funds are directed towards the purchase of equipment and components necessary for the project, as well as sub-contracting specific tasks, such as civil works, electricity and plumbing services, and other activities related to construction and development.

11.5.3 Key partners

The key partners in the Spanish pilot region are:

Axaragua (AXA) is the public water authority of Algarrobo, responsible for operating the municipal WWTP and operating wastewater treatment and drinking water purification. The organisation manages five WWTPs in the region, collecting effluent from 14 urban areas.

AXA manages the treatment of effluent, with the Algarrobo plant providing secondary treated wastewater, which retains valuable nutrients for reuse in the circular value chain. In addition to wastewater management, AXA also manages the supply of drinking water and well water for both residents and irrigators and receives payments through water tariffs.

Bioazul (BioA) is an engineering and technology consulting company that develops eco-innovative solutions, with a particular focus on water treatment and reuse. BioA acts as the coordinator among the pilot partners involved in the business model and serves as the technology provider for the WRP treating municipal wastewater from the Algarrobo facility into nutrient optimised irrigation water tailored for agricultural applications.

BioA has already reached a mature stage after 20 years of operation, independent of P2Green. Importantly, its profitability does not rely on this proposed business model. Instead, the business associated with P2Green and its proposed revenue streams would serve as a complementary addition to the company's existing profitability but are not essential for its economic success.

Agualytics (AGL) is a technology company, providing technologies to measure and manage data from agricultural fields. In P2Green, AGL oversees the algorithmic development that will measure N, P, and K concentrations in the reclaimed water and analyse data from sensors installed in the soil of agricultural fields. AGL will both provide electronic sensors and software in the form of a Decision Support System to analyse plant and soil nutrient needs providing customers with valuable insights to optimise fertigation processes by reducing chemical fertiliser use.

TROPS (TROPS) is a farmer cooperative representing over 3,000 farmers in the Axarquía region where TROPS generates revenue through the commercialisation of its members' fruit. As agronomical advisor in the project, TROPS investigates the impact of nutrient-rich reclaimed water on crops and ensures that the farmers' interests and needs are represented in the development of the technologies. TROPS are specialised in the cultivation of avocados and mangoes and are essential to create awareness of crops grown with reclaimed water. The cooperative structure of TROPS allows resources, knowledge, and risks to be shared among its members, thereby acting as a gatekeeper to potential customers of the solutions offered in the business model, since the collaborative structure will allow larger investments to be undertaken if it benefits the cooperative.

CETAQUA (CET) is an R&D technological centre constituted as a nonprofit foundation and acts as the water research and scientific partner in the business model. Their role includes analysing data collected from samples of reclaimed water, soil, plant leaves and fruits to ensure that the reclaimed water meets the necessary quality standards for agricultural purposes. Additionally, they will provide insights the groundwater impacts of

using reclaimed water. Their scientific supporting role entails that they will only play a part in the preparation stages and not when the business model becomes operative.

Table 42 provides a list of key suppliers, distributors, and other key stakeholders for the Spanish pilot.

Table 42: Key Partners - Axarquía pilot region

Resources provided or activity performed	
Key suppliers	<p>Irrigation communities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In events of elevated salinity resulting from seawater intrusion into the sewage system, it is necessary to dilute the reclaimed water with well water. Currently, this water is collected from a well owned by the local irrigation community. <p>Mineral fertiliser suppliers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Suppliers of mineral fertilisers are critical to the business model as addition to the reclaimed water is essential to complement the nutrient content. TROPS has established contractual agreements with different fertilising companies. <p>Equipment suppliers for the WRP</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Suppliers of equipment are essential to be able to scale WRP's. Currently, suppliers of electric equipment, pipes, and other infrastructure are well-known, while suppliers of technological equipment lack contractual agreements. <p>Equipment suppliers of SFT components</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Suppliers of electronical sensors and software.
Key distributors	<p>Regional government</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishment of new piping infrastructure for reclaimed water from treatment facilities to irrigation users. Extensive investments are required, with the Regional Government of Andalusia having already initiated parts of roll out. <p>Food retailers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marketing and distribution of avocados and mangos to end-consumers. Many retailers already sell fruits grown with reclaimed water; however, this is often non-visible at the point of purchase.
Other key partners	<p>Third-party certification body</p>

- Third-party certification bodies are considered necessary to develop a certification about reclaimed water use in agriculture. The certification should contain information on the reduced environmental impacts and possibly contain elements such as 'circular economy', or 'zero-kilometre' principles to demonstrate its improved ecological footprint and create more positive perceptions of reclaimed water use to increase social acceptance and possibly the willingness to pay by end-consumers.

11.5.4 Channels

The key channels of the Spanish business model are divided into the following channel categories:

- Channels that are vital to raise awareness about the WRP, the fertigation tool, a possible combined offering, and fruits grown from reclaimed water.
- Channels that are vital to enable customers of the WRP and fertigation tool to evaluate its functionality.
- Channels that are vital to distribute and allow customers to purchase the products and services.
- Channels that are vital for the delivery of the value proposition along with after-sales support.

Raising awareness

When promoting and raising awareness around the WRP, the business model will rely on the personnel of BioA who are dedicated to commercial activities. This includes advertising, and reaching out to clients, and taking part in relevant networks and associations at regional, national and European levels to promote the system.

Due to the low maturity of the technology provided by AGL, commercial agreements for the fertigation tool have not been reached with customers, yet. However, AGL owns established sales channels of other technologies already being used by farmers in Almeria. This channel could potentially be used to raise awareness of the fertigation tool among their established customers.

It must also be noted that AXA, owns an online channel in which citizens can obtain information about their efforts in the project. Additionally, TROPS owns a communication channel towards the end-consumers of fruit through the retailers. This channel is vital for awareness creation and can potentially be utilised to promote the use of reclaimed water in farming practices.

Enabling evaluation

CET contributes with an important evaluation channel to the business model. As a research centre, CET provides analyses of environmental impacts, and insights into the functionality and safety of the reclaimed water through samples of water, soil, and fruits. The results of these analyses are essential for customers – farmers, retailers or WWTPs - to enable them to evaluate the performance of the reclaimed water.

To enable end-consumers of fruit to evaluate the value proposition related to avocados and mangos grown with reclaimed water, certifications play a vital role. Currently, eco-certifications for fruits do not take the origin of the water used for irrigation into account. This means that end-consumers are not able to evaluate the fruits from an environmental perspective that consider the use of water. Thus, there is an existing need for an official third-party certification to be included as an externally owned evaluation channel of the business model.

Purchase and distribution channels

The dedicated personnel of BioA responsible for commercial activities, along with AGL's existing relationships with farmers in Almeria, represent vital purchase channels for both the WRP, and the fertigation tool. These channels will also become vital for the value proposition of the combined offering, meaning that individual sales activities of either BioA or AGL contain the potential to benefit the other party.

For the fruits and vegetables, TROPS facilitates an important channel through their existing relationships with Spanish retailers. As a farming cooperative, TROPS undertakes the sales activities of the individual farmers, meaning that the business model depends on the buyer-seller relationships with the retailers to be well-functioning. Since the purchase and distribution channel of retailers are externally owned the margins on the fruits must be divided in the relationship with TROPS.

Value delivery and after sales support

When installing the treatment system, BioA works directly with the customer and provide essential water engineering and design solutions depending on the specific installation. Additionally, BioA normally establishes a maintenance contract that entails maintenance and service of the system to support the customer after installation.

11.5.5 Organisational value creation flows

Collaboration is the overarching key organisational value that is determining for the success of the circular solution. However, collaboration also requires an extra effort from the partners to be able to succeed with the circular solution. Collaboration is operationalised through the following value creation flows among the partners:

Collaboration (between all partners)

A fundamental parameter for the execution of the Spanish pilot is the close collaboration between the partners. The joint value creation of the circular value chain needs both the reclaimed water, the fertigation technology, the impact assessment, the crops and the agricultural management for the successful performance of the circular business model.

Knowledge sharing

The partners of the pilot point towards the fact that collaboration among the partners connects the pieces of the circular value chain, and that the partner organisations cannot make the circular business model happen if they did this independently. The partners of the pilot are in dialogue through regular meetings to share knowledge across organisations, that act as valuable input to their respective business needs. In their role as a technology provider, AGL must obtain knowledge on the characteristics of the reclaimed water being delivered to their customers. Knowledge related to the agronomic impact on crops agronomically, and the specific legal requirements of the water, is essential to improve the technology where knowledge sharing creates the right support for all partners to utilise their expertise for the benefit of the joint value creation.

Synergy effects

The partners note that collaboration within a project foster increased familiarity among participants, as ongoing interactions help them get to know one another better and uncover new capacities within each organisation, ultimately creating opportunities for synergy.

In this context, current collaborations link expertise across the different organisations. These synergy effects are specifically evident in the relationship between BioA and AGL. The full value of the reclaimed water provided by BioA depends on the fertigation tool developed by AGL, since it provides information on relevant nutrient levels. Only when farmers gain information on nutrient levels in the water and soil will they obtain the full value of the reclaimed water provided by BioA. Similarly, the full value of AGL's SFT depends on the TT at BioA's WRP for the reclaimed water to reach the quality required for fertigation. As an additional beneficial effect of these technologies, along with adoption of tertiary treatment in local WWTPs, farmers gain resilience during drought periods by reducing reliance on well water, while also decreasing dependence on mineral fertilisers.

One possibility derived from this organisational value creation flow lies in combining the offerings entailing that e.g., BioA will be able to offer the entire irrigation system, rather than only the WRP. However, a combined offering would require a formal agreement between the two organisations (elaborated under financial value creation flows).

Capacity building

Collaboration between the partners allows capacities to be built and strengthened at different stages of the circular value chain. The WWTP operated by AXA currently only

performs secondary treatment of wastewater, meaning that valuable nutrients go to waste when being discharged to the ecosystem. The decentralised tertiary treatment system of BioA can be adapted and customised to the established treatment plants based on the volumes of water and allows AXA to develop their wastewater treatment capacities. Another element of capacity building is related to the creation of new agricultural knowledge, facilitated by the fertigation tool of AGL. TROPS gain the potential to strengthen their farming practices when obtaining insights into optimal amounts of fertiliser to be used. Thereby, the collaboration between partners builds a platform for new capacities to be developed and existing capacities to be utilised in other areas.

Gatekeeping

Gatekeeping has been identified as a unique organisational parameter of the Spanish pilot region. In their role as a farmer cooperative, TROPS represent a network of potential users of reclaimed water. In this role, TROPS can facilitate contact and establish relationships with other customers, which is crucial to scale the use of reclaimed water and fertigation to more users.

11.6 Value capture

11.6.1 Revenue streams

The circular business model will capture value through different possible revenue streams consisting of technology sales, payments related to water tariffs, maintenance contracts, etc.

In many instances, the partners will be responsible for their own specific value capturing mechanisms and how they organise their revenue streams, while for some revenue streams it will depend on organisational agreements between the partners. The crucial element is that the revenue streams should be able to capture the value created by all partners, from wastewater treatment to sales of fruits in order for the CBM to be viable. Currently, no revenue streams exist within P2Green, meaning the following sections will be based on possible and envisioned revenue streams. Specific attention will be given to BioA and AGL in their roles of technology providers. The business model and revenue streams proposed in P2Green pilot need further maturity (e.g., development of the SFT) to be considered.

Table 43: Revenue streams - Axarquía pilot region

Revenue stream	Description
Reclaimed water tariffs	Payments of water tariffs represent a revenue stream of the business model since AXA receives payments of water tariffs from users, being households or irrigation communities, depending on the amount of water used.

	<p>When distributing water from their owned WWTP, AXA is responsible for charging water fees related to both well water and reclaimed water use.</p> <p>Currently, when users receive reclaimed water from the WWTP they must pay an average water tariff of 0,12 €/m³ against 0,05 €/m³ for well water (2025 prices). These tariffs reflect the costs of electricity, analysis, personnel, etc. This entails that reclaimed water is more expensive than well water, reducing the incentives to use reclaimed water. However, when well water is not available, the reclaimed water is utilised, establishing a revenue stream from users to AXA. How water tariffs may be addressed to support this revenue stream is explored further under the section “unique conditions in the Spanish context”.</p>
Sales of water reclamation plants (WRP)	<p>Sales of WRPs represent a critical revenue stream accounting for one out of three essential revenue streams related to the value proposition of the WRP, for the business model to be viable.</p> <p>The first part of the revenue stream will be based on traditional asset sale, where a transactional fee will be derived from selling the ownership rights of the physical treatment system. This is important to cover the costs related to its development. However, rent-based solutions where the ownership of the technology is kept by BioA, similarly poses as an opportunity to ensure recurring revenue from rent and maintenance contracts.</p>
Water engineering services	<p>Water engineering service fees are another critical element of the revenue streams related to the WRP. The services include engineering work related to the initial phase of the customer relationship and includes design of solutions, pre-piloting for demonstration, installation, commissioning, training and capacity building of customer, technical-economic feasibility study to select the most appropriate solution, and after-sales service advice. These service payments will be highly dependent on the needs of customers, preferably on a usage fee basis, where customers pay for their use of the intellectual properties of BioA.</p>
Subcontracts	<p>Lastly, subcontracts represent a critical mechanism to the revenue streams related to the WRP. This revenue stream build on different types of subcontracts, such as maintenance contracts where technical staff of BioA will regularly inspect the plant, or alternatively, operation</p>

	<p>contracts where technical staff is responsible for the functioning of the plant.</p> <p>These subcontracts are essential to ensure recurring revenue streams by selling continuous access to the technical services, in a subscription like model.</p>
Sales of Smart Fertilization Tools (SFT)	<p>Similar to the sales of the water reclamation technology, a critical element of the business model is to derive revenue from the sales of ownership rights to the physical components of the tool. This traditional asset sale will build 1/3 pillars of the revenue stream related to the SFT and ensure that AGL cover their costs for production of the tool.</p>
Subscription access to the decision support system	<p>The second essential revenue stream related to the SFT, is based on the decision support system consisting of a software connected to the electrical sensors installed in the soil. Moving from mere equipment production to also encompass software development, provides an opportunity to generate additional revenue from app subscriptions (Coates et al. 2020). Thus, to ensure recurring revenue, access to this system could be sold through subscription fees to allow users continuous access to the real-time data derived from the sensors.</p>
Supporting services	<p>Lastly, a revenue related to different supporting services of the SFT must be integrated to the business model. This includes a built-in contract with regular maintenance also poses an option to ensure recurring revenue and increase the likelihood that customers will use the services when needed.</p>
Collaborative offering	<p>Establishing a revenue stream based on the combination of the WRP and SFT rely on an efficient collaborative agreement to be formed. From earlier projects, AGL have experience related to adaptations of the SFT with other technologies primarily through application programming interfaces (APIs). This approach allows for a seamless interoperability of the different systems, typically facilitated by subscription-based licenses that grant the collaborating part access to specific data.</p> <p>Thus, such a revenue stream could be organised with e.g., BioA undertaking the direct relationships with the customers of the combined solution, based on their expertise in this area, and subsequently direct the payments received from asset- and service sales onto</p>

	<p>AGL for provision of access to the SFT. The exact license-payments depend on the specific agreement between the two parties.</p> <p>It must also be noted that, depending on the interests of both parties, other collaborative agreements involving deeper levels of integration could also be explored.</p>
Fruit sales	<p>Sales of fruits grown from reclaimed water facilitates flows of revenue from the food consumers and into the CBM. Based on positive indications from relevant stakeholders, showing a willingness to pay higher prices for more sustainably grown fruits, premium prices could be applied to enhance the financial viability of the business model. As mentioned earlier such premiums will require certification- or labelling schemes to be developed to increase the visibility of the sustainable characteristics of the fruit and thereby facilitate premium payments from more conscious consumers.</p>

11.6.2 Financial value creation flows

There are currently no financial value creation flows stemming between the partners in the Spanish pilot. In this system, all partners depend on the successful commercialisation of WRP and SFT to generate revenue and create financial value between each other, forming a mutually beneficial cycle.

Below are suggestions of how to create internal financial value creation flows between the partners in pilot.

Operationalising financial value creation flows between partners

From BioA / AGL to TROPS and farmers: Reduced costs and improved yields

Through monitoring agronomic levels in water and soil, users of the fertigation tool will obtain insights into the exact levels of nutrients needed by the crops. Farmers will therefore be able to limit the amount of conventional fertiliser and well-water applied to the fields, when substituting this with reclaimed water. Eventually, this will both save costs related to the procurement of these supplies but also result in increased health of plants through less contaminated soil. Subsequently, this increases productivity and yields of the farming operations according to the pilot region.

Between TROPS and BioA / AGL: Investments in WRP and SFT

The cooperative structure of TROPS allows resources, knowledge, and risks to be shared among its members, which fosters a collaborative environment aimed at maximising benefits for all involved. In one scenario of the business model, TROPS is a potential investor of the WRP and SFT. The returns on this investment will contribute to

the overall success and profitability of the cooperative, rather than being directly tied to specific individual farms. However, an alternative scenario is the event that the individual farmers themselves undertake the investment.

In continuation of the formal agreements proposed under organisational value creation flows, one option is to base the offering on a license agreement where AGL will act as a licensor that provides the intellectual property of the SFT to BioA. As a licensee BioA will pay fees, e.g., percentages of the revenue generated from the combined offering, for AGL. Another agreement could be based on a contracting model where AGL is contracted by BioA to deliver the value proposition of the SFT for customers. BioA will be viewed as the service provider of the combined offering, while AGL receives contract fees for the installation and services related to the SFT. While TROPS will obtain benefits mainly using the SFT, it must also be recognised that their contribution to the development of the tool's intellectual property pose as an argument to consider payments of revenue from the sales related to the SFT. However, whether a shared ownership agreement, where the technological partner can exploit and commercialise the tool, while TROPS receives a percentage of the profits is yet to be determined.

From BioA to AXA: Avoided discharge taxes

The WRP provided by BioA allows AXA to deliver secondary treated wastewater or effluents to other entities as an alternative to discharging it to the surrounding ecosystem. In this sense, AXA saves money on discharge taxes which they are currently paying, through an elimination of these tax payment requirements. Additionally, the government is currently subject to pay fines related to marine discharges, which is also reduced with the solution provided by BioA.

From BioA to AXA: Avoided costs

An additional value created by the WRP relates to the reduced costs of AXA's current treatment operations. Discharged wastewater must reach a certain quality to be discharged according to the Wastewater Discharge Regulations. Hence, AXA eliminates the costs related to removal of nutrients to comply with such parameters. These costs, however, are not estimated yet.

11.6.3 Cost structure

The cost structure of the Spanish pilot region is divided into capital expenditures (CAPEX) and operating expenses (OPEX) assuming full capacity utilisation.

Since the business model is still under development, the cost structure relies on assumptions and best estimates provided by the technology providers. This includes the need to extrapolate the costs of the TT.

The distribution of CAPEX and OPEX, as seen in **Table 44**, suggests a balance between high initial investments, CAPEX, covering the water reclamation reactors and mixing station equipment, while ongoing operational costs, OPEX, covers reactor

operations, salaries, and raw materials etc. in a scenario where the OPEX is accounted for as operating at capacity.

Table 44: Cost structure of CAPEX and OPEX - Axarquía pilot region

CAPEX / OPEX	Estimated amount (EUR)	Percentage of total expenditures (%)
Total CAPEX	63.556	51 %
Total OPEX	61.443	49 %
Total	124.999	100%

The water reclamation reactor (including design and engineering requirements) and mixing station equipment represent key resources essential for delivering the value proposition of reclaimed water for fertigation. The different cost items for both CAPEX and OPEX are included in **Table 45**. Due to confidentiality, the specific cost elements are not elaborated in monetary amounts.

Table 45: Cost items under CAPEX and OPEX – Axarquía pilot region.

Cost category	Key items
Capital expenditures (CAPEX)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water reclamation reactor (including design and engineering requirements) Mixing station equipment
Operating expenditures - Fixed (1 year)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reactor repair and maintenance (including personal costs, consumables, spare parts, and electricity costs) Reclaimed water FTE Mixing station FTE
Operating expenditures – Variable (considering 72 L wastewater treated) (1 year)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reclaimed water reactor operation (Considering personal costs, consumables, spare parts, and electricity costs) Reclaimed water pumping

- Mixing station and fertigation modules

The primary fixed and variable OPEX costs stem from the mixing station, reclaimed water reactor operations, and the mineral fertilisers required to enhance reclaimed water with the necessary nutrient levels.

Defining capital requirements is challenging for the pilot as it will depend on whether the developed SFT offers a favourable cost-benefit balance in the short term. Most small farmers are experienced as a price sensitive customer segment and therefore are reluctant to make significant investments in improvements unless the financial benefits are immediate and clear.

11.6.4 Financing

To identify suitable financing sources and the corresponding financing partners it is necessary to develop an overview of the necessary inherent investment needs, i.e. funding requirements of the Spanish pilot region.

The successful implementation of the circular business model in the Spanish pilot region, La Axarquía, requires significant financial resources to support infrastructure development, technological advancements, and operational costs. The funding requirements are driven by the region's unique environmental challenges, including water scarcity, nutrient pollution, and the transition towards more sustainable agricultural practices. The financial needs can be broadly categorised into capital expenditures (CAPEX) and operational expenditures (OPEX), with a focus on securing both public and private funding streams.

Funding requirements

In this chapter we provide an overview of the financing requirements of the key partners involved in the Spanish pilot region.

Implementing a circular nutrient optimised fertigation model generally requires financial investment in:

Table 46: Funding requirements in the stages of the CBM - Axarquía pilot region

Stage	
Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Construction and installation of decentralised TTP.• Expansion and modernisation of existing wastewater treatment facilities.• Installation of pipeline infrastructure for reclaimed water distribution.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Procurement of irrigation tanks and mixing units for fertigation.
Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research and development of SFT. • Deployment of monitoring sensors for water and soil nutrient concentrations. • Development of digital infrastructure and decision-support systems.
Operational costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintenance of treatment plants and fertigation equipment. • Energy consumption for water treatment and pumping systems. • Personnel costs for technical operations, software development, and advisory services. • Data analysis and environmental monitoring
Certification & market development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Certification of sustainably grown crops (avocados and mangos) irrigated with reclaimed water. • Marketing and promotion of circular agricultural products. • Capacity-building workshops and knowledge-sharing activities with farmers.
Financial incentives and support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subsidies for WWTP upgrades. • Incentives for farmers to adopt reclaimed water and fertigation technologies. • Public-private partnerships to support regional infrastructure investments.

Funding requirements will change and evolve throughout the different stages of the circular business model. The following **Table 47** provides an overview of the identified funding requirements as well as types of funding for each of the three development stages of the business model.

Table 47: Funding requirements - Axarquía pilot region

Stages of development			
Stage	Proof of concept & design development	Testing & pilot implementation	Scaling & optimisation

Corresponding TRL	1-4	5-7	8-9
Stage objective	Validate the feasibility of the business model concept and develop initial technological designs.	Pilot the integrated circular business model under real-world conditions.	Expand the business model across the region and optimise operational performance.
Investment in	R&D for TTP design, Algorithm development for SFT, Soil and water quality research, Preliminary certification assessments, Market research and feasibility studies, Start-up costs, concept validation, basic prototyping.	Installation of decentralised TTP, Deployment of SFT and sensor systems, Data collection and environmental impact assessments, Capacity-building workshops for farmers, Certification trials and regulatory compliance testing. Product development, pilot infrastructure, logistics.	Large-scale installation of decentralised treatment plants, Full-scale rollout of SFT, Development of certification schemes and eco-labels, Infrastructure for reclaimed water distribution networks, Marketing campaigns and product pro-motion, Ongoing maintenance and technical support.
Funds required	€500,000 – €1,000,000	€1,000,000 – €3,500,000	€3,500,000 – €10,000,000
Types of funding	Public & Private grants, innovation funds, and early-stage venture capital	Public-private partnerships, regional government subsidies, and pilot project grants	Green bonds, sustainability-linked loans, private investments, and revenue reinvestment
Requirements of financing partners	Strong founding Team, Large (growing) Market,	Proven Revenue Model, Clear path and timeline to profitability	Stable, profitable business with recurring Cash-flows

	Differentiated Product/Technology		
Position of Key Technology/ Partner at Start of P2GreenN		AGL & BioA (Irrigation System - TRL 6)	BioA (Membrane Bioreactor - TRL 9)
Target Position of Key Technology/ Partner			AGL & BioA (Irrigation System TRL 8) BioA (Membrane Bioreactor - TRL 9)

To successfully implement the circular business model, each key partner involved in the project requires specific funding allocations to fulfil their roles effectively. This chapter outlines the funding requirements for BioA, AXA, AGL, TROPS, and CET, detailing their financial needs for infrastructure, research, operational costs, and other essential expenditures.

BioA

BioA plays a crucial role in biotechnological advancements and organic waste valorisation. It requires funding for research and development to enhance biotechnological processes for waste treatment and biomass conversion. Investment is also needed for infrastructure, particularly in setting up and maintaining decentralised TTP. Additionally, resources must be allocated to regulatory compliance to ensure that all bioprocesses meet environmental and safety standards. Operational costs, including staffing, and technical services, necessitate financial support. Furthermore, integrating automation and digital monitoring systems requires additional funding to optimise efficiency and process control.

AXA

As a key water management partner, AXA requires financial support to upgrade existing wastewater treatment plants and improve water treatment infrastructure. Investment is essential for the development and implementation of circular water management systems, like pipeline infrastructure to connect reclaimed water to agricultural fields, ensuring efficient reuse and recycling of water resources. To improve sustainability, funding is needed for research and adoption of energy-efficient operations. Moreover, budget is also necessary for regulatory adherence to comply with EU and national wastewater treatment regulations. Lastly, AXA requires investment in workforce training and capacity-building programs to enhance the skills of its employees and ensure operational excellence.

AGL

AGL specialises in data-driven water quality monitoring and analysis, and its funding needs are centred around technological advancements. Investment is necessary for the acquisition and development of advanced sensor technology to improve real-time water quality monitoring. Additionally, funding is required to build and maintain data analytics infrastructure, enabling AI-driven platforms to support decision-making. R&D efforts also demand financial support to innovate and enhance predictive modelling for water management. As data security is a critical component, a budget must be allocated for cybersecurity and data protection. Moreover, AGL requires financial backing for pilot programs and field testing to deploy and refine new water quality monitoring technologies.

TROPS

TROPS, a key agricultural stakeholder, focuses on sustainable farming and resource efficiency. To promote regenerative agriculture and organic cultivation methods, investment in sustainable farming practices is essential, e.g. infrastructure for nutrient-rich reclaimed water distribution or in certification processes for sustainably grown crops. Water conservation initiatives require capital to develop efficient irrigation systems and implement rainwater harvesting techniques. Additionally, TROPS might require a budget for market expansion strategies, allowing for the development of new sustainable product lines and entry into new markets.

CET

CET, a leader in water research and technological innovation, requires funding for soil and water sampling, data analysis and validation of reclaimed water quality. Investment is necessary for the development of innovative water treatment solutions, including next-generation filtration and recycling systems. To influence regulatory frameworks and sustainability policies, CET requires financial support for policy and advocacy efforts. Additionally, knowledge transfer and training initiatives necessitate a budget to organise workshops, training programs, and the dissemination of best practices.

11.6.5 Barriers to entry and key readiness factors

Barriers to entry

This section outlines specific barriers to entry for potential investors considering the circular business model piloted in Spain. The focus is on barriers uniquely relevant to this innovative approach of utilising reclaimed water for agricultural fertigation and bio-fertiliser production.

Financial and economic barriers

- High initial investment: Establishing decentralised TTP, expanding pipeline infrastructure, and developing the SFT require significant capital. The lack of established financing models for such integrated systems increases the risk for investors.

- Pricing challenges: Reclaimed water tariffs are higher than the cost of illegal well water. Farmers' limited willingness to pay poses a challenge to revenue generation, making profitability uncertain.
- Extended payback periods: Due to slow market adoption and extensive capacity-building needs among farmers, the return on investment may be delayed.

Regulatory and compliance barriers

- Complex and evolving regulation: Compliance with evolving EU wastewater directives and nutrient management regulations requires ongoing investment in monitoring and reporting. Delays in adapting local regulations create further uncertainties.
- Lack of certification standards: There are no established certifications for crops grown with reclaimed water, limiting product differentiation and access to premium markets.

Technological and operational barriers

- Reliability and scalability of technology: The SFT is still in development, and its large-scale efficacy remains unproven. The dependence on precise data and reliable infrastructure adds complexity.
- Infrastructure limitations: The lack of comprehensive and reliable piping systems for reclaimed water distribution requires heavy public investment and coordination, delaying scalability.
- Risk of over-fertilisation: Without effective monitoring, the use of reclaimed water poses the risk of nutrient overload, damaging crops and surrounding ecosystems. Farmers' concerns over salinity levels in reclaimed water exacerbate this issue.

Market and adoption barriers

- Farmer resistance and market acceptance: Farmers are hesitant to use reclaimed water due to concerns about salinity. Market education and trust-building are time-consuming and costly.
- Uncertain consumer demand: The market for sustainably grown crops using reclaimed water is not fully established. Without certifications, consumer demand and willingness to pay a premium remain limited.

Coordination and stakeholder management

- Multi-stakeholder complexity: The model requires active collaboration among technology providers (BioA, AGL), public authorities (AXA), farmer cooperatives (TROPS), and research institutions (CET). Misalignment in objectives or communication gaps can delay implementation.
- Dependency on public support: Expansion of infrastructure relies heavily on regional government investment, making the business model vulnerable to changes in public policy and funding priorities.

By addressing these barriers, the pilot can help potential investors better understand the risks and the specific complexities associated with scaling this circular business model in the Spanish pilot region.

Key funding readiness factors

This section identifies the critical funding readiness factors that need to be addressed by the key partners - BioA, AGL, AXA, TROPS, and CET - to attract investment and ensure the successful scaling of the circular business model in the Spanish pilot region.

Clear and sustainable revenue streams

- BioA and AGL should solidify pricing models for the water reclamation technology and the SFT. This includes evaluating subscription-based models or licensing fees to secure consistent revenue.
- TROPS needs to explore premium pricing opportunities for sustainably grown crops and develop partnerships with eco-conscious retailers.
- AXA should assess the feasibility of adjusting reclaimed water tariffs to balance affordability for farmers while ensuring revenue generation.

Regulatory compliance and risk mitigation

- BioA and AXA must demonstrate compliance with EU wastewater directives and local regulations to reduce regulatory risks.
- CET should actively engage in research to validate the environmental and agronomic safety of reclaimed water, helping to secure certifications.

Market validation and stakeholder buy-in

- TROPS should strengthen farmer engagement through training and awareness programs to build trust and increase the adoption of reclaimed water.
- AGL needs to demonstrate the efficacy of the SFT through pilot projects and showcase its cost-saving potential to farmers.

Scalability and infrastructure readiness

- AXA and regional authorities need to commit to expanding piping infrastructure to ensure reliable access to reclaimed water.
- BioA should develop modular treatment systems that can adapt to varying scales and local conditions to facilitate scalability.

Financial strategy and risk management

- Developing an investment plan with a clear timeline, cost estimates, and projected ROI will enhance investor confidence.

11.6.6 Funding options and funding sources

Considering the funding needs of the key partners outlined in the previous chapter, this section examines appropriate funding sources and recommends potential financial partners for each stakeholder within the Spanish circular business model. Accordingly, the following funding sources and partners have been identified for the Spanish pilot.

Table 48: Funding options and funding sources - Axarquía pilot region

Key partner	Funding type	Funding partner	Description / Access requirements
BioA	Grants, Equity & Blended Finance	European Innovation Council (EIC) Accelerator	<p>Open to single start-ups and SMEs, individuals intending to launch an SME, and small mid-caps (for equity only).</p> <p>Applicants should: (i) have an innovative, game-changing product, service, or business model with the potential to create new markets or disrupt existing ones in Europe and globally.</p> <p>(ii) demonstrate ambition and commitment to scale up, seeking substantial funding where risks are too high for private investors alone.</p> <p>Grant Component: Up to €2.5 million for innovation activities.</p>

			Investment Component: €0.5 million to €15 million for market deployment and scale-up.
	Grants	Horizon Europe – Green Deal Call	<p>Open to a wide range of entities, including SMEs, large companies, research institutions, and public bodies.</p> <p>Projects must align with the European Green Deal priorities, focusing on areas like climate action, clean energy, and sustainable industry. Amount varies depending on specific call topics and project scopes.</p>
	Soft loans	CDTI (Centro para el Desarrollo Tecnológico Industrial, Spain)	<p>Spanish companies, particularly SMEs, engaged in technological development and innovation.</p> <p>Projects should be technically and financially viable, aiming to enhance the technological capacity of the company.</p> <p>Amount typically ranges from €175,000 to €3 million, depending on the project. Fixed interest rate, covering up to 85% of the project budget.</p>
	Participative, subordinated loans	ENISA (Empresa Nacional de Innovación, Spain)	<p>Spanish SMEs and start-ups with innovative business models.</p> <p>Companies must demonstrate financial viability and growth potential.</p> <p>Amount from €25k to €1.5m. Variable interest rates linked to the company's performance.</p>
AXA	Grants	European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)	Projects must contribute to economic development and cohesion in EU regions.

			<p>Applicants can include public authorities, NGOs, and private sector entities, depending on the specific program.</p> <p>Amount varies by region and project; typically co-finances up to 50% of project costs.</p>
	Long-term loans	European Investment Bank (EIB) Water Sector Loans	<p>Projects must be technically, economically, and financially viable.</p> <p>Open to both public and private sector promoters engaged in water infrastructure and related projects.</p> <p>Amount typically starts from €25m; can finance up to 50% of project costs.</p>
AXA, TROPS	Grants and subsidies	<p>Junta de Andalucía (i) Grants for Water Infrastructure Projects,</p> <p>(ii) Agricultural Modernisation Grants</p>	<p>Entities operating within the Andalusia region. Amount varies depending on the specific grant call and project scope.</p> <p>(i) Projects should address water scarcity, improve water infrastructure, or promote sustainable water management.</p> <p>(ii) Projects should aim to modernise agricultural practices, improve sustainability, or enhance competitiveness.</p>
AGL, CET	Grants	<p>Horizon Europe</p> <p>(i) Digital Solutions for Agriculture</p> <p>(ii) Water Management Research Projects</p>	<p>Is the EU's key funding programme for research and innovation. It tackles climate change, helps to achieve the UN's Sustainable Development Goals and boosts the EU's competitiveness and growth.</p>

AGL	Grants	Red.es (Spanish Government)	<p>Spanish SMEs seeking to implement digital solutions.</p> <p>Projects should aim to enhance digital capabilities, including smart agriculture technologies.</p> <p>Amount varies by program; can range from €5k to over €100k.</p>
		European Innovation Partnerships (EIP-AGRI)	<p>Consortia of farmers, researchers, advisors, and businesses collaborating on innovative agricultural projects.</p> <p>Projects should focus on practical solutions to agricultural challenges, including smart agriculture technologies.</p> <p>Amount varies by project and consortium; typically co-financed.</p>
TROPS	Grants	European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD)	<p>Farmers, cooperatives, and rural businesses.</p> <p>Projects should promote sustainable agriculture, environmental preservation, or rural community development.</p> <p>Amount varies by region and project; can co-finance up to 75% of eligible costs.</p>
	Loans	ICO (Instituto de Crédito Oficial, Spain)	<p>Spanish businesses and entrepreneurs.</p> <p>Projects should contribute to economic development, innovation, or sustainability.</p> <p>Amount depends on the specific line of credit; can range from €10k to several million euros.</p>

CET	Grants	Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation Grants	<p>Research institutions, universities, and innovative companies.</p> <p>Projects should focus on scientific research, technological development, or innovation.</p> <p>Amount varies by program and project; can range from €50k to several million euros.</p>
		EU LIFE Programme & CINEA (Circular economy and quality of life sub-programme)	<p>Public and private entities registered in the EU.</p> <p>Projects should address environmental conservation, climate change mitigation, or related areas.</p> <p>Typically co-finances up to 55% of eligible project costs; no specific minimum or maximum.</p>

BioA

Role: Development and installation of decentralised TTP, a crucial component of the circular business model to ensure water reclamation and nutrient recycling.

As BioA requires funding for both installation/equipment and R&D, it could continue using research and technological innovation grants from the EU (e.g. Horizon Europe) and local organisations (Spanish Centre for the Development of Industrial Technology – CDTI). In parallel, BioA could start seeking more conventional financings such as EIB concessional loans (for infrastructure projects with environmental benefits) or from Instituto de Crédito Oficial (ICO).

AXA

Role: Upgrading and expanding wastewater treatment plants to enable water reclamation and connection to agricultural irrigation systems.

As an existing municipal WWTP, AXA already has access to long-term loans from traditional financial institutions. This could be complemented by (i) additional subsidies from the Regional Government of Andalusia for example or the Spanish Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge (MITECO grants), (ii) public-private partnerships to leverage private capital, as well as (iii) the issuance of green

bonds which are ideal for long-term financing of environmentally beneficial infrastructure projects.

AGL

Role: Development and deployment of SFT to optimise nutrient use and water efficiency in agriculture.

As the company is already profitable, there are no acute financing needs. However, to support the scale-up of the company, it could envisage to seek funding for technological innovation from the Spanish Ministry for Science and Innovation or the Neotec Program (CDTI). Only in case a partnership is acceptable, the company could seek equity financing from venture capital focused on technology start-ups or private equity once the business has scaled-up (however we understand that shared ownership is currently not envisaged).

TROPS

Role: Distribution of nutrient-rich reclaimed water to farmers and promoting sustainable agricultural practices.

The cooperative structure of TROPS positions it as a central advisor which could find and share resources. TROPS could support its farmers by finding certification grants for circular agricultural products, use blended finance models or sustainability-linked loans by working with the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD), local development banks such as ICO or the Andalusian Agricultural Development Agency.

CET

Role: Scientific research, environmental impact assessments, and capacity-building activities.

CET is a non-profit research organisation and would therefore benefit from various research grants or collaborative R&D projects in the fields of water management and circular economy including from Horizon Europe, the EU LIFE Programme (in particular LIFE's Circular economy and quality of life sub-programme, through the implementing agency CINEA), or from the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC). Traditional financial instruments would not apply in this case.

To conclude, by aligning each company with the most suitable financing options, the Spanish pilot region can effectively support the implementation of a circular business model for sustainable water management and agriculture. BioA can leverage EU research grants and concessional loans for infrastructure and innovation, while AXA can benefit from traditional long-term loans, regional/national subsidies, public-private partnerships, and green bonds. AGL, already profitable, can seek innovation funding for scaling up, with venture capital as a future option if partnerships are considered.

TROPS can utilise certification grants, blended finance models, and sustainability-linked

loans to support farmers in adopting circular agricultural practices. Lastly, as a non-profit, CET is best positioned to secure research grants from EU and national programs. This strategic financial alignment ensures that each entity contributes effectively to the region's sustainability goals.

11.7 Unique conditions in the Spanish pilot

The following section will highlight unique conditions that are crucial for the potential success of the Spanish business model including urban wastewater legislation and water reuse schemes with a subsequent analysis of the potential cost responsibility for scaling the solution.

According to the new regulations¹¹ of the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (European Parliament & Council, 2024) Member States of the EU should promote the reuse of treated wastewater, particularly in regions facing water scarcity (like in Andalusia) while ensuring that it does not negatively impact the environment or human health (European Commission, n.d.c).

The directive enforces that urban wastewater treatment plants with a load of 150,000 population equivalents (p.e.) and above must implement TT by 2039, with phased compliance deadlines¹². Additionally, agglomerations of 10,000 p.e. and above discharging into eutrophication-sensitive areas must also implement TT, with deadlines extending to 2045 (European Parliament & Council, 2024). Given the Algarrobo plant, part of the Spanish P2Green pilot, processes wastewater equivalent to 23,970 people (p.e.), it falls under the directive's requirements if it discharges into eutrophication-sensitive areas.

In Andalusia, the availability of water heavily depends on surface water and groundwater, both of which are increasingly scarce during drought periods, there is a need to enhance water conservation and sustainability. This greatly favours the need to increase the use of reclaimed water. According to SuWaNu Europe, the use of reclaimed water is allowed in Andalusia as an irrigating source, supported by the Spanish law RD 1620/2007 (SuWaNu Europe. (n.d.c)). However, only 5.93% of the treated wastewater was reused as reclaimed water, with only 2.5% used in agriculture, while 27.8% in industry and 69.2% for irrigation of gardens and golf courses (SuWaNu Europe. (n.d.b)).

The 5.93% reuse rate in Andalusia is well below the Spanish national average of 10.43% and in contrast to 71.8% in Murcia and 47.5% in Valencia, the neighbours of Andalusia. Given that drought is the main risk of water shortage in Andalusia and only one-third of agricultural crops are irrigated (as of 2016), the potential for extending the irrigation of agricultural crops with reclaimed water is significant. As emphasised by

¹¹ Valid from 01/01-2025

¹² 30% by 31 December 2033, 70% by 31 December 2036, and all by 31 December 2039 (**Directive (EU) 2024/3019**)

SuWaNu Europe “Andalusia is technologically prepared, has a suitable national regulation, and enough practical experience to support and operate the water reclamation processes necessary to ensure safe and successful water reuse for agricultural irrigation.” (SuWaNu Europe. (n.d.b)). The high values of reused water in Murcia and Valencia are dependent on multiple factors. One being investments and involvement of regional governments (Nieto-López, Mudarra-Martínes, & Andreo, 2021). According to Euro Weekly News, 2024, Murcia has invested over 1.3€ billion in water purification, sanitation and urban water reuse over the past 30 years. And the regions are funding the WWTPs with fees from all water users included in their water bills. Valencia's EPSAR manages wastewater treatment and reuse within a broader water cycle framework, while Murcia's Esamur focuses specifically on sanitation and wastewater treatment, including reuse (Navarro Caballero, 2018; EPSAR. (n.d.)). In both regions, the fee is structured differently depending on the type of user—domestic (households) or non-domestic (businesses, industries, etc.). The fee consists of two components: a fixed and a variable part. Additionally in Murcia the price is further differentiated with a correction coefficient ranging from 0.5-8, based on pollution load, making use of the principle “he who pollutes more, pays more.” And following the Water Framework Directive (WFD) principle of full cost recovery (Esamur, n.d.).

Another defining factor is the pricing of different water sources. In a comparison of the prices of reclaimed water

Table 49 shows the difference between freshwater and reclaimed water in Andalusia and Murcia. As is shown the price of reclaimed water is €0.12/m³ in Andalusian and €0.07/m³ in Murcia¹³, (Interreg Europe, 2019), Andalusian having the highest price and Murcia, the lowest. The pricing difference is only 0.05€/m³ between the two regions, but the problem is that in Andalusia a lot of farmers use well water, which according to AXA¹⁴ only costs the price of electricity to pump the water, surmounting to a price of €0.05/ m³, making the reclaimed water non-competitive. The problem is that in the long term, the wells where the water is pumped from will be empty, because of the increasing water scarcity faced by these southern regions of Spain. In the region of Murcia, taxation has been implemented to further control the extraction of groundwater (Fleskens, et al., 2013), increasing the costs for these farmers. According to Interreg Europe (2019), the cost of freshwater for irrigation in Murcia is €0.2/m³, making the reclaimed water price of €0.07/m³ highly competitive. This pricing difference creates an incentive to use reclaimed water in Murcia, especially compared to Andalusia, where there is a lack of control over well water pumping. As noted in the report "Challenges of Recycled Water Pricing" (Fagundes & Marques, 2023), “Private users are not motivated to switch to recycled water if their costs are already low”. Therefore, ensuring that the price of reclaimed water is lower than other options is key to its adoption.

¹³ Data provided by AXARAGUA, 2025

¹⁴ email correspondence with Elvira from AXARAGUA

Table 49: Prices of water (Interreg Europe, A. (2019))

Pricing €/m ³	Freshwater / Well water	Reclaimed water
Murcia	0.2€/m ³	0.07€/m ³
Andalusia ¹⁵	0.05€/m ³	0.12€/m ³

Murcia and Valencia have achieved high water reuse rates through a combination of financial models. These include extensive government funding to develop and enhance infrastructure, making water reuse feasible. Similarly, in cases outside the Spanish region, governmental subsidies, reflecting the value for society and nature, have been key sources of revenue for WWTPs (Otoo et al. 2018). Additionally, they impose taxes on well water in Murcia to reduce its usage and implement cross-subsidisation through water treatment fees included in all user bills. By raising the price of well water above its actual production and distribution costs, using the extra revenue to help cover the costs of reclaimed water. This way reclaimed water can be sold at a more affordable price and become more competitive. This type of cross-subsidisation can help increase water availability (De Paoli & Mattheiss, 2016). Andalusia could adopt similar financial cross-subsidisation measures, leveraging its lower well water prices compared to Murcia and addressing the current lack of restrictions and taxes on well water extraction. With this model, Murcia has been able to reach a level of reused water so high that 64.86% of the irrigable land can use water from WWTP's (Navarro Caballero, 2018).

Additionally, some level of governmental subsidising may be needed at first, as users may not yet understand the true cost of water or the high quality of reclaimed water (Fagundes and Marques, 2023). And especially in terms of financing and building the separate piping infrastructure needed to scale the use of reclaimed water. In Andalusia the government must invests in scaling the infrastructure needed to connect WWTP's with agricultural land, because the existing piping infrastructure cannot be used for reclaimed water, because of pathogens.

The analysis of the financial models used related to reclaimed water in Murcia and Valencia, emphasises, that the cost of is shared between the government investing money and increased involvement into the reuse of water, but also the citizens and industries of the regions, by paying their sanitation fee, making it possible to fully cost recover the treatment of water at their WWTPs and in combination with well water taxation, making the price of reclaimed water competitive. In conclusion, it is crucial to design a pricing strategy that encourages the use of reclaimed water, while also meeting the goals of Article 15 in EU Directive 2024/3019, which states that all member

¹⁵ Water tariffs as provided by Axaragua

states shall systematically promote the reuse of treated wastewater, particularly in areas facing water scarcity (European Parliament and Council, 2024).

11.8 Conclusion

The Spanish pilot demonstrates a value chain in which partners collaborate to establish a circular nutrient loop, by reusing treated wastewater for agricultural purposes and linking it to food consumers – thereby closing the loop from fork to farm.

The pilot reduces wastewater discharge, lowers reliance on high energy mineral fertilisers, and expects to see a decrease in soil pollution. However, trade-offs could potentially include energy use during the treatment process and greater investment in technology. Through the strategic collaboration between BioA, AXA, AGL, TROPS, and CET the pilot has enabled the development of an integrated system, that combines a decentralised TT system with smart fertigation technology. A unique feature of the circular business model is the involvement of both public authorities, research centre, technology providers, and a potential customer of the future offering. This structure has enabled assumptions of the value creation to be continuously tested, with close and frequent communication playing a key role to overcome challenges.

The Spanish pilot addresses the pressing issues of water scarcity, nutrient pollution of nearby waters, and degradation of soil in the Axarquía region. This has led to many municipalities considering alternative sources of irrigation through the development of new water strategies.

An important driver of the CBM is related to the new Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (EU 2024/3019) which mandates TT for large WWTPs, creating regulatory pressure across the EU. This is particularly relevant in Spain, where many WWTP in Andalusia (the Spanish pilot region), have yet to fully embrace TT, unlike areas like Murcia and Valencia. Compared to these regions Andalusia shows a low reuse rate representing a substantial, untapped market opportunity.

Strengths

BioA's technology offers a competitive and tailored alternative to traditional TT upgrades. One of the aspects that distinguishes the TT unit from their competitors is their ability to design and adapt technological solutions to the specific needs of each client (e.g., quality and volume to be treated, quality to be achieved eventually, final use for reclaimed water, etc.). For WWTP operators like AXA, adopting BioA's technology may be more cost-effective than upgrading to traditional TT systems. This approach could enable them to offer high-quality reclaimed water that meets both regulatory requirements and the specific needs of farmers.

By converting secondary treated wastewater into high-quality reclaimed water and integrating a SFT (provided by AGL), BioA's reclaimed water system not only meets regulatory nutrient and pathogen requirements but also tailors the water's nutrient

content to the precise needs of crops which reduces the risk of over-fertilisation. Monitoring and control with water and nutrient use allow users to reduce costs related to well-water and conventional mineral fertilisers.

The pilot has demonstrated strong cooperation among partners, successfully integrating expertise from water engineering, data analytics, and agronomic support. The interdependence between BioA's treatment technology, AGL's monitoring tools, and TROPS' established farmer network creates a robust value chain that addresses both technical, environmental, and market demands. It must also be noted that the engagement of TROPS has created a potential to continuously test assumptions of the value created for farmers who are a critical potential customer of the technologies developed in the pilot region. Additionally, TROPS possess a crucial voice in the Spanish food industry with close relations to food retailers, which are essential to drive adoption of the agricultural products of the circular value chain.

The business model has several strengths related to value capturing. The existing system, in which users pay for water, is already well-established and requires minimal changes to accommodate payments for reclaimed water. Additionally, there is a revenue potential in offering a combined solution, as the greatest value is realised when both technologies are integrated into a combined value proposition tailored to the relevant customer segment. However, while the synergy between these technologies enhances their overall potential, it is important to recognise their independent value. Each technology can operate separately, generating revenue for the business model without relying solely on integration.

Furthermore, a viable revenue stream also depends on premium payments for sustainably produced fruit. In this regard, TROPS' strong sustainability image adds a competitive advantage to the business model, as the brand is already associated with high quality and contributions to the green transition. This established reputation not only strengthens the business model but also legitimises the collaboration of the partners.

Core strengths of the collaboration include an already established sense of trust and familiarity, as well as one partner acting as a gatekeeper toward farmers. This strengthens the collaboration by allowing other organisations to benefit from already established relationships with the targeted farmer segment.

The Spanish pilot region can drive sustainable water management and agriculture by aligning companies with suitable financing. BioA can access EU grants and loans, while AXA can benefit from long-term loans, subsidies, public-private partnerships, and green bonds. AGL can seek innovation funding and, if needed, venture capital for scaling. TROPS can support farmers to set up certification grants, blended finance, and sustainability-linked loans. As a non-profit, CET is best suited for EU and national research grants, ensuring all entities contribute to regional sustainability.

Challenges

One key challenge is the technological maturity of the SFT. Without a fully functional tool, a critical step in the value chain would be missing, impacting the overall feasibility of the solution. If no combined solution for water reclamation and smart fertigation is achieved, the benefits of integrating both technologies would be lost.

Another challenge is the occasional seawater intrusion into sewage systems causing episodes of high salinity levels of the reclaimed water. This is dependent on local conditions, and is specifically evident in the region of Axarquía, which compromise the perceived value for farmers. Many farmers, particularly those growing salt-sensitive crops such as avocados and mangoes, which dominate in the region, perceive reclaimed water as harmful, making them more reluctant to adopt the solution. This reluctance is amplified by media coverage reinforcing fears about salinity, making it harder to build trust in the solution. Since the current technology does not have the capability to effectively remove salts, the solution relies on dilution by mixing reclaimed water with well water to reach acceptable levels of salinity. However, while negative perceptions among farmers present a barrier, the general perceptions of reclaimed water are improving as the frequency of droughts and periods with water scarcity rises.

One major scalability challenge is the need to expand the existing piping infrastructure. Reclaimed water must be distributed via dedicated piping systems that cannot be mixed with other existing water sources. This means that entirely new pipes must be constructed for farmers located in areas without the necessary infrastructure, often covering considerable distances between the treatment plant and farm locations. However, due to the new Urban Wastewater Directive, the local governments of Spain are investing heavily in pipelines and other infrastructure to expand reclaimed water use, also as a means to reduce the fines paid to the EU for the discharge of polluted wastewater.

The financial burden of this infrastructure is large and typically falls beyond the capacity of individual farmers. In Andalusia, the regional government is strategically investing in new piping networks as part of its efforts to promote sustainable water use. However, the need or request from larger entities such as irrigation communities or farming cooperatives is essential to push for regional governments and municipalities to invest in these piping systems. This is crucial to expand the potential customer base of the business model. Additionally, irrigation communities must obtain legal permissions to use reclaimed water. The process of being granted such permissions depends on the river basin authority of the specific region. If these irrigation communities are located in areas without adequate piping, they are dependent on their submitted applications being approved to represent a possible customer of the business model.

Despite well water being relatively inexpensive compared to reclaimed water drought conditions significantly limit its availability. In such cases, reclaimed water becomes the only reliable option, ensuring a steady and consistent water supply. However, the

treatment technologies required to make wastewater safe for reuse in agricultural settings are inherently more expensive due to the treatment process, higher energy use, advanced monitoring, and the need for separate distribution systems. This cost factor is compounded by the low price of well water in the region, as the price of retrieving this is only based on the electricity needed to pump it from underground. Therefore, even though the region is drought prone and water is a scarce resource, when available, well water is significantly cheaper. This illustrates how the current water tariffs are largely a remnant of the past when water reservoirs were not as severely affected by scarcity, highlighting a lack of adaptation to present environmental pressures. Simultaneously, the presence of illegal wells undermines the potential of the business model, as certain irrigation communities, operating without governmental oversight, can supply themselves with inexpensive well water. Moreover, this makes the WRP an economic risk for the farmers and local communities due to the high capital costs in acquiring a WRP.

To overcome these challenges, innovative financial strategies are essential. Tariff models where well water prices are set above their production costs to help fund reclaimed water is one approach. Alternatively, subsidisation to improve farming practices will contribute to increasing the adoption of reclaimed water, while also European funds might be relevant in this relation to help digitalise agricultural practices.

These challenges highlight the technical, financial, and infrastructural hurdles that must be addressed to ensure the successful deployment and scaling of the system. At the same time, recognising and internalising the environmental and social costs associated with unsustainable well water extraction, such as aquifer depletion, ecological degradation, and longterm water scarcity, can help shift the economic logic. These costs are typically not reflected in current water tariffs but impose real burdens on the environment and future water users. By accounting for these externalities, the solutions proposed in the pilot region may emerge as competitive alternatives.

In summary, while the Spanish pilot involves high treatment and distribution costs and requires significant capital investment, the convergence of regulatory mandates, water scarcity, and technological innovation creates ground for a scalable reclaimed water model, particularly if challenges such as the salinity levels of reclaimed water and the low technological maturity of the SFT are addressed.

12 Conclusion

In task 3.1 of work package 3, the primary focus has been to identify the existence of value creation between the collaborating pilot region partners, while examining how flows of value creation become operational as an overarching method for developing CBM's for each pilot region. Building on the framework of the CBMC and relevant literature within business model development and CE, the foundational elements were established to determine which value creation parameters existed on financial, organisational, and environmental levels.

Organisational value creation

Across all pilot regions the findings indicates that organisational value creation plays a crucial role both related to the establishment and operation of a CBM. Factors that contribute to the overall success of the pilot region and enhance the competitiveness of the organisations are generated through collaboration between the partners. Synergy effects emerge through partnerships, as the individual organisations can leverage the expertise and capabilities of their partners rather than developing these internally. Moreover, since the business models are rooted in technological innovation, collaboration fosters opportunities to enhance overall value creation derived from the use of the technologies. In the North German Plain, this is illustrated by pushing the boundaries of how the technology can be installed, while in the Spanish pilot region, it is reflected in the way the technologies directly complement each other. Furthermore, across all regions, the organisations benefit from leveraging their partners' established image and reputation, which enhances the legitimacy of the solutions embedded within the business models.

It must also be emphasised that knowledge sharing is a critical factor to improving each partner's own operations and benefiting the business models as a whole. Given that these business models involve multiple stages of the circular value chain, they have provided an opportunity to better understand the needs of customers. Addressing where the value proposition falls within the overall value chain help understand the value added and how it fits into the larger scheme of value creation (Leschke 2013). For instance, in the Swedish and Spanish pilot region, direct collaboration with producers within the food industry allowed the technology providers to obtain knowledge of their needs and preferences related to crops, but also preferences of the end consumers they are serving, which contributes to identify areas for improvements in the business models. Involvement of food industry actors is similarly crucial to close the loop from farm to fork, and due to their power in the industry, where farmers are often unable to drive industry changes alone (Sivertsson et al. 2015).

Additionally, findings from the North German Plain showed a future opportunity to combine two different types of fertilisers to develop a superior product for end users. This exemplifies how knowledge sharing also serves as a foundation for product development, ultimately increasing the likelihood of market adoption for these solutions.

In total, collaboration entails that the individual partners have a stronger foundation to build upon, both in developing and operating the business model.

Environmental value creation

By collaborating on the utilisation of otherwise lost and untapped resources, the partners collectively generate a range of environmental benefits. Across all pilot regions, the most significant value is linked to avoided pollution, which manifests in various ways. It reduces the amount of nutrients entering marine environments, thereby mitigating water pollution and eutrophication. Additionally, the technologies of the different business models serve as direct substitutes for conventional treatment practices at WWTPs, which are often energy intensive and major contributors to CO₂ emissions. Furthermore, the production of locally sourced fertilisers decreases the need for long distance transportation of mineral fertilisers, further reducing environmental impact.

These environmental benefits are particularly relevant for public stakeholders and authorities and play a crucial role in demonstrating how the business models across all regions create value.

The production of biobased fertilisers also helps lower the reliance on CO₂-intensive fertilisers among farmers while also providing essential nutrients to address issues related to soil fatigue. In the Spanish pilot region, monitoring and control is an integrated part of the technological solution, contributing to prevent fertiliser overuse, which positively affects both plant health and soil agronomic conditions. At the same time, the North German Plain (and Swedish pilot region in the future) employ dry- or urine diverting toilets, contributing to freshwater conservation.

These environmental parameters collectively reduce emissions and pollution across the supply chains of the participating companies and their customers, ultimately enhancing their image. Integrating these environmental value considerations into value capturing mechanisms has been a key focus in the development of business models.

Financial value creation

As with environmental value, the primary financial value creation parameters are related to avoided pollution and thereby avoided costs. Among the partners, this relates to costs that are avoided by utilising human excreta, instead of disposing of it, which would incur disposal fees. For public authorities, financial value is generated indirectly, as they avoid the costs associated with nutrient removal during wastewater treatment processes.

Simultaneously, savings are achieved in various ways: In some instances, the technologies offer customers an alternative to being connected to public sewage systems, which typically involve upfront and ongoing costs. Additionally, for the Spanish

pilot region, direct cost savings are realised through the reduction of water and fertiliser consumption by controlling the amount of water and nutrients used for fertigation.

Across the regions, the inflow of nutrients creates opportunities for financial value creation for the technology providers who intake the roles of fertiliser producers, by providing access to an essential production input to derive commercial benefits from the nutrients. In the North German Plain region, this has involved offering users a reward mechanism designed to ensure a return on investment (ROI) for the system over a set period.

Together with environmental value creation, these types of financial benefits has proven crucial when integrating value capturing mechanisms into the business models.

Implications for the circular business model development

The development of the CBMs is closely tied to the operationalisation of the value creation achieved in the pilot regions. The CBMs have been structured around various building blocks, each contributing to one or more elements of the value dimensions of: value proposition, value creation and delivery, and value capture. Fundamentally, there are three key success factors for a CBM, referred to as the triple fit challenge (Lewandowski, 2016):

1. Fit between the value proposition and customer segments.
2. Fit between the cost structure and revenue streams.
3. Fit between CBM elements and adoption factors.

While the identification and investigation of value creation flows have contributed to understand the value propositions of the respective business models, it is common across all pilot regions that the fit with customer segments is largely based on assumptions or early indications. This means that there remains an important task in testing these assumptions in the market to ensure optimal adoption by customers.

For the fit between cost structure and revenue streams, a simple, yet incredibly challenging task exists: the costs and revenues must be balanced, and the business model should indicate possibilities for generating profit (Lewandowski et al., 2016). By utilising the technologies available in each CBM, several options related to marketing of physical products or technologies either through direct transactional sales, royalty-based payments, or licensing have been outlined in order to draw commercial benefits from the value created. Arguments for subsidies also play a vital role for the generation of sufficient revenue streams to cover capital and operational expenditures.

While a variety of possibilities have been presented related to the generation of revenue streams, two overarching challenges are significantly influencing the economic incentives and ability to capture value from the business model operations. On one

hand, the business models depend on the ability to source higher volumes of urine to reach economies of scale to drive down the prices of the products and services forming the value propositions. This is complicated since all models are currently competing against well-established large scale industries within wastewater treatment and fertiliser production.

The second challenge lies in an area that also touches upon the fit between the business model and external adoption factors. Current economic structures in society complicate financial incentives of creating circular nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) flows. This is primarily due to competition from mineral fertilisers, traditional sewage systems, and water tariffs not favouring nutrient recycling practices. Therefore, to achieve successful business models, economic incentives must be extended beyond the value capturing mechanisms of the partners, to also involve external factors such as changes in water tax legislation, the use of certifications, and public awareness campaigns aimed at educating public stakeholders and consumers.

Given that the business models compete against well established political and economic systems, which are often subsidised by political entities, there is a significant need to collaborate with public actors and authorities to increase the likelihood of solution adoption. The challenge also lies in the fact that the involved technologies can be characterised as radical innovations based on proprietary technology, rather than incremental innovations with minor improvements to existing products (Abetti, 2000). These challenges the current systems and attempts to radically transform the way we approach the utilisation of human excreta for fertilisation purposes. Thus, a more comprehensive shift of the legislative frameworks is needed to support the adoption of the CBMs.

Recognising and internalising the environmental and social costs associated with conventional fertilisers and linear wastewater systems, such as nutrient runoff, water contamination, greenhouse gas emissions, soil degradation, and aquifer depletion, can help shift the economic balance in favour of circular solutions. These external costs are not reflected in current market pricing structures but represent significant long term societal burdens. By accounting for these externalities, the solutions proposed in the pilot regions may emerge as competitive alternatives. Such internalisation strengthens the business case for circular systems and reinforces the need for supportive regulatory and fiscal frameworks to foster adoption at scale.

13 References

- Abetti, P. A. (2000). Critical Success Factors for Radical Technological Innovation: A Five Case Study. *Creativity and Innovation Management*, vol. 9 no. 4, A 208-221.
- Aliahmad, A., Kanda, W., & McConville, J. (2023). Urine recycling: Diffusion barriers and upscaling potential; Case studies from Sweden and Switzerland. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 414, 137583. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.137583>
- Anderson, J. C., & Narus, J. A. (1998). Business marketing: Understand what customers value. *Harvard Business Review*, 76(6), 53-65.
- Antikainen, M., & Valkokari, K. (2016). A framework for sustainable circular business model innovation. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 6(7), 5-12.
- Attanasio, G., Preghenella, N., De Toni, A. F., & Battistella, C. (2021). Stakeholder engagement in business models for sustainability: The stakeholder value flow model for sustainable development. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 31(3), 860-874.
- Badeti, U., Jiang, J., Kumarasingham, S., Almunashiri, A., Pathak, N. K., Chanan, A., Freguia, S., Ang, W. L., Ghaffour, N., Shon, H. K., & Phuntsho, S. (2024). Source separation of urine and treatment: Impact on energy consumption, greenhouse gas emissions, and volumetric nitrification rate. *Desalination*, 560, 116012. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0011916424003448>
- Beneker, G., Gonzáles, P., Parfitt, S., & Senecal, D. (2023). Progress in setup of pilot regions. *P2Green Consortium*. Accessible at p2green.eu
- Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation. (2019). Creating the Path to Profitability for the Reinvented Toilet – Business Model Options and Strategic Considerations. *Gates Open Res*, 3: 1713
- Bocken, N., Short, S. W., Rana, P., & Evans, S. (2014). A literature and practice review to develop sustainable business model archetypes. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 65, 42-56.
- Bocken, N., Rana, P., & Short, S. W. (2015). Value mapping for sustainable business thinking. *Journal of Industrial and Production Engineering*, 31(1), 67-81.
- BREEAM. (2025). Achieve your net zero goals with BREEAM certification. Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method, retrieved April 10, 2025 from: <https://breeam.com/about/>
- Britannica. (2025). *Gotland*. Encyclopedia Britannica. Retrieved January 29, 2025, from <https://www.britannica.com/place/Baltic-Sea>

Cabezas, E. (2022). Record drop forecast as Axarquía's drought-hit avocado harvest gets under way. *SUR in English*. Retrieved January 2025, from <https://www.surinenglish.com/malaga/axarquia/cent-decline-expected-20221121152418-nt.html>

Cabezas, E. (2024a). Environmentalists warn against the 'agricultural extractivism' of Malaga's subtropical crops. *SUR in English*. <https://www.surinenglish.com/environment/20240129-agricultural-extractivism-malaga>

Cabezas, E. (2024b). Malaga's mango harvest ends with 25 percent more fruit than expected. *SUR in English*. <https://www.surinenglish.com/environment/20240129-mango-harvest-malaga>

Cabezas, E. (2024c). Mango harvest gets underway in east of Malaga province with a drop of 70 percent forecast. *SUR in English*. <https://www.surinenglish.com/environment/20240129-mango-harvest-east-malaga>

Carstensen, J., Andersen, J. H., Gustafsson, B. G., & Conley, D. J. (2014). Deoxygenation of the Baltic Sea during the last century. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 111(15), 5628–5633. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1323156111>

Casadesus-Masanell, R., & Ricart, J. (2014). How to design a winning business model. *Harvard Business Review*. <https://hbr.org/2011/01/how-to-design-a-winning-business-model>

Chertow, M., & Ehrenfeld, J. (2012). Organizing self-organizing systems: Toward a theory of industrial symbiosis. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 16(1).

Coates, J., & Knezovich, J. (2020). Make way for the future of sanitation: A review of new enterprise models shaping the development of a transformational sanitation economy. *Ernst & Young (EY)*. Retrieved January 29, 2025 from: <http://www.toiletboard.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/2020-ey-tbc-make-way-for-the-future-of-sanitation.pdf>

Conley, D. J., Carstensen, J., Aigars, J., Axe, P., Bonsdorff, E., Eremina, T., Haahti, B. M., Humborg, C., Jonsson, P., Kotta, J., Lännegren, C., Larsson, U., Maximov, A., Medina, M. R., Lysiak-Pastussak, E., Remeikaitė-Nikienė, N., Walve, J., Wilhelms, S., & Sillén, L. (2011). Hypoxia is increasing in the coastal zone of the Baltic Sea. *Environmental Science and Technology*, 45(16), 6777-6783.

Danmarks Nationalleksikon. Valeur, B., et al. (2024). *Gotland*. Retrieved January 29, 2025, from <https://lex.dk/Gotland>

Departamento de Fruticultura Tropical, V. Galán Saúco. (2005). Tropical and subtropical fruits in Spain. *Instituto Canario de Investigaciones*. Retrieved January 11, 2025, from [\(PDF\) Tropical and subtropical fruits in Spain](#)

De Paoli, G., & Mattheiss, V. (2016). Cost, pricing, and financing of water reuse against natural water resources. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12270.41289>

DIRECTIVE (EU) 2024/3019 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 27 November 2024 concerning urban wastewater treatment (recast) (Text with EEA relevance). (2024). *Official Journal of the European Union*. Retrieved January 29, 2025, from <http://data.europa.eu/eli/C/2023/250/oj>

Ellen MacArthur Foundation. (2014), Towards the circular economy Vol. 3: accelerating the scale-up across global supply chains .Retrieved march 23, 2025, from <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/towards-the-circular-economy-vol-3-accelerating-the-scale-up-across-global>

Ellen MacArthur Foundation. (2015). Towards a circular economy: Business rationale for an accelerated transition. *Ellen MacArthur Foundation*.

Ellen MacArthur Foundation. (2016). WORKSHEET Business Model Canvas. The Circular Design Guide. *Ellen MacArthur Foundation*. Retrieved January 23, 2025, from <https://emf.thirdlight.com/link/tsb3y1er2tg1-iebwi8/@/preview/1?q>

Ellen MacArthur Foundation. (2023a). How does the circular economy create value? *Ellen MacArthur Foundation*. Retrieved August 14, 2024, from <https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/how-does-the-circular-economy-create-value>

Ellen MacArthur Foundation. (2023b). The circular economy in detail. *Ellen MacArthur Foundation*. Retrieved August 17, 2024, from <https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/the-circular-economy-in-detail-deep-dive>

Ellen MacArthur Foundation. (2023c). What is the linear economy? *Ellen MacArthur Foundation*. Retrieved December 16, 2024, from [What is the linear economy?](#)

Ellen MacArthur Foundation. (2024a). Circular economy principles. *Ellen MacArthur Foundation*. Retrieved December 16, 2024, from <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/circular-economy-principles>

Ellen MacArthur Foundation. (2024b). 3. Create the conditions for collaboration. *Ellen MacArthur Foundation*. Retrieved January 29, 2025, from <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/adaptive-strategy-for-circular-design/collaborations>

Esamur. (n.d.). *Canon de saneamiento*. Entidad de Saneamiento y Depuración de la Región de Murcia. Retrieved March 13, 2025, from <https://www.esamur.com/canon-de-saneamiento>

EPSAR. (n.d.). Funciones. *Entidad Pública de Saneamiento de Aguas Residuales*. Retrieved March 5, 2025, from <https://www.epsar.gva.es/epsar/funciones>

European Commission. (n.d.a). Circular economy action plan. *European Commission*. Retrieved January 22, 2025, from https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/circular-economy-action-plan_en

European Commission. (n.d.b). Implementing circular economy for nutrient recovery in urban wastewater treatment plants. *European Commission*. Retrieved January 22, 2025, from https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/urban-environment/european-green-capital-award/implementing-circular-economy-nutrient-recovery-urban-wastewater-treatment-plants_en

European Commission. (n.d.c). Water reuse. Retrieved April 3rd, 2025, from https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/water/water-reuse_en

European Commission. (2019). Market briefs: Fertilisers (June 2019). European Union. retrieved 24.03.2025 from: https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2019-07/market-brief-fertilisers_june2019_en_0.pdf

European Environment Agency. (2024). Population connected to at least secondary wastewater treatment (Indicator). Retrieved March 24, 2025, from <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/european-zero-pollution-dashboards/indicators/population-connected-to-at-least-secondary-wastewater-treatment>

European Investment Bank, & Knight, C. (2023). What is the linear economy? *European Investment Bank*. Retrieved January 29, 2025, from <https://www.eib.org/en/stories/linear-economy-recycling>

Euro Weekly News. (2024). Murcia leads the charge: National water plan. Euro Weekly News. Retrieved March 5, 2025, from <https://euoweeklynews.com/2024/05/20/murcia-leads-the-charge-national-water-plan/>

Fagundes, T. S., & Marques, R. C. (2023). Challenges of recycled water pricing. *Utilities Policy*, 82, 101569. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jup.2023.101569>

Fleskens, L., Nainggolan, D., Termansen, M., Hubacek, K., & Reed, M. S. (2013). Regional consequences of the way land users respond to future water availability in Murcia, Spain. *Regional Environmental Change*, 13(3), 615–632.

Tristan Martin. L'urine humaine en agriculture: des filières variées pour contribuer à une fertilisation azotée durable. Alimentation et Nutrition. Université Paris-Saclay, 2020. Français. Retrieved March 27, 2025 from <https://pastel.hal.science/tel-03350482/document>

United Nations. (n.d.). *Capacity building*. Retrieved 27.03.2025 from <https://www.un.org/en/academic-impact/capacity-building>

Ganguly, A., & Euchner, J. (2018). *Conducting business experiments*. *Research-Technology Management*, 61(2), 27-36.
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/08956308.2018.1421381>

Goldeimer (nd.). "Alle für Klos! Klos für alle!" Retrieved April 3, 2025, from <https://goldeimer.de/>

Geissdoerfer, M., Pieroni, M. P. P., Pigosso, D. C. A., & Soufani, K. (2020). Circular business models: A review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 277, 123741.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.123741>

German Environmental Agency (UBA). (2017). Gewässer in Deutschland: Zustand und Bewertung. Retrieved February 5, 2025, from https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/377/publikationen/171018_uba_gewasserd_t_l_engl_bf.pdf

GlobalG.A.P. (No date). Impact areas and claims. *GlobalG.A.P.*, retrieved April 10, 2025 from: <https://www.globalgap.org/about/impact-areas-and-claims/>

Guldmann, E. (2016). *Best practice examples of circular business models*. Danish Environmental Protection Agency. Retrieved 03.04.2025 from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321764939_Best_Practice_Examples_of_Circular_Business_Models

Hagenvoort, J., Ortega-Reig, M., Botella, S., García, C., de Luis, A., & Palau-Salvador, G. (2019). Reusing Treated Waste-Water from a Circular Economy Perspective—The Case of the Real Acequia de Moncada in Valencia (Spain). *Water*, 11(9), 1830.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/w11091830>

Hoogesteger, J., Bolding, A., Sanchis-Ibor, C., Veldwisch, G. J., Venot, J.-P., Vos, J., & Boelens, R. (2023). Communalities in farmer managed irrigation systems: Insights from Spain, Ecuador, Cambodia and Mozambique. *Agricultural Systems*, 204, 103552

Interreg Europe, A. (2019). A1.2 Final report on AQUARES region's needs and opportunities in water reuse.

Internet Archive: Wayback Machine. (2011). *Anuario Económico de España 2011*.

Retrieved January 11, 2025, from

https://web.archive.org/web/20120620123757/http://www.anuarioeco.lacaixa.comunicacions.com/java/X?cgi=caixa.le_menuGeneral.pattern

Joyce, A. (2017). Co-creation and Design Thinking to Envision More Sustainable Business Models: A Foresight Design Approach for Organizational Sustainability of SME Manufacturers. In: Bellemare, J., Carrier, S., Nielsen, K., Piller, F.T. (eds) *Managing Complexity*. Springer Proceedings in Business and Economics. Springer, Cham.

Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2016). *Marketing Management - Global Edition*. Harlow: Pearson Education Limited.

LEAF. (No date). About LEAF Marque. Linking Environment And Farming, retrieved April 10, 2025, from <https://leaf.eco/leafmarque/about>

Lewandowski, M. (2016). Designing the business models for circular economy—Towards the conceptual framework. *Sustainability*, 8(43).

Leflaive, X., & Hjort, M. (2020). Addressing the social consequences of tariffs for water supply and sanitation (Environment Working Paper No. 166). *OECD, Environment Directorate*. <https://one.oecd.org/document/ENV/WKP%282020%2913/en/pdf>

Leschke, J. (2013). Business model mapping: A new tool to encourage entrepreneurial activity and accelerate new venture creation. *Journal of Marketing Development and Competitiveness*, 7(1), 18-26. Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/business-model-mapping-new-tool-encourage/docview/1462032076/se-2>

Ministerio de Ciencia. (No date). European Regional Development Fund (FEDER). *Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovación y Universidades*, retrieved April 10, 2025, from: <https://www.ciencia.gob.es/en/Estrategias-y-Planes/Fondo-Europeo-de-Desarrollo-Regional-FEDER.html>

Mohamed, A. M. O., & Bicer, Y. (2022). Computational exploration of adsorption enhanced Haber-Bosch using MOFs and ionic liquid/MOFs. In *Computer Aided Chemical Engineering* (Vol. 50). Elsevier.

National Water Strategy. (2023). National Water Strategy: Federal Environment Ministry draft summary. *Bundesministerium für Umwelt, Naturschutz und nukleare Sicherheit*. Retrieved May 21, 2025, from [National Water Strategy](#)

Navarro Caballero, T. M. (2018). Water reuse and desalination in Spain – Challenges and opportunities. *Journal of Water Reuse and Desalination*, 8, 10.2166/wrd.2018.043.

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Nieto-López, J. M., Mudarra-Martínez, M., & Andreo, B. (2021). Advances in science, technology & innovation (pp. 109–113). *Springer*.https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-59320-9_24

Nußholz, J. (2017). Circular business models: Defining a concept and framing an emerging research field. *Sustainability*, 9(10), 1810.

Nußholz, J. (2018). A circular business model mapping tool for creating value from prolonged product lifetime and closed material loops. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 197, 185–194.

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0959652618319061?via%3Dihub>

Okendo, A. (2024). Navigating the export avocado value chain: A blueprint for sustainable growth. *Agri Frontier*. Retrieved January 29, 2025, from [Navigating the Export Avocado Value Chain: A Blueprint for Sustainable Growth - Agri Frontier](#)

Osterwalder, A., & Pigneur, Y. (2010). Business model generation. *John Wiley & Sons Inc.*

Osarenkhoe, A., & Fjellström, D. (2017). Clusters' vital role in promoting international competitive advantage: Towards an explanatory model of regional growth. *International Journal of Business and Society*, retrieved December 13, 2014 from

<https://www.redalyc.org/journal/289/28966569009/html/>

Otoo, M., & Drechsel, P. (2018). Resource recovery from waste: business models for energy, nutrients and water reuse. Routledge.

P2GreenN. (2023a). Closing the gap between fork and farm for circular nutrient flows. P2Green Project PDF.

P2GreenN. (2023b). Learn more about the project. P2GreenN. Retrieved January 22, 2025, from <https://p2green.eu/about/>

P2GreenN Project. (n.d.). Pilot regions. P2GreenN. <https://p2green.eu/pilot-regions/>

Peters, G., & Thompson, R. L. (2020). Nitrous oxide: A potent, long-lived, and rapidly increasing greenhouse gas. CICERO Center for International Climate Research. <https://cicero.oslo.no/en/articles/nitrous-oxide-a-potent-long-lived-and-rapidly-increasing-greenhouse-gas>

Rao, K. C., Kvarnström, E., Di Mario, L., Drechsel, P. (2016). Business models for faecal sludge management. Colombo, Sri Lanka: International Water Management Institute (IWMI). CGIAR Research Program on Water, Land and Ecosystems (WLE). 80p. (Resource Recovery and Reuse Series 6). Retrieved January 29, 2025 from <https://www.iwmi.org/news/resource-recovery-reuse-6/>

Reijnders, L. (2014). Phosphorus resources, their depletion and conservation: A review. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 93, 32-49.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2014.09.006>

Rodríguez-Villanueva, P., & Sauri, D. (2021). Wastewater Treatment Plants in Mediterranean Spain: An Exploration of Relations between Water Treatments, Water Reuse, and Governance. Retrieved from <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4441/13/12/1710>

Rethink Action. (n.d.). European Union's Horizon Gotland, Sweden Northern Area case study. *Rethink Action*. Retrieved January 29, 2025, from

<https://rethinkaction.eu/cases/gotland-sweden/>

Richardson, J. (2008). The business model: An integrative framework for strategy execution. *Strategic Change*, 17, 133-144.

Ritala, P., Albareda, L., & Bocken, N. (2021). Value creation and appropriation in economic, social, and environmental domains: Recognizing and resolving the institutionalized asymmetries. *Journal of Cleaner Production*.

REGULATION (EU) 2020/741 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 25 May 2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse (Text with EEA relevance). (2020). *Official Journal of the European Union*.

Schremmer, M. (2022). "Blog: Goldeimer Trockenklos auf Events – warum wir so viele Anfragen ablehnen müssen", Goldeimer.de. Retrieved April 3rd 2025 from

<https://goldeimer.de/blogs/blog/festivaltrockenklos-vermietung>

Sivertsson, O., & Tell, J. (2015). Barriers to Business Model Innovation in Swedish Agriculture. *Sustainability*, 7(2), 1957-1969. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su7021957>

Stewart, W. M., & Roberts, T. L. (2012). Food security and the role of fertilizer in supporting it. *Procedia Engineering*, 46, retrieved 3rd of April, 2025 from:

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2012.09.015>

SuWaNu Europe. (n.d.b). State of play analyses for Andalusia, Spain. *SuWaNu Europe*.

SuWaNu Europe. (n.d.c). SWOT and PEST analyses for implementation of reuse practices in Andalusia, Spain. *SuWaNu Europe*.

Stuber, M. (2023). Drought and lack of irrigation water massively hits mango and avocado harvest in Malaga. *SUR in English*. Retrieved January 11, 2025, from [Drought and lack of irrigation water massively hits mango and avocado harvest in Malaga province | Sur in English](#)

Simha, P., & Ganesapillai, M. (2017). Ecological sanitation and nutrient recovery from human urine: How far have we come? *Sustainable Environment Research*, 27(3), 107–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.serj.2016.12.001>

Umweltbundesamt. (2017). Wasserwirtschaft in Deutschland: Grundlagen, Belastungen, Maßnahmen (Aktualisierte Webversion). Umweltbundesamt. From https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/1410/publikationen/uba_wasserwirtschaft_in_deutschland_2017_web_aktualisiert.pdf

VunaNexus. (n.d.). From research to market-ready solutions. *VunaNexus*. Retrieved January 29, 2025, from <https://www.vunanexus.com/technology>

Venanzi, D. (2012). Financial performance measures and value creation: The state of the art. Springer. Retrieved December 13, 2024 from http://dspace.kottakalfarookcollege.edu.in:8001/jspui/bitstream/123456789/4815/1/Venanzi2012_Book_FinancialPerformanceMeasuresAn.pdf

Wettengel, J. (2024). Water conflicts to intensify in Germany due to climate change – Report. *Clean Energy Wire*. Retrieved January 21, 2025, from <https://www.cleanenergywire.org/news/water-conflicts-intensify-germany-due-climate-change-report>

14 Appendices

Appendix I: Circular Business Model Canvas: Gotland Pilot Region

Appendix II: Circular Business Model Canvas: VunaNexus, German Pilot Region

Appendix III: Circular Business Model Canvas: Goldeimer, German pilot region

Appendix IV: Circular Business Model Canvas: Axarquía pilot region

<p>Key Partners (and resources acquired)</p> <p>Pilot region partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bosch (Black) Technology partner Analytics (AGL) Technology provider Auragrip (AMA) and WWT operator TRIPS (TRIPS) Farmer cooperative and agronomical advisor CETAQIA (GET) Research and scientific insights <p>Key suppliers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Irrigation communities Water utilities Equipment suppliers for WBP Equipment suppliers of SF <p>Value Proposition</p> <p>Water Reclamation Plant (WRP)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Installation and maintenance of tertiary water treatment for reclaimed water production <p>Smart Fertigation Tool (SFT)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electronic sensors and cloud-based software for fertigation control <p>Water reclamation and joint fertigation services</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complete fertigation management system combining reclaimed water production with nutrient control <p>Advocates and mangas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> High-quality avocados & mangas cultivated with reclaimed water 	<p>Key Activities</p> <p>Upstream</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collection of sewage from municipality (AMA) Primary and secondary treatment of wastewater (AMA) Production Transportation of secondary wastewater (Black) Transportation of reclaimed water via pipelines for irrigation users (Black) Measurements of nutrient content/levels of reclaimed water, plants and soil (AGL) Automatic adaptation of recycled water to fit with agronomic needs based on agronomic systems (AGL) <p>Downstream</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fertigation of mangas and avocados (TRIPS) Marketing and advertising of sustainable agriculture (TRIPS) After sales technical service advice (Bos) Marketing and advertising of sustainable agriculture (TRIPS) <p>Key Resources</p> <p>Physical resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Production facility for technology production (Black) (AGL) Piping infrastructure Deposit tanks and mixing units (Black) (AGL) <p>Human resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Commercial personnel (Bos) (AGL) Developers and software engineers (AGL) Proprietary knowledge (Black) (AGL) (TRIPS) Proprietary knowledge (TRIPS) (TRIPS) Proprietary knowledge (TRIPS) (TRIPS) Proprietary knowledge (TRIPS) (TRIPS) Proprietary knowledge (TRIPS) (TRIPS) <p>Financial resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU- and regional funds (all consortium partners) Funds from established businesses (all consortium partners) 	<p>Customer Relationships</p> <p>Water Reclamation Plant</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Block providing commercial personnel for advertising and participation in relevant networks Block providing sales and marketing support for the promotion of new stations AMA TRIPS communicating about sustainable agricultural practices <p>Smart Fertigation Tool</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automated services for seamless experience with minimal need of personal assistance. Co-creation for generation of customized solution, personal assistance for maintenance, automated services for seamless experience. <p>Advocates and mangas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Date-driven and trust relationships, with pull-effects from strong brand equity. <p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Building awareness Block providing commercial personnel for advertising and participation in relevant networks AMA TRIPS communicating about sustainable agricultural practices Enabling evaluation CET providing scientific analysis for assessment of functionality and safety Third-party certification (still missing) providing environmental information Purchase and distribution Block commercial personnel providing sales activities TRIPS providing external sales channels to reach end-consumers TRIPS facilitating sales and distribution through retailer-relationships TRIPS providing externally owned sales channels to reach end-consumers Value delivery and after sales support Block providing water engineering to customize offerings. Block providing maintenance and after-sales services. 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <p>Customers of Water Reclamation Plants</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public water authorities Municipalities, landscape organizations, golf courses <p>Customers of Smart Fertigation Tool</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Individual farmers Farming cooperatives <p>Customers of water reclamation and joint fertigation services</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Farming cooperatives Farming cooperatives <p>Customers of avocados and mangas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food retailers Supermarkets
<p>Cost Structure</p> <p>Main tasks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water reclamation reactor (including design and engineering) Reactor repair and maintenance (including personnel costs, consumables, spare parts, and electricity) Mixing station equipment Mixing station FTE <p>Environmental negatives</p> <p>Energy costs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of non-renewable energy to construct WRP and build pipeline infrastructure. <p>Supply chain risks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sea intrusion from pipes posing environmental and agricultural threats of using reclaimed water. <p>Over-application of nutrients</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Without the use of the SFT, irrigation users risk over-applying nutrients, leading to negative environmental and agricultural impacts. 	<p>Revenue Streams</p> <p>Reclaimed water tariffs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Payments of reclaimed water use (from irrigation users to AMA) <p>Sales of WRP</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transaction asset sales with WWP (customers to Bos) Transaction asset sales with WWP (customers to Bos) <p>Water engineering services</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Subscription fees to gain access to WWP (customers to Bos) Subscription fees to gain access to WWP (customers to Bos) <p>Environmental positives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Preventing over-application of nutrients and reducing contamination of soil Reducing application of groundwater Minimizing nutrient runoff to protect streams and phosphates entering drinking water supplies of groundwater Improved condition of natural habitats Increased water flows and groundwater levels to enhance conditions of nearby wetland and natural habitats as a side-effect of using reclaimed water 	<p>Revenue Streams</p> <p>Reporting services</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Block in maintenance contracts for SFT services <p>Collaborative offering</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Asset and service sales with subsequent internal items-payments (irrigation users to Bos and onto AGL) <p>Final sales</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Block providing maintenance and after-sales services. <p>Environmental positives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced water pollution Mitigating outflows of nutrient-rich wastewater to Mediterranean Sea Reducing water pollution, better practices Reducing the need for phosphate extraction and production of energy intensive mineral fertilizers. 	

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